

3.I^M: An Interpretable Dynamical AI Agent

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Abstract—Developmental Psychology has been used in conjunction with the algorithmic and/or dynamical methods to design AI agents, as it deals with human cognitive development from birth. When applied, the conjunction with the algorithmic method can build interpretable AI agents (have humanly comprehensible processes and characteristics) through the use of concept-representing symbols. It, however, leads to symbol-grounding and/or other problems that offset its merit in interpretability, which may facilitate the creation of human intelligence-level AGI. On the other hand, the conjunction with the dynamical method emphasises the design of AI agents on the real-time unfolding of processes internal to, and in the interactions with the environment of, these agents. However, its related literature is dominated by work on uninterpretable AI agents. Also, none of the current literature on the combination of Developmental Psychology with the hybrid of the two methodologies deals with the resolution of all the mentioned deficiencies.

Thus, the novel AI agent 3.I^M is presented in this paper, and modelled as a set of dynamical difference equations containing mathematical operators acting on information, some of which are derived from its interactions with an artificial environment. The operators are inspired by Developmental Psychology, represent concepts, and belong to an algebra and a measure. They facilitate 3.I^M interpretability, as demonstrated in the analytical investigations into the computer simulation-confirmed cognitive abilities (e.g., the generalization and fusion of the information) of 3.I^M, and into the dynamics of the information attribute inspired by the nature of human consciousness. The dynamics is one of the major 3.I^M features envisioned as necessary to create the future developmental AGI version of 3^M, i.e., the abstract base class of 3.I^M.

Index Terms—Mathematical operator, Dynamical, Developmental Psychology, Interpretability, Consciousness, AGI

I. INTRODUCTION

Developmental Psychology includes the study of the cognitive development of humans over their progression in life. It is employed to determine the cognitive components from which complex mental concepts are formed over time [1], a type of development process foundational to the set of AI design principles referred to as, 3^M. Some of these components may be responsible for: the recognition by 2-month-old infants of uncommon contingencies of physical objects [2]; the comparison of physical objects by 4 to 6-month-old infants, evident in their longer stare at the object with unexpected orientation than at the same object but with expected orientation [3]; the differentiation of human intentions by 6-month-old infants [4]; and the association of physical objects (e.g., the association of a dog to its owner) by infants at 8 months old [5].

The cognitive abilities of infants are considered in Sloutsky’s “three core assumptions: that the only building blocks for words and concepts are sensory and perceptual experiences,

that these experiences are operated upon strictly by means of general-purpose processes (including associative learning, similarity assessment, and attentional weighting), and that higher level conceptual processes are unnecessary to account for the evidence from children” p3 [6]. The assumptions were supported by the implication of Spelke [1] that infants have antecedent fundamental knowledge (e.g., prediction ability) from which their cognition develops. However, they were countered by Waxman and Gelman based on the premise that the ability to associate is insufficient for children to form words in human language [6]. Despite the debate over them, their mathematical connotation makes them the basis for defining the mathematical operators inherent to the version of 3^M denoted as, 3.I^M. Thus, 3.I^M has initial information content, i.e., akin to human neonates [7]–[9]. It is a dynamical AI system; a kind of system explored next, followed by the discussions on the algorithmic methodology, the dynamical-algorithmic hybrid technique, and finally 3.I^M.

A. Dynamical Method

The cognitive system of infants is hypothesized as dynamical, i.e., its processes may unfold in real time [10]. If this hypothesis is true, the strategy of applying mathematical tools to describe and investigate the time-evolution of the human cognitive system (e.g., in Dynamical System Theory [11]) is more appropriate than the algorithmic method [12]. To name a few, the dynamical approach to cognition is applied in: (a) designing a stack of connected feedback control blocks whose afferent and efferent information they abstract at an increasing degree according to their stack level starting from the bottom [13]; (b) modelling artificial neural network (ANN) dynamics using stochastic differential equations [14]–[17]; (c) investigating the patterns of human sensory stimulation dependence on his/her sensori-motor activities using a control engineering approach that employs block diagrams and coupled, linear, and time-invariant differential equations [18]; (d) investigating human memory recall and attention dynamics using Complex System Theory [19]; (e) and constructing the Unlimited Computable AI [20] by approximating the non-computable AIXI [21], which involves reinforcement learning and theoretically could output its best action in any previously known or unknown environmental scenario it encounters. However, reinforcement learning-based AIs are reflexive but without the reflective character that is vital in robotics [22].

Some dynamical AI agents have uninterpretable dynamics and learned concepts (e.g., those represented by the transition probabilities in AIRL agents, and by the phase space attractors and trajectories in the solutions to the ANN differential

equations [10]), thereby compounding the analytical challenge of their investigations. The uninterpretability: (a) is believed to impede the creation of human intelligence-level AIs even after decades of research [23]; (b) renders the dynamical AI design method unsuitable for modelling reasoning and abstract concepts [24] [25]; (c) cannot provide the assurance that any deep ANN will abide by rules critical in risky applications, e.g., driverless cars [26]; (d) brings about the incomplete understanding of the finite-width deep ANN pre-training technique effectiveness, and of the seeming irrelevance of the unsupervised training phase of convolutional deep ANN [27].

There are several methods to increase learned concept interpretability in dynamical AI agents [28], [29], such as: (a) Principal Component Analysis applied to the sub-symbolic representations in ANN [30]; (b) the application of an extremely wide hidden layer of deep ANN [31]; (c) Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations (LIME) that create a proxy interpretable model by selectively inputting information to the uninterpretable proxied AI agent to determine which of the inputs are responsible for the agent's character of interest [32]; (d) and Generalized Additive Models (GAM)s that limit inter-feature interaction in single-feature AI models to elucidate each feature [33].

There are interpretable dynamical AI agents, e.g.: the Enhanced Turing Machine that utilizes concept-representing ungrounded symbols manipulated through predefined rules in response to symbolic environmental objects sequenced on the machine's tape [34], [35]; and the Quantum Probability Theory cognitive model, whose concept-based ungrounded operators affect the time-dependent transformation of its mental states [36]. The interpretable dynamical Transparent Neural Networks (TNN) [37] are constituted of graphs (with connections and nodes, some of which contain ANN) modifiable by operators (some are algorithmic and have undefined algebra) that are inspired by neurobiology but not Developmental psychology under which they are trained. Thus, interpretable dynamical AI agents established from the principles of Developmental Psychology (whose use for training AI agents is not considered foundational) are absent from the literature.

B. Algorithmic Method

Unlike the dynamical approach to AI design, the algorithmic method implements cognition-related processes as algorithms executed within a contingent time period. It is applied to design: (a) the Piagetian system of [38] that employs the fundamental data structure, referred to as monad, that can represent an operation or concept; (b) the Novamente AI engine [39] that employs algorithms to train simulated android agents according to the Piagetian theory on learning [40]; (c) the developmental robot NICO [41] that is flexible to design, is classified as fully algorithmic when its dynamical environment interface is not considered, and interacts with humans in various modalities (e.g., facial, visual and auditory); (d) and, the iCub humanoid developmental robot that, as with NICO, is also classified as fully algorithmic. It is animated through the algorithm library, called YARP, which includes

Developmental Psychology-inspired modules [42], [43] responsible for its actions, such as; reaching and grasping, the neonate-exhibited gaze, spinal behaviour, and eye movement [44]. Although, iCub periodically senses and reacts to its environment, however, its algorithmic processes (e.g., reasoning) are unsynchronized to the rhythm of, and incompatible to integrate with, its low-level dynamical physical components (e.g., motors and mechanical joints) [45] that may process dynamical environmental signals [10] (e.g., audio and video).

This type of incompatibility also prevails in algorithmic method-designed interpretable AI agents that, however, "can almost be characterized by the long list of things that are Somebody Else's Problem." p3 [12] (e.g., the symbol-grounding problem [46]). Further, the algorithmic AI design method inherently requires predefined rules (e.g., for symbolic manipulation), resulting in the designed AI agents being less adaptive to the changes in their respective environments [47].

Examples of these rules are for: the propositional logic operators, which are convenient for analytical proofs; the set connector and similarity copula in NARS [48]; the "has-part" connective operator in MicroPsi [49]; the tensor product operator used to arrange words in the semantic analysis [50]; the operators which build data structures in SOAR [51]; and the symmetry-based operator of CSE [52] that segregates sensory information sequences. However, Developmental Psychology-inspired operators in an algebra are absent in the literature.

C. Hybrid Methods

The hybrid of dynamical and algorithmic design methodologies is applied to the creation of AI agents such as psyNet [39], [53], [54] and the following developmental robots: (a) The Magellan Pro robot [55] internally executes algorithmic processes, for example, to track over time the information on a moving physical object it perceives. The dynamics of its physical state and perceived information are modelled with simultaneous difference equations which encode uninterpretable learned concepts. And its knowledge is represented by a mathematical tuple (akin to $3.I^M$) but not acted upon by mathematical operators (different from $3.I^M$). (b) The MDB robot learns in real-time and continually and autonomously adapts to its environment by evolving its ANN-constituted models using Evolutionary Algorithm [56]. (c) The NAO robot [57] learns its movements through the dynamical differential equation model of the movement-generating cortex-basal ganglia circuit in humans, where the equation contains a non-linear function whose parameters are found through the Natural-Actor-Critic algorithm.

These enumerated robots have uninterpretable learned concepts, and algorithmic components that do not execute in real-time. Thus, the dynamical and algorithmic hybrid approach used to design them does not resolve the aforementioned pitfalls of either or both of the approaches.

D. The $3.I^M$ AI agent

The above discussions support Developmental Psychology as a vital design principle for the possible creation of human-level AGI agents. For example, if the aforementioned Sloutsky

assumptions are true, then it could be possible to build a developmental AGI agent capable of autonomously learning all concepts and henceforth attaining human-level intelligence. Now, if the human somato-cognitive system is indeed dynamical (as proposed in [10]), then the AGI agent may well be dynamical as well. However, even being a dynamical system, if the AGI agent has uninterpretable learned concepts, then the aspired intelligence level may be untenable [23]. Therefore, if a human-level AGI agent is to be created, arguably, it has to be dynamical, interpretable, and designed according to the principles of Developmental Psychology.

Thus, this paper presents the novel AI agent $3.I^M$ modelled as coupled dynamical difference equations. These equations contain mathematical operators inspired by the Sloutsky assumptions and act on *sensations* (the agent's somatosensations and perceived environmental information), i.e., akin to the operators in the algorithmic CSE [52]. The operators facilitate interpretable concept-representation and promote the analytical investigation of the cognitive abilities of, and the information dynamics in, $3.I^M$. They are part of the algebra and measure utilized in $3.I^M$, thereby 3^M stands for the Mathematical Model of a Mind. Through them, the investigations of $3.I^M$ do not require error-accumulating numerical solution (e.g., the Runge-Kutta method [58]), and avoid the extreme challenge of solving non-linear differential/difference equations such as those found in some dynamical cognition models presented in Section I-A. Their utilization is a form of reductionist methodology, which is viewed by Quine [59] as being lacking in explanatory potency. However, considering the ubiquity of reductionist methodology in various fields of study (e.g., Physics and Chemistry), reductionism is chosen as one of the guiding design principles of $3.I^M$.

In the $3.I^M$ design, its operators act on information defined as a mathematical tuple (analogous to that of the Magellan Pro robot [55] and the monad in the Piagetian system cited in Item I-B.a), inspired by the occurrence probability of a stochastic neural network activation state being the dependent variable of the Fokker-Plank equation [60] corresponding to the stochastic differential equation of the network, e.g., Equation 2 in [14]. The tuple has a component that represents consciousness level whose dynamics is expressed in the solution of the $3.I^M$ difference equations. The notions of consciousness and self-awareness are considered relevant in AI [61], [62], as manifested in the cognitive architecture of LIDA [63], CERA [64], and MLECOG [23]. Apart from them, the $3.I^M$ design also takes inspiration from the concepts of: (a) embodiment (the influence of an agent's body on its cognitive development) that supports AI agents (e.g., those investigated in [65]–[68]) to obtain intellectual development superior to their unembodied counterparts [69], and that plays a vital role in human cognitive growth (as upheld in Developmental Psychology [70]) even in the learning of Mathematics [71]; (b) neuronal stochasticity that can help the human brain find optimal solutions to mental problems [72], [73]; (c) and human mental ability to transform the information from their experiences, an ability mimicked in the creative AIs explored in [74]–[77].

Due to the scope limitation of this paper, only the $3.I^M$ capabilities to generalize and fuse some of its contained

information are investigated. In the foregoing, the general features of 3^M , the abstract base class of $3.I^M$, are presented in Section II. Section III explores the necessary mathematical tools to investigate $3.I^M$. This is followed in Section IV by the detailed definition of 3^M thereby yielding the derived class $3.I^M$. The outcomes of the $3.I^M$ interactions with its environment are investigated in Section V. And the conclusion and future of this work are provided in Section VI.

II. FUNDAMENTAL FEATURES OF 3^M

The fundamental features of any instance of the 3^M derive class (e.g., $3.I^M$) are as follows: (a) Dynamical: All processes within the instance and the interactions with its environment must unravel in real time. (b) Mathematical: The processes in the instance must be expressible as dynamical equations that facilitate interpretability of concepts acquired by, and inherent to, the instance. Further, the equations must contain concept-representing mathematical operators derived from human mental abilities and Developmental Psychology principles, and must be components of an algebra and a measure for the instance. (c) Developmental: Over its lifetime, the instance must have a *brain* (information processor) that autonomously evolves its *postnatal* (acquired and created) information, catalysed by its *body* (transducer of information external and internal to the instance) and environmental interactions. (d) Embodied: The environment interactions must play a vital role in the cognitive development of the instance (analogous to humans' [70], [71]). (e) Transformative: The mathematical operators described in Item II.b (item b of Section II) must be capable of transforming (an ability analogous to that of creative AIs [74]–[77]) and/or inter-relating postnatal information in the instance. (f) Simulative: The transformation results must be made to interact with the output of the other instance components (i.e., related to the interactions in the component [78] and autopoietic [79] systems). (g) Self-aware: The instance must be the registrar of some activities of its body and brain. (h) Stochastic: Some cognitive processes in the instance must have an element of randomness (an element also found in the human brain [72], [73]). (i) Situated in a suitable environment: The instance must not experience purely random or identical stimuli from its environment for a prolong period of time.

These fundamental features are employed to construct the 3^M block diagram, illustrated in Figure 1, that expresses a feedback system, a type of system necessary for the adaptive behaviour of the CERA-CRANIUM AI agent [64]. The diagram has sections labelled Body and Brain that correspond to the body and brain of 3^M , respectively — the block labelled Environment situate 3^M . Body and Brain are composed of components which have state being a mathematical set labelled as a letter or a string of letters under a tilde symbol ($\tilde{}$) (e.g., \tilde{STT}). Body is composed of the Sensors component with state \tilde{SEN} and issues sensations; and of the Actuators component with state \tilde{ACT} , also generates sensations, and enables 3^M to alter, autonomously explore and interact with Environment.

The Brain section is composed of the following components: (i) Memory \tilde{MEM} stores the postnatal information of

Fig. 1: The 3^M architecture

3^M . (ii) Transformer \widehat{XFM} contains and executes the 3^M -inherent mathematical operators that either transform or interrelate the Memory information (an implementation of Feature II.e). (iii) Contrector \widehat{CON} produces information on the Transformer operator actions, i.e. makes 3^M self-aware (a fulfilment of Feature II.g). (iv) Interactor \widehat{INT} performs the interaction of Transformer output with the Memory and Contrector outputs (an employment of Feature II.f). (v) Selector \widehat{SEL} processes the Memory, Contrector and Interactor outputs according to the self-awareness attribute of these outputs referred to as the *consciousness level* (a realization of Feature II.g). (vi) Executioner \widehat{XEC} processes the Selector output to activate Actuators.

(vii) Feedback \widehat{FBK} processes the Selector and Executioner outputs to obtain the 3^M output and the information it feeds to Sensors and Sumer. (viii) Sumer \widehat{SUM} unites the Sensors and Feedback outputs, then feed the resulting union to Memory.

Being dynamical, 3^M interacts with Environment in real discrete time τDUR , referred to as the *external time*, \exists *external time index* $\tau \in \mathbb{N}_0^+$ (a set of non-negative integers) and a fixed $DUR \in \mathbb{R}^+$ (a set of positive real values). Its internal processes execute in real discrete time $t = m\delta$, referred to as the *internal time*, \exists *internal time index* $m \in \mathbb{N}_0^+$ where $DUR = \Delta\delta$, the *period* $\Delta = 4$, and the fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{R}^+$. For convenience, δ is made unity and, except when defined differently, the variable

$t = \tau\Delta\delta = \tau\Delta$ from here onwards. The internal time index m is related to the external time index as

$$\tau = NTOX(m) = \lfloor m/\Delta \rfloor. \quad (\text{II.1})$$

The internal time parametrises each 3^M component state (e.g. $\widetilde{XFM}(t+1)$) while the external time index parametrises the Environment state $\widetilde{ENV}(\tau, x)$. Prior to and at internal time $t = 0\Delta = 0$, each 3^M component state is an empty set, while Environment starts to provide information to Body at $t = 0$.

A. Body

As previously mentioned, Body is composed of Actuators and Sensors which in turn is composed of subcomponents with label s (e.g., $s = \text{“eye”}$) and state \widetilde{SEN}_s . Thus, the Sensors state is

$$\widetilde{SEN}(t + \delta, x) = \widetilde{SEN}(t + 1, x) = \bigcup_{s \in ISEN} \widetilde{SEN}_s(t + 1, x), \quad (\text{II.2})$$

where x indicates an Environment location;

$$ISEN = \{s \mid s = \text{string}\}; \quad (\text{II.3})$$

$\widetilde{SEN}_s(t + 1, x) = \emptyset, \forall \tau \leq 0$; and the \cup operator is defined in Section III-B. Also, Actuators is composed of subcomponents with label a (e.g., $a = \text{“foot”}$) and state \widetilde{ACT}_a . Thus, its state is

$$\widetilde{ACT}(t + 3, x) = \bigcup_{a \in IACT} \widetilde{ACT}_a(t + 3, x), \quad (\text{II.4})$$

where,

$$IACT = \{a \mid a = \text{string}\}; \quad (\text{II.5})$$

and $\widetilde{ACT}_a(t + 3, x) = \emptyset, \forall \tau \leq 0$. At external time index $\tau > 0$, it is activated by Executioner according to the function \mathcal{A} as

$$\widetilde{ACT}(t + 3, x) = \mathcal{A}(\widetilde{ACT}(t + 3 - \Delta, x), \widetilde{XEC}(t + 2)). \quad (\text{II.6})$$

Its effect to Environment is related by the function \mathcal{E} as

$$\widetilde{ENV}(\tau, x) = \mathcal{E}(\widetilde{ENV}(\tau - 1, x), \widetilde{ACT}(t + 3 - \Delta, x)). \quad (\text{II.7})$$

Environment in turn affects Sensors according to the function \mathcal{S} as

$$\widetilde{SEN}(t + 1, x) = \mathcal{S}\left(\frac{\widetilde{ENV}(\tau, x), \widetilde{SEN}(t + 1 - \Delta, x)}{\widetilde{FBK}(t + 2 - \Delta), \widetilde{ACT}(t + 3 - \Delta, x)}\right) \quad (\text{II.8})$$

where the Environment location x is dropped in $\widetilde{SEN}(t + 1, x)$ and $\widetilde{ACT}(t + 3, x)$ for convenience from here onwards; and the functions \mathcal{S} , \mathcal{E} and \mathcal{A} are defined in the derived class of the abstract base class 3^M .

B. Brain

At external time index $\tau > 0$, Sumer, Memory, Transformer, Contrector, Interactor, Selector, Executioner and Feedback (described in the above enumeration) have output/state defined respectively as

$$\widetilde{SUM}(t + 1) = \widetilde{SEN}(t + 1) \cup \widetilde{FBK}(t + 2 - \Delta), \quad (\text{II.9})$$

$$\widetilde{MEM}(t + 1) = \Gamma_{[MEM]}(\widetilde{SUM}(t + 1)), \quad (\text{II.10})$$

$$\widetilde{XFM}(t + 1) = \Gamma_{[XFM]}(\mathcal{J}(\Omega, \widetilde{MEM}(t + 1))), \quad (\text{II.11})$$

$$\widetilde{CON}(t + 1) = \Gamma_{[CON]}(\mathcal{C}(\widetilde{XFM}(t + 1))), \quad (\text{II.12})$$

$$\widetilde{INT}(t + 2) = \Gamma_{[INT]} \left(\left\{ \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \widetilde{CON}(t + 1) \cup \\ \widetilde{MEM}(t + 1) \end{array} \right\} \middle| \circ \right\} \right), \quad (\text{II.13})$$

$$\widetilde{SEL}(t + 2) = \mathcal{L} \left(\widetilde{INT}(t + 2), \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \widetilde{CON}(t + 1) \cup \\ \widetilde{MEM}(t + 1) \end{array} \right\} \right), \quad (\text{II.14})$$

$$\widetilde{XEC}(t + 2) = \mathcal{X}(\widetilde{SEL}(t + 2)), \quad (\text{II.15})$$

and

$$\widetilde{FBK}(t + 2) \triangleq \Gamma_{[FBK]}(\widetilde{SEL}(t + 2), \widetilde{XEC}(t + 2)) \quad (\text{II.16})$$

where:

- 1) all the states are empty at $\tau \leq 0$ (e.g., $\widetilde{FBK}(-\Delta + 2) = \emptyset$);
- 2) the elements of $\widetilde{FBK}(t + 2)$ with consciousness level attribute greater than or equal to the fixed threshold $THR \in \mathbb{R}^+$ comprise the 3^M output at internal time $t + 2$;
- 3) in Equation II.11,

$$\Omega = \bigcup_{o=1}^{NOP} \Omega_o \quad (\text{II.17})$$

is a set of NOP operators Ω_o rooted from human mental abilities and Developmental Psychology principles (to fulfill Feature II.e);

- 4) and $\Gamma_{[\cdot]}$, $\langle \cdot \mid \circ \mid \cdot \rangle$, \mathcal{C} , \mathcal{L} \mathcal{J} and \mathcal{X} are the methods/functions defined in 3^M derive class.

3^M is inherited and its methods implemented to obtain the $3.I^M$ agent. However, before investigating this implementation, let us first explore the algebra and measure for $3.I^M$.

III. MATHEMATICAL FOUNDATIONS

Let \mathbb{Z}_0^+ be a set comprised of zero and all positive integers expressible as

$$\sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n a_n \triangleq z, \quad (\text{III.1})$$

where a_n is a boolean value (i.e., either TRUE or FALSE);

$$2^n a_n = \begin{cases} 2^n & a_n = \text{TRUE} \\ 0 & a_n = \text{FALSE}; \end{cases} \quad (\text{III.2})$$

and $NBT = 64$ is the number of bits used to represent unsigned integer in the computing machine used to simulate for this paper the $3.I^M$ dynamics. If $a_n = \text{TRUE} \forall 0 \leq n < NBT$ then z is denoted as \mathbb{Z}^∞ . Further, let $\mathbb{Z}^+ = \mathbb{Z}_0^+ - 0$ (i.e., a \mathbb{Z}_0^+ without zero); $\mathbb{N}^+ = \mathbb{N}_0^+ - 0$ be the set of all positive integers; and $\mathbb{R}_0^+ = \mathbb{R}^+ \cup 0$. Furthermore, let the set

$$ENT = \{1, 3\} \subset \mathbb{Z}_0^+. \quad (\text{III.3})$$

Its elements are the only possible entries of the matrix $X \triangleq [m_{r,c}]$. The matrix of form X has $m_{r,c} \triangleq X[r,c]$ as its entry at row r and column c , and has $NROW$ and $NCOL \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ as its fixed number of rows and columns, respectively. When all the entries of X are equal to one it is denoted as $\mathbb{1}$. All matrices of the X kind comprised the set \mathbb{M} which when depleted by $\mathbb{1}$ is denoted as $\mathbb{M}_{\neq 1} \subset \mathbb{M}$.

A. Objects

The fundamental information in $3.I^M$, referred to as the *bare basic object*, is labelled as a letter or a string of letters under the caret symbol ($\widehat{}$) and defined as the tuple

$$[Type, Data] \triangleq \widehat{O} \quad (\text{III.4})$$

(akin to the knowledge representation employed in the developmental Magellan Pro robot [55] cited in Section I-C) where *Type* is a string of letters that signifies the type of \widehat{O} ; and *Data* is an element of either \mathbb{M} or \mathbb{Z}_0^+ — when *Type* is either “eyeVissn” or other, respectively — and is the quantitative aspect of \widehat{O} . The type and data of \widehat{O} are extracted by the operators $\langle \cdot \rangle_\rho$ and $\langle \cdot \rangle_\delta$, respectively (e.g., $\langle \widehat{O} \rangle_\rho = \text{“eye”}$). **Definition 1:** If two bare basic objects are of the same type then their data must belong to the same domain, i.e., the data is either in \mathbb{Z}_0^+ or \mathbb{M} . In addition, if their data are identical then they are said to be *equal*. ■ The space of all bare basic objects is denoted as $\widehat{\Phi}$.

The bare basic object \widehat{O} is used to define the entity referred to as the *basic object* labelled as a letter or a string of letters under the arrow symbol (\rightarrow) and expressed as

$$\{\widehat{O} \mid \mathbf{i} : i, \mathbf{c} : c, \mathbf{p} : p, \mathbf{t} : t, \mathbf{o} : o\} \triangleq \vec{O} \quad (\text{III.5})$$

where \mathbf{i} , \mathbf{c} , \mathbf{p} , \mathbf{t} and \mathbf{o} are referred to as the *attributes* of \widehat{O} and signify the ID (identification number), consciousness level, purity, internal time label and forming operator label (the type of Transformer operator that produced \vec{O}) of \widehat{O} , respectively.

The symbols i, c, p, t and o are referred to as the *descriptors*, and each describes the attribute nearest to its left such as in Equation III.5, e.g., $\{\widehat{O} \mid \mathbf{i} : 3, \mathbf{c} : 0.1, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : 5, \mathbf{o} : \text{“common”}\}$ describes the bare basic object \widehat{O} as having 0.1 consciousness level. The time and consciousness level descriptors and the data of the bare basic object are inspired by the time t , the probability ρ , and the activation state \mathbf{x} variables in the Fokker-Plank equation corresponding to the stochastic differential equation model (e.g., Equation 2 in [14]) of neural networks, respectively, where $\rho(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the occurrence probability of \mathbf{x} at t and the dependent variable of the former equation. If the descriptors are variables then $i \in \mathbb{N}^+$, $c \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $t \in \mathbb{N}_0^+$, $1 \leq p \leq 4$, and o is a string of letters. The descriptors c and t can also be relationships, e.g., $\{\widehat{A} \mid \mathbf{i} : 7, \mathbf{c} : \leq 0.1, \mathbf{p} : 2, \mathbf{t} : < 5, \mathbf{o} : \text{“bJoin”}\}$ describes the bare basic object \widehat{A} as having internal time lesser than 5. When an attribute is not the main subject of a current topic in the foregoing it and its descriptor exist but not indicated, e.g., the basic object $\vec{C} = \{\widehat{C} \mid \mathbf{c} : 3\}$ denotes that its bare basic object \widehat{C} is also endowed with internal time label, forming operator label, etcetera, but not indicated.

A bare basic object or two acted upon, respectively, by a unary or binary Transformer operator (an element of Ω in Equation II.17) yield an entity referred to as, the *bare object*; and a bare object or two acted upon by the operators also yield a bare object. A bare object O endowed with attributes yields the entity referred to as the *object* labelled as a letter or string

of letters under the symbol ($^\circ$) and expressed as

$$\mathring{O} = \{O \mid \mathbf{i} : i, \mathbf{c} : c, \mathbf{p} : p, \mathbf{t} : t, \mathbf{o} : o\} \quad (\text{III.6})$$

where o is a string of letters corresponding to the Transformer operator that produces \mathring{O} . The bare object O is referred to as, the *bare component* of \mathring{O} ; has symbol being the base of the symbol for object \mathring{O} or basic object \vec{O} of which it is a bare component; and is related as $O = \langle \mathring{O} \rangle_\beta = \langle \vec{O} \rangle_\beta$. The ID, consciousness level, purity, internal time label and forming operator label attribute of the object \mathring{O} are extracted through $\langle \mathring{O} \rangle_\eta$, $\langle \mathring{O} \rangle_\gamma$, $\langle \mathring{O} \rangle_\pi$, $\langle \mathring{O} \rangle_\tau$ and $\langle \mathring{O} \rangle_\omega$, respectively. If any two objects $\mathring{A} = \{A \mid \mathbf{i} : d_a^1, \mathbf{c} : d_a^2, \mathbf{p} : d_a^3, \mathbf{t} : d_a^4, \mathbf{o} : d_a^5\}$ and $\mathring{B} = \{B \mid \mathbf{i} : d_b^1, \mathbf{c} : d_b^2, \mathbf{p} : d_b^3, \mathbf{t} : d_b^4, \mathbf{o} : d_b^5\}$ have descriptors $d_a^i = d_b^i, \forall 1 \leq i \leq 5$, and bare components $A = B$ then they are said to be equal. Given an external time index σ , an object \mathring{O} is referred to as σ -old or σ -new if $NTOX(\langle \mathring{O} \rangle_\tau) < \sigma$ or $\langle \mathring{O} \rangle_\tau \geq \sigma$, respectively. Further, if a set is composed of σ -old (σ -new) objects then it is described also as a σ -old (σ -new) set.

The entity \hat{O} is referred to as the *empty object* and considered simultaneously as an object and a bare basic object. It and the empty set \emptyset are the identity operands of the union operator \cup , e.g., for an object \mathring{O} ,

$$\mathring{O} \cup \hat{O} = \mathring{O}. \quad (\text{III.7})$$

It and any scalar yield itself under any arithmetic operation, e.g.,

$$\hat{O} + 1.37 = \hat{O}. \quad (\text{III.8})$$

Definition 2: Given a bare basic object \widehat{O} , if $\langle \widehat{O} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$ is equal to zero, or if the matrix $\langle \widehat{O} \rangle_\delta = \mathbb{1} \in \mathbb{M}$ then \widehat{O} is set to \hat{O} . Further, if an object \mathring{O} has zero or negative consciousness level attribute or bare component equal to \hat{O} then it is also set to \hat{O} . ■ These settings must be performed prior to the use of \widehat{O} or \mathring{O} in any mathematical operation. Lastly, the symbol \hat{O} expresses an object not \hat{O} .

B. Sets

An object or bare object is considered as a singleton set. The 3^M component state and the set of objects \mathring{A}_i have similar labelling scheme, e.g., $\widetilde{SET} = \{\mathring{A}_i \mid 1 \leq i \leq N\}$ where $N = |\widetilde{SET}|$ is the set cardinality. The set can also be expressed as

$$\widetilde{SET} = \{SET \mid \mathbf{C} : C, \mathbf{T} : T\} \quad (\text{III.9})$$

where the set of bare objects

$$SET = \{A_i \mid 1 \leq i \leq N\} \triangleq \langle \widetilde{SET} \rangle_\beta \quad (\text{III.10})$$

is referred to as the *bare set* and the *bare component* of \widetilde{SET} ; $A_i = \langle \mathring{A}_i \rangle_\beta$; the attribute symbols \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{T} signify consciousness level and internal time label of the objects $\mathring{A}_i \in \widetilde{SET}$, respectively; and the symbols C and T are descriptors, each describes the attribute nearest to its left. When the object \mathring{O} or the set \widetilde{S} of objects has exponent of the form “(integer)” (e.g., $\mathring{O}^{(n)}$ or $\widetilde{S}^{(n)}$) then $\mathring{O}^{(n)} \neq \mathring{O}$ or $\widetilde{S}^{(n)} \neq \widetilde{S}$ but the bare component $\langle \mathring{O}^{(n)} \rangle_\beta = \langle \mathring{O} \rangle_\beta$ or $\langle \widetilde{S}^{(n)} \rangle_\beta = \langle \widetilde{S} \rangle_\beta$, respectively. A *bare state* is a set of all bare objects outputted by a

$3.I^M$ component, e.g., a bare Memory state is the set of all bare objects outputted by Memory. Any set S expressed in the form $\{e_i\}$ has elements e_i assumed to be indexed with $1 \leq i \leq |S|$ (i.e., $S = \cup_{i=1}^{|S|} e_i$), except when defined differently.

Definition 3: Both the set subtraction and \cup operators retain their set theoretic properties when acting on sets of objects, bare objects or scalar values. ■ Lastly, given an ordered set O , the expression $\mathcal{O}(i \in O)$ yields the ordered of the element i in O , e.g., $\mathcal{O}(25 \in \{7, 16, 25, 34, 43\}) = 3$, i.e., third in the order.

The set Ω of operators in Equation II.17 is comprised of the binary join and common operators symbolized as \oplus and \otimes , respectively, and explored next.

C. Join

The definitions below pertinent to the join operator \oplus are inspired by the tensor inner product [80], and by the mental focus on a set of information in human immediate memory — an act related to the definition of consciousness in Global Workspace Theory [63], [64]. Under the \oplus operator: (a) any two elements $A, B \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$ yield

$$A \oplus B \triangleq \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n (a_n \text{ OR } b_n) \quad (\text{III.11})$$

where OR is the boolean OR operation,

$$A = \sum_{m=0}^{NBT-1} 2^m a_m, \quad (\text{III.12})$$

$$B = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n b_n, \quad (\text{III.13})$$

and a_m and b_n take boolean values, based on Equation III.1; (b) any two matrices $M = [m_{r,c}], N = [n_{r,c}] \in \mathbb{M}$ produce

$$M \oplus N \triangleq [m_{r,c} \oplus n_{r,c}]; \quad (\text{III.14})$$

(c) each of the spaces \mathbb{Z}_0^+ and \mathbb{M} is proven in Theorems B.1 and B.2 (refer to Appendix), respectively, to be closed, and comprised of self-idempotent, commutative and associative elements; (d) any two bare basic objects $\widehat{A}, \widehat{B} \in \widehat{\Phi}$ of the same type ψ (i.e., $\psi = \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\rho = \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\rho$) produce the entity

$$\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{B} \triangleq [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \oplus \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta] \quad (\text{III.15})$$

proven as a bare basic object in Theorem B.3; (e) if these bare basic objects differ in type and neither is an empty object then the \oplus operator is commutative over them and the expression $\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{B}$ is irreducible; (f) if any three elements of $\widehat{\Phi}$ are not all of the same type then the \oplus operator is associative over them. (g) any bare basic object in $\widehat{\Phi}$ is proven in Theorem B.4 to be self-idempotent; (h) elements of $\widehat{\Phi}$ are proven in Theorem B.5 to be commutative and associative; (i) and the empty object $\widehat{\emptyset} \in \widehat{\Phi}$ is defined as the identity element of $\widehat{\Phi}$, i.e.,

$$\widehat{A} = \widehat{\emptyset} \oplus \widehat{A} = \widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{\emptyset} \quad (\text{III.16})$$

and

$$\widehat{\emptyset} \oplus \widehat{\emptyset} = \widehat{\emptyset}. \quad (\text{III.17})$$

The join of all bare basic objects in the set $S = \{\widehat{O}_j\}$ is expressed as

$$\prod_{j=1}^{||S||:\oplus} \widehat{O}_j \triangleq O. \quad (\text{III.18})$$

D. Common

The succeeding definitions related to the common operator \otimes are influenced by the tensor product [80], and by the theorized infants' mental ability to extract similarities among the physical objects he/she perceives (cited in Section I) [81]–[84]. Under the \otimes operator: (a) any two elements $A, B \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$ (and defined respectively in Equations III.12 and III.13) produce

$$A \otimes B \triangleq \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n (a_n \text{ AND } b_n) \quad (\text{III.19})$$

where AND is the boolean AND operation; (b) any two matrices $M = [m_{r,c}], N = [n_{r,c}] \in \mathbb{M}$ form

$$M \otimes N \triangleq [m_{r,c} \otimes n_{r,c}]; \quad (\text{III.20})$$

(c) each of the spaces \mathbb{Z}_0^+ and \mathbb{M} is proven in Theorems B.6 and B.7, respectively, to be closed, and constituted by self-idempotent, commutative and associative elements; (d) any two bare basic objects $\widehat{A}, \widehat{B} \in \widehat{\Phi}$ of the same type ψ create

$$\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B} \triangleq [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta] \quad (\text{III.21})$$

proven as bare basic object in Theorem B.11; (e) if \widehat{A} and \widehat{B} differ in type then

$$\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B} \triangleq \widehat{\emptyset}; \quad (\text{III.22})$$

(f) the space $\widehat{\Phi}$ is proven in Theorem B.11 to be closed, and comprised of elements proven self-idempotent in Theorem B.12, and commutative and associative in Theorem B.13; (g) the space $\widehat{\Phi}$ has $\widehat{\emptyset}$ as its null element, i.e.,

$$\widehat{\emptyset} \otimes \widehat{A} \triangleq \widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{\emptyset} \triangleq \widehat{\emptyset} \quad (\text{III.23})$$

and

$$\widehat{\emptyset} \otimes \widehat{\emptyset} \triangleq \widehat{\emptyset}. \quad (\text{III.24})$$

The \otimes operator distributes to the \oplus operator, and vice-versa, over the elements of \mathbb{Z}_0^+ and \mathbb{M} as proven respectively in Theorems B.8 and B.9. **Definition 4:** The distribution is defined over three $\widehat{\emptyset}$ bare basic objects not all of similar type. ■ While, Theorem B.15 proves the distribution over all elements of $\widehat{\Phi}$.

The \oplus and \otimes operators are used in Transformer to create new objects in $3.I^M$. These objects are proven in Theorem E.3 to only have basic object form, such that, the two terms are interchangeable from here onwards; and so as the terms bare object and bare basic object.

The \otimes operator is used to define the *generalization* $\langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\beta$ of the bare set $S = \{\langle \widehat{O}_i \rangle_\beta\}$ in

$$\langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\beta = \prod_{i=1}^{||S||:\otimes} \langle \widehat{O}_i \rangle_\beta \triangleq \langle \widehat{O}_1 \rangle_\beta \otimes \langle \widehat{O}_2 \rangle_\beta \otimes \dots \otimes \langle \widehat{O}_{|S|} \rangle_\beta. \quad (\text{III.25})$$

If $\langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\beta \neq \widehat{\emptyset}$ then S is referred to as the *category*; and $\langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\beta$ and $\langle \widehat{O}_i \rangle_\beta$ are referred to as the *prototype* and *member* of the

category S , respectively. If $\langle \hat{C} \rangle_\beta \neq \langle \hat{O}_i \rangle_\beta, \forall \langle \hat{O}_i \rangle_\beta \in S$ then it is referred to as the *authentic generalization* of S .

The ability to generalize is fundamental to cognition, without which a natural organism is less likely to survive [85]. The cognitive ability of $3.I^M$ to generalize is not pre-programmed; rather, it is supported in Dynamics F.1 (refer to Appendix) to emerge from the interactions between Environment and $3.I^M$.

E. Measures

Apart from the defined Algebra above, $3.I^M$ is also endowed with the following two types of measure. The first type is referred to as the *data measure* and indicated, for any given \hat{O} object \hat{O} and bare component $\hat{O} = \langle \hat{O} \rangle_\beta$, as

$$\|\hat{O}\| = \|\hat{O}\| = \|\langle \hat{O} \rangle_\delta\| \quad (\text{III.26})$$

where

$$\|\langle \hat{O} \rangle_\delta\| = \begin{cases} \#_Z(\langle \hat{O} \rangle_\delta) & \langle \hat{O} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+ \\ \#_A(\langle \hat{O} \rangle_\delta) & \langle \hat{O} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{M}; \end{cases} \quad (\text{III.27})$$

$\#_A(a)$ is the number of entries in the matrix $a \in \mathbb{M}$ equal to 3; and $\#_Z(z)$ is the number of coefficients $a_n = \text{TRUE}$ in $z = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n a_n$.

Definition 5: The second type of measure is referred to as the *consciousness measure* and denoted as $\langle \hat{O} \rangle_\gamma$ which is simply the consciousness level of the object \hat{O} . ■ The two types of measure of any object are proven in Theorems C.1 and C.2 to be non-negative. **Definition 6:** The two types of measure $\|\langle \hat{O} \rangle_\delta\|$ and $\langle \hat{O} \rangle_\gamma$ are zero iff $\hat{O} = \hat{\emptyset}$. ■

F. Edge

The data measure is also applied to the bare basic object \hat{E} whose data *EDG* expresses the edge of a given figure in the data *GVN* of the bare basic object \hat{G} where both data are matrices/images in \mathbb{M} with entry/pixel at row r and column c either 3 or 1 ($\in ENT \subset \mathbb{Z}_0^+$) representing black or white color, respectively; and both bare basic objects have identical type “eyeVissn”. To compute the image *EDG*, all of its pixels are first set as white. If the pixel *GVN*[r, c] is black and has at least one adjacent white pixel then *EDG*[r, c] is set to black. This rule is applied to all black pixels of *GVN* to compute *EDG*, exemplified in Figure 2. The derivation of \hat{E} from \hat{G} is expressed as

$$\hat{E} = \textcircled{E} \hat{G} \triangleq [\text{“eyeVissn”}, \textcircled{E} \langle \hat{G} \rangle_\delta] \in \hat{\Phi} \quad (\text{III.28})$$

where the unary operator \textcircled{E} represents the edge extraction operation. The operator \textcircled{E} acting on $\hat{\emptyset}$ is defined to yield $\hat{\emptyset}$, i.e.,

$$\textcircled{E} \hat{\emptyset} = \hat{\emptyset}. \quad (\text{III.29})$$

If *GVN* is an all-black image then, by the edge extraction procedure, it has no edge as every pixel in it does not have a white pixel neighbour. Thus, *EDG* in this case is an all white image (i.e., $EDG = \mathbb{1}$), such that by Definition 2, $\hat{E} = [\text{“eyeVissn”}, EDG] = \hat{\emptyset}$. In view of this, **Definition 7:** any two “eyeVissn”-type bare basic objects \hat{A} and \hat{B} are referred to as *similar* if $\hat{A} = \hat{B}$ and $\hat{A}, \textcircled{E}\hat{A} \neq \hat{\emptyset}$. While any two non-“eyeVissn”-type bare basic objects \hat{C} and \hat{E} are referred to as

similar if $\hat{C} = \hat{E}$ and $\hat{C}, \hat{E} \neq \hat{\emptyset}$. If any two bare basic objects are not similar they are referred to as *different*. Further, any two sets of objects are said to be similar if given any element of one set there exists a similar element in the other set, and vice versa. Otherwise, they are said to be different. ■

Fig. 2: Edge extraction: (a) given image (b) edges in the given image

G. Measure of Similarity

The similarity-based approach explored in [84] explains well the ability of young children to generalize. To define similarity in $3.I^M$ context, consider any two bare basic objects \hat{A} and \hat{B} and the function

$$SIM(\hat{A}, \hat{B}) = \begin{cases} \frac{\|\hat{A} \otimes \hat{B}\|^2}{\|\hat{A}\| \times \|\hat{B}\|} & \hat{A}, \hat{B} \neq \hat{\emptyset} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (\text{III.30})$$

The measure of similarity between them, when $\langle \hat{A} \rangle_\delta$ or $\langle \hat{B} \rangle_\delta \notin \mathbb{M}$, is

$$\langle \hat{A} | \hat{B} \rangle = SIM(\hat{A}, \hat{B}); \quad (\text{III.31})$$

and when $\langle \hat{A} \rangle_\delta, \langle \hat{B} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{M}$,

$$\langle \hat{A} | \hat{B} \rangle = SIM(\hat{A}, \hat{B}) SIM(\textcircled{E}\hat{A}, \textcircled{E}\hat{B}). \quad (\text{III.32})$$

The measure of similarity between any two similar or different bare objects is proven in Theorem C.4 to be one or non-negative less than one, respectively.

H. Set objects IDing

In the foregoing, it is possible that a set \tilde{S}' may contain objects with ID not set yet. Let these objects comprise the set \tilde{U} . To determine the IDs, an object in \tilde{U} is arbitrarily picked, when possible, and its ID is made equal to one plus a given seed *SID*. Then another object in \tilde{U} with undetermined ID is picked arbitrarily, when possible, and have its ID made equal to one plus the last set ID. This process is repeated until each object in \tilde{U} with undetermined ID has its ID set, thereby \tilde{S}' is relabelled as \tilde{S} . This ID determining process is expressed as,

$$\tilde{S} = IDS(\tilde{S}', SID). \quad (\text{III.33})$$

I. Binary Operations on Objects

Let us now consider the binary join and common operations over objects. These operators applied to any two $\hat{\emptyset}$ (according to Definition 2) objects \hat{A} and \hat{B} , with $A = \langle \hat{A} \rangle_\beta$ and $B = \langle \hat{B} \rangle_\beta$, produce the objects

$$\hat{A} \oplus \hat{B} = \{A \oplus B \mid \mathbf{i} : i_\oplus, \mathbf{c} : c_\oplus, \mathbf{p} : p_\oplus, \mathbf{t} : t, \mathbf{o} : \text{“bJoin”}\} \quad (\text{III.34})$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{A} \otimes \dot{B} = \{A \otimes B \mid \mathbf{i} : i_{\otimes}, \mathbf{c} : c_{\otimes}, \\ \mathbf{p} : p_{\otimes}, \mathbf{t} : t, \mathbf{o} : \text{"common"}\}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{III.35})$$

respectively, where

$$t = \max\{\langle \dot{A} \rangle_{\tau}, \langle \dot{B} \rangle_{\tau}\}; \quad (\text{III.36})$$

$$c_{\oplus} = \frac{1}{2}(\langle \dot{A} \rangle_{\gamma} + \langle \dot{B} \rangle_{\gamma}) PUF_{\oplus}; \quad (\text{III.37})$$

$$c_{\otimes} = \frac{1}{2}(\langle \dot{A} \rangle_{\gamma} + \langle \dot{B} \rangle_{\gamma}) PUF_{\otimes}; \quad (\text{III.38})$$

and PUF_{\oplus} and PUF_{\otimes} are the purity factors.

The latter, together with the purity descriptors p_{\oplus} and p_{\otimes} (in Equations III.34 and III.35, respectively) are computed as follows:

- 1) If $\langle \dot{A} \rangle_{\pi} = 2$ or 1, and $\langle \dot{B} \rangle_{\pi} = 2$ or 1, then $p_{\oplus} = 2$ and PUF_{\oplus} equals the constant $P_{\oplus} \in \mathbb{R}^+$. Otherwise, $p_{\oplus} = 4$ and PUF_{\oplus} equals another constant $PTN \in \mathbb{R}^+$.
- 2) If $\langle \dot{A} \rangle_{\pi} = 3$ or 1, and $\langle \dot{B} \rangle_{\pi} = 3$ or 1, then $p_{\otimes} = 3$ and $PUF_{\otimes} = 1.0$. Otherwise, $p_{\otimes} = 4$ and $PUF_{\otimes} = PTN$.

Now, consider any $3.I^M$ component (e.g., Transformer) that applies the binary operators \oplus and/or \otimes to its input objects to produce a set \overline{PRD} of objects — with temporarily undetermined ID (i_{\oplus} or i_{\otimes} in Equations III.34 or III.35, respectively). The set \overline{PRD} is feed to Equation III.33 together with SID being equal to the maximum ID found in the input objects to obtain the set $\overline{PRD} = IDS(\overline{PRD}, SID)$ of objects with determined ID.

J. Consolidator

Consolidator processes any given *partition* (a set of similar $\hat{\otimes}$ objects) to yield a single object. If the partition \tilde{A} is a subset of the set S of objects then it must contain all elements of S similar to any of its elements. Consider the partition $\tilde{A} = \{\dot{A}_i \mid i \in NDX\}$ as a set ordered according to the increasing index value i (e.g., $\tilde{A} = \{\dot{A}_1, \dot{A}_3, \dot{A}_7\}$) where

$$\dot{A}_i = \{A \mid \mathbf{i} : h_i, \mathbf{c} : c_i, \mathbf{p} : p_i, \mathbf{t} : t_i, \mathbf{o} : o_i\}; \quad (\text{III.39})$$

A is the bare component of every $\dot{A}_i \in \tilde{A}$; and NDX is a set of positive integers. It is consolidated by $\Gamma_{[CN]}(\cdot)$ into a single object,

$$\Gamma_{[CN]}(\tilde{A}) \triangleq \begin{cases} \dot{A} & \tilde{A} \neq \emptyset \\ \hat{\otimes} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (\text{III.40})$$

where

$$\dot{A} = \{A \mid \mathbf{i} : h, \mathbf{c} : c, \mathbf{p} : p, \mathbf{t} : s, \mathbf{o} : o\}; \quad (\text{III.41})$$

$$c \triangleq \sum_{i \in NDX} c_i; \quad (\text{III.42})$$

the internal time descriptor

$$s \triangleq \max\{t_i \mid i \in NDX\}; \quad (\text{III.43})$$

and the descriptors h, p, o are described next.

The purity descriptor p is equal to 1 if there is at least one $\dot{A}_i \in \tilde{A}$ with $\langle \dot{A}_i \rangle_{\pi} = 1$. Else, it is equal to 2 if there is at least

one $\dot{A}_j \in \tilde{A}$ with $\langle \dot{A}_j \rangle_{\pi} = 2$. Else, it is equal to 3 if there is at least one $\dot{A}_k \in \tilde{A}$ with $\langle \dot{A}_k \rangle_{\pi} = 3$. Else, it is equal to 4.

To compute the descriptors h and o in Equation III.41, consider the descriptor s in Equation III.43 and $J = \{j \mid j \in NDX; \langle \dot{A}_j \rangle_{\tau} = s\}$ (i.e., J is a set of indices in NDX that correspond to objects in \tilde{A} with internal time label equal to s). If J has only one element j then $o = \langle \dot{A}_j \rangle_{\omega}$ and $h = \langle \dot{A}_j \rangle_{\eta}$. Otherwise, let $q = \max\{\langle \dot{A}_j \rangle_{\omega} \mid j \in J\}$ where the $\max\{\cdot\}$ operation yields the forming operator label with the highest alphabetical order among $\langle \dot{A}_j \rangle_{\omega}, j \in J$ (e.g., “common” has higher order than “bJoin”). Now, form the set of indices $M = \{k \mid k \in J; \langle \dot{A}_k \rangle_{\omega} = q\}$ and take $m = \min\{M\}$. Finally, $o = \langle \dot{A}_m \rangle_{\omega}$ and $h = \langle \dot{A}_m \rangle_{\eta}$.

The consolidation outcome \dot{A} in Equation III.40 is said to *absorb* every object $\dot{A}_i \in \tilde{A}$; and $\langle \dot{A} \rangle_{\beta} = A$ is also said to absorb every $\langle \dot{A}_i \rangle_{\beta} \in \langle A \rangle_{\beta}$. If the absorption of a bare object A occurs in the $3.I^M$ block/component C (e.g., Transformer), with state \tilde{S} , then the expression $A \overset{\approx}{\approx} S$ denotes A is produced and probably absorbed in C , and may or may not be an element of $S = \langle \tilde{S} \rangle_{\beta}$. In relation to the uncertainties, the expression $A \overset{\approx}{\approx} S$ signifies A as probably an element of S .

The versions of the consolidator $\Gamma_{[CN]}$ are denoted as $\Gamma_{[CNL]}$, $\Gamma_{[CNA]}$ and $\Gamma_{[CNM]}$. The consolidator $\Gamma_{[CNL]}$ is identical to $\Gamma_{[CN]}$ while $\Gamma_{[CNA]}$ and $\Gamma_{[CNM]}$ only differ to $\Gamma_{[CN]}$ in computing the consciousness level attribute of \dot{A} which for $\Gamma_{[CNA]}$ and $\Gamma_{[CNM]}$ is

$$c \triangleq \frac{1}{|NDX|} \sum_{i \in NDX} c_i \quad (\text{III.44})$$

and

$$c \triangleq \max\{c_i \mid i \in NDX\}, \quad (\text{III.45})$$

respectively.

The consolidator $\Gamma_{[CN]}$ defined thus far has an argument being a set of similar objects. Let us now consider the set $\tilde{M} = \{\dot{M}_i\}$ of objects \dot{M}_i which are rearranged to form

$$\tilde{M} = \bigcup_{i=1}^{NPAR(\tilde{M})} \tilde{P}_i \cup \tilde{O} \quad (\text{III.46})$$

where the function $NPAR(\cdot)$ extracts the number of partitions of its argument; \tilde{O} is a set of all elements in \tilde{M} that are, or can be set based on Definition 3 to, $\hat{\otimes}$;

$$\tilde{P}_i = \bigcup_{j=1}^{|\tilde{P}_i|} \dot{M}_{i(j)} \quad (\text{III.47})$$

is a partition of $\tilde{M} - \tilde{O}$ and composed of $\hat{\otimes}$ objects different to any element of $\tilde{M} - \tilde{O} - \tilde{P}_i$; and $i(j)$ is a bijective function that maps j to an index k such that $\dot{M}_k \in \tilde{P}_i$. The set \tilde{O} in Equation III.46 can be dropped based on Equation III.7, such that,

$$\tilde{M} = \bigcup_{i=1}^{NPAR(\tilde{M})} \tilde{P}_i. \quad (\text{III.48})$$

As proven in Theorem C.4, the partition elements satisfy, $\langle \dot{M}_{i(j)} \parallel \dot{M}_{i(k)} \rangle = 1$ and $0 \leq \langle \dot{M}_{i(j)} \parallel \dot{M}_{l(k)} \rangle < 1, \forall j \neq k, \dot{M}_{i(j)}, \dot{M}_{i(k)} \in \tilde{P}_i, \dot{M}_{l(k)} \in \tilde{P}_l$ and $l \neq i$.

The partitioned set \widetilde{M} of Equation III.48 is acted upon by the consolidator $\Gamma_{[CN]}$ to obtain

$$\Gamma_{[CN]}(\widetilde{M}) \triangleq \bigcup_{i=1}^{NPAR(\widetilde{M})} \Gamma_{[CN]}(\widetilde{P}_i). \quad (\text{III.49})$$

It follows from Equation III.40 that

$$\Gamma_{[CN]}(\widetilde{M}) = \bigcup_{i=1}^{NPAR(\widetilde{M})} \dot{C}_i \quad (\text{III.50})$$

where the object $\dot{C}_i = \Gamma_{[CN]}(\widetilde{P}_i)$. As proven in Theorem D.1, \dot{C}_i is different to \dot{C}_j and cannot be set to $\hat{0}$, $\forall i \neq j$, $1 \leq i, j \leq NPAR(\widetilde{M})$. Thus, the set $\Gamma_{[CN]}(\widetilde{M})$ has $\hat{0}$ elements with different bare component such that it is referred to as bare *unique*. Pursuing on uniqueness, if a set is composed of basic objects of different types then it is referred to as type unique.

K. Consciousness function and object

Any function $f(\dot{O})$ of object $\dot{O} = \{O \mid \mathbf{i} : i, \mathbf{c} : c, \mathbf{p} : p, \mathbf{t} : t, \mathbf{o} : o\}$ yields

$$f(\dot{O}) \triangleq \begin{cases} \dot{O}' & f(c) > 0 \\ \hat{0} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (\text{III.51})$$

where

$$\dot{O}' = \{O \mid \mathbf{i} : i, \mathbf{c} : f(c), \mathbf{p} : p, \mathbf{t} : t, \mathbf{o} : o\},$$

i.e., it only acts on the consciousness level of \dot{O} when $f(c) > 0$, such that, it is referred to as the *consciousness function*. If it is a function of bare unique set $\widetilde{O} = \{\dot{O}_i\}$ of objects with positive data measure it obtains

$$f(\widetilde{O}) \triangleq \bigcup_{i=1}^{|\widetilde{O}|} f(\dot{O}_i). \quad (\text{III.52})$$

In relation to consciousness, any object in any $3.I^M$ component state (e.g., \widetilde{SEL} in Equation II.14) is referred to as being *subconsciously perceived* by $3.I^M$ if its consciousness level is below the constant THR ; otherwise, it is referred to as being *consciously perceived* by $3.I^M$. These terminologies, however, are not meant to imply $3.I^M$ as a conscious entity. This completes the mathematical foundation of $3.I^M$.

IV. SPECIFIC IMPLEMENTATION: $3.I^M$

In this section, the $3.I^M$ environment is first described, then the $3.I^M$ features derive from 3^M Body and Brain are explored.

A. Environment

The 3^M environment state $\widetilde{ENV}(\tau, x)$ defined in Equation II.7 is further specified to obtain the $3.I^M$ environment which, at external time index τ , is

$$\widetilde{ENV}(\tau, x) = \{AFX(x), IMG(x)\} \quad (\text{IV.1})$$

where x is an Environment location of an image cell such as those illustrated in Figure 3;

$$|AFX(x)| \in \{2^i \mid 0 \leq i \leq 31 < NBT\} \subset \mathbb{Z}^+ \quad (\text{IV.2})$$

is an affect value; and each cell image/array $IMG(x) \in \mathbb{M}$ has entries either three (black) or one (white). The $3.I^M$ environment is unaffected by Actuators and external time index, as implied in Equations IV.1 and IV.2 that implicitly define the function \mathcal{E} in Equation II.7.

B. Body

In $3.I^M$, Body is composed of Eye as sensor, labelled as “eye”, and Foot as sensor and actuator simultaneously, labelled as “foot”. For this configuration, Equation II.3 has

$$ISEN = \{eye, foot\} \quad (\text{IV.3})$$

and Equation II.5 has

$$IACT = \{foot\}. \quad (\text{IV.4})$$

Foot can transfer $3.I^M$ across the $3.I^M$ environment, say at location x indicated in Figure 3. Its location is identical to those of Body, Brain and $3.I^M$ at the same external time.

Fig. 3: The $3.I^M$ environment

C. Force and Intention

The force applied to Actuators is defined as the basic object

$$\vec{F} = \{\widehat{F} \mid \mathbf{i} : h_f, \mathbf{c} : c_f, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t_f, \mathbf{o} : o_f\} \quad (\text{IV.5})$$

where h_f, c_f, t_f and o_f are determined by Executioner;

$$\widehat{F} = [\text{“force”, } FD]; \quad (\text{IV.6})$$

and the force data

$$FD \in \{1, 3, 7\} \subset \mathbb{Z}_0^+. \quad (\text{IV.7})$$

The intention to apply force to Foot (the only subcomponent of Actuators) is defined as

$$\vec{I} = \{\widehat{I}_{Foot} \mid \mathbf{i} : h_i, \mathbf{c} : c_i, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t_i, \mathbf{o} : o_i\} \quad (\text{IV.8})$$

where h_i, c_i, t_i and o_i are also determined by Executioner;

$$\widehat{I}_{Foot} = [\text{“footIntnt”, } IV]; \quad (\text{IV.9})$$

and the types “footIntnt” and “force” are collectively referred to as the *action* type. There is an intention to apply force to Foot when IV is one but otherwise three, i.e.,

$$ID \in \{1, 3\} \subset \mathbb{Z}_0^+ \quad (\text{IV.10})$$

By itself, \vec{I} is merely an intention to, but cannot, activate Foot. However, it may provide reflectiveness to the future versions of 3^M , a characteristic absent in the reflexive-only AIRL agents [86].

D. Calluser

When Foot transfers $3.I^M$ to another Environment location at external time index τ it issues an object/sensation whose

data depends on the so called *Calluser* (inspired by the characteristic of human feet to become callus) defined as

$$CAL(\tau) = 1 \ll (\tau \% 8) \quad (IV.11)$$

where the number 1 is an 8-bit unsigned integer; \ll is a wrap-around shift-left bit operator; and $\%$ is a modulo operator. Calluser is not only used for Foot but for other $3.I^M$ subcomponents as well.

E. Foot

Given an external time index $\tau \geq 0$, suppose at internal time $t + 2$ Executioner produces the “force” and “footIntnt”-type basic objects \vec{F} and \vec{I} defined in Equations IV.5 and IV.8, respectively. In view of Equation II.6, the Executioner outputs are feed at internal time $t + 3$ to Foot which has state

$$\widetilde{ACT}_{foot}(t + 3) = \{\vec{F}, \vec{I}\}. \quad (IV.12)$$

Considering there is only one actuator (Foot), the total Actuators output $\widetilde{ACT}(t + 3)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}(\widetilde{ACT}((\tau - 1)\Delta + 3), \widetilde{XEC}(t + 2)) \\ = \widetilde{ACT}_{foot}(t + 3) \end{aligned} \quad (IV.13)$$

thereby implicitly defining the function \mathcal{A} in Equation II.6 for $3.I^M$.

Now, at external time index $\tau + 1$ Foot transfers $3.I^M$ to the Environment location

$$x(\tau + 1) = x(\tau) + JMP(\vec{F}, \vec{I}) \quad (IV.14)$$

where $x(0) = 0$; and the function

$$JMP(\vec{F}, \vec{I}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \langle \vec{F} \rangle_\delta = 3, \langle \vec{I} \rangle_\delta = 1 \\ & \langle \vec{F} \rangle_\gamma, \langle \vec{I} \rangle_\gamma \geq THR \\ 2 & \langle \vec{F} \rangle_\delta = 7, \langle \vec{I} \rangle_\delta = 1 \\ & \langle \vec{F} \rangle_\gamma, \langle \vec{I} \rangle_\gamma \geq THR \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (IV.15)$$

maps its arguments to the distance Body is displaced in Environment.

To implement Features II.d and g for $3.I^M$, Foot generates the sensation (inspired by the sensation we feel when we move our feet)

$$\vec{F}_{sen} = \{\widehat{F}_{sen} \mid \mathbf{i} : h_{sen}, \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t + 1, \mathbf{o} : “ ”\} \quad (IV.16)$$

when it moves Body at external time index τ (i.e., $t = \tau\Delta$), where h_{sen} is determined below; “ ” is a single space character; the bare basic object

$$\widehat{F}_{sen} = [“footSen”, CAL(\tau)]; \quad (IV.17)$$

and $CAL(\tau)$ is defined through Equation IV.11.

When Foot steps on (or when $3.I^M$ is at) the Environment location x it issues the pain or pleasure affect

$$\vec{F}_{afx} = \{\widehat{F}_{afx} \mid \mathbf{i} : h_{afx}, \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t + 1, \mathbf{o} : “ ”\} \quad (IV.18)$$

where h_{afx} is determined below; the bare basic object

$$\widehat{F}_{afx} = [“footAffect”, |AFX(x)|]; \quad (IV.19)$$

$|AFX(x)|$ is defined in Equation IV.2; and the affect type

$$\text{“footAffect”} = \begin{cases} m^- & AFX(x) < 0 \rightarrow \text{pain} \\ & AFX(x) = 0 \rightarrow \# \\ m^+ & AFX(x) > 0 \rightarrow \text{pleasure.} \end{cases} \quad (IV.20)$$

The Sensors output from Foot at internal time $t + 1$ is

$$\widetilde{SEN}_{foot}(t + 1) \triangleq \vec{F}_{sen} \cup \vec{F}_{afx}. \quad (IV.21)$$

F. Eye

At internal time $t + 1$, Eye issues the sensation of seeing (an implementation of Features II.d and g of 3^M) as the basic object

$$\vec{Y}_{sen} = \{\widehat{Y}_{sen} \mid \mathbf{i} : g_{sen}, \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t + 1, \mathbf{o} : “ ”\} \quad (IV.22)$$

where g_{sen} is determined below; and the bare basic object

$$\widehat{Y}_{sen} = [“eyeSen”, CAL(\tau)]. \quad (IV.23)$$

Simultaneously, it generates information, that corresponds to the Environment information perceived by $3.I^M$, as the basic object

$$\vec{Y}_{vis} = \{\widehat{Y}_{vis} \mid \mathbf{i} : g_{vis}, \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t + 1, \mathbf{o} : “ ”\} \quad (IV.24)$$

where g_{vis} is determined below; the bare basic object

$$\widehat{Y}_{vis} = [“eyeVissn”, vision]; \quad (IV.25)$$

$$vision = IMG(x(\tau)); \quad (IV.26)$$

$IMG(x(\tau)) \in \mathbb{M}$ is an image defined in Section IV-A; and $x(\tau)$ is the $3.I^M$ location in Environment defined through Equation IV.14. The types “eyeVissn”, “eyeSen”, “footAffect” and “footSen” are collectively referred to as the *sensory* type.

The Eye output at internal time $t + 1$ is

$$\widetilde{SEN}_{eye}(t + 1) = \vec{Y}_{sen} \cup \vec{Y}_{vis} \quad (IV.27)$$

by using Equations IV.22 and IV.24. Thus, using Equations II.2, IV.21 and IV.27 with SID as the maximum ID of all objects in all $3.I^M$ component states prior to the internal time $t + 1$, the Sensors state is

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{SEN}(t + 1) &= \mathcal{S} \left(\begin{array}{l} ENV(\tau, x), \widetilde{SEN}((\tau - 1)\Delta + 1), \\ \widetilde{FBK}((\tau - 1)\Delta + 2), \\ \widetilde{ACT}((\tau - 1)\Delta + 3) \end{array} \right) \\ &= IDS(\widetilde{SEN}_{foot}(t + 1) \cup \widetilde{SEN}_{eye}(t + 1), SID), \end{aligned} \quad (IV.28)$$

thereby determining the IDs h_{sen} , h_{afx} , g_{sen} and g_{vis} in Equations IV.16, IV.18, IV.22 and IV.24, respectively; and implicitly defining the function \mathcal{S} in Equation II.8 for $3.I^M$. The Sensors state is proven in Theorem E.1 to contain different objects.

At this point, $3.I^M$ Body is fully specified. Let us give details on $3.I^M$ Brain.

G. Memory

At internal time $t + 1$, Memory simply consolidates the Sumer state to yield its state, via Equation II.10, as

$$\widetilde{MEM}(t + 1) = \Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{SUM}(t + 1)). \quad (IV.29)$$

Let the Memory state be split as

$$\widetilde{MEM}(t + 1) = \widetilde{MEM}^o(t + 1) \cup \widetilde{MEM}^w(t + 1) \quad (IV.30)$$

where the sets $\widetilde{MEM}^o(t + 1)$ and $\widetilde{MEM}^w(t + 1)$ are comprised of τ -old and τ -new objects, respectively. It is fed to Transformer to generate novel objects in $3.I^M$, i.e., to fulfil Item II.e.

H. Transformer

Transformer is designed with motivation from the human ability to create new information. It uses the set of operators in Equation II.17 as

$$\Omega = \{\otimes, \oplus\}. \quad (IV.31)$$

Its state at internal time $t + 1$ is

$$\widetilde{XFM}(t + 1) = \Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{XFM}'(t + 1)) \triangleq \bigcup_{j=1}^{NXFM} \dot{X}_j \quad (IV.32)$$

where $NXFM = |\widetilde{XFM}(t + 1)|$;

$$\widetilde{XFM}'(t + 1) = \widetilde{MEM}^o(t + 1) \cup \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\widetilde{XFM}''(t + 1)); \quad (IV.33)$$

$$\widetilde{XFM}''(t + 1) = \widetilde{CMB}(t + 1) \cup \widetilde{CMN}(t + 1); \quad (IV.34)$$

and $\Gamma_{[CNL]}$ and $\Gamma_{[CNM]}$ yield $\hat{\otimes}$ objects only (i.e., with positive consciousness level based on Definition 2) when each of their argument has at least one $\hat{\otimes}$ object, as implied in Section III-J. Utilizing the segregation expressed in Equation IV.30, with $\dot{M}_i^o \in \widetilde{MEM}^o(t + 1)$ and $\dot{M}_j^w \in \widetilde{MEM}^w(t + 1)$, yields

$$\widetilde{CMB}(t + 1) = \bigcup_{i=1, j=1}^{NOLD, NNEW} \Theta(\dot{M}_i^o, \dot{M}_j^w, \oplus) \quad (IV.35)$$

where $NOLD = |\widetilde{MEM}^o(t + 1)|$ and $NNEW = |\widetilde{MEM}^w(t + 1)|$;

$$\widetilde{CMN}(t + 1) = \bigcup_{i=1, j=1}^{NOLD, NNEW} \Theta(\dot{M}_i^o, \dot{M}_j^w, \otimes); \quad (IV.36)$$

and

$$\Theta(\dot{A}, \dot{B}, \omega) = \begin{cases} \dot{A} \omega \dot{B} & \langle A \rangle_\rho = \langle B \rangle_\rho \\ \hat{\otimes} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (IV.37)$$

The upper line of Equation IV.37 implies that the \oplus and \otimes operators act only on \dot{M}_i^o and \dot{M}_j^w with identical type. As a consequence, and proven in Theorem E.3, Transformer only produces basic objects. Equations IV.31 to IV.37 implicitly define \mathcal{T} and $\Gamma_{[XFM]}$ in Equation II.11.

I. Contrector

The action of each binary operator $\omega \in \Omega$ that transpired in Transformer at internal time $t + 1$ is registered by Contrector

to $3.I^M$ (i.e., an implementation of Feature II.g) by generating at $t + 1$ the basic object

$$\mathcal{C}(\dot{X}_j) = \begin{cases} \vec{\mathcal{C}}_j'' & \langle \dot{X}_j \rangle_\gamma \geq THR \\ & \langle \dot{X}_j \rangle_\omega = \text{“bJoin”} \\ & \text{or “common”} \\ \hat{\otimes} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (IV.38)$$

for every object $\dot{X}_j \in \widetilde{XFM}(t + 1)$ defined through Equation IV.32. In Equation IV.38

$$\vec{\mathcal{C}}_j'' = \{ \widehat{\mathcal{C}}_j'' \mid \mathbf{i} : h_j, \mathbf{c} : THR, \\ \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t + 1, \mathbf{o} : \text{“ ”} \} \quad (IV.39)$$

where h_j is determined below; and

$$\widehat{\mathcal{C}}_j'' = [\langle \dot{X}_j \rangle_\omega, CAL(\tau)]. \quad (IV.40)$$

All of the Contrector generated basic objects constitute the set $\widetilde{CON}''(t + 1)$ which is fed to the function

$$IDS(\widetilde{CON}''(t + 1), SID) = \widetilde{CON}'(t + 1) \quad (IV.41)$$

to determine h_j using SID being the maximum ID of objects outputted by Memory and Transformer at $t + 1$. The set $\widetilde{CON}'(t + 1)$ is then consolidated to obtain the Contrector output

$$\widetilde{CON}(t + 1) = \Gamma_{[CNA]}(\widetilde{CON}'(t + 1)) \quad (IV.42)$$

that, as proven in Theorem E.5, could be empty or comprised of objects

$$\vec{\mathcal{C}}_\oplus = \{ [\text{“bJoin”}, CAL(\tau)] \mid \mathbf{i} : h_\oplus, \mathbf{c} : THR, \\ \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t + 1, \mathbf{o} : \text{“ ”} \} \quad (IV.43)$$

and/or

$$\vec{\mathcal{C}}_\otimes = \{ [\text{“common”}, CAL(\tau)] \mid \mathbf{i} : h_\otimes, \mathbf{c} : THR, \\ \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t + 1, \mathbf{o} : \text{“ ”} \} \quad (IV.44)$$

where h_\oplus and h_\otimes are determined by $\Gamma_{[CNA]}$. The Contrector output does not contain $\hat{\otimes}$ due to the action of $\Gamma_{[CNA]}$ when $\widetilde{CON}'(t + 1)$ contains at least one $\hat{\otimes}$ object, as implied in Section III-J. Equations IV.38 to IV.44 implicitly define the function \mathcal{C} in Equation II.12. The types “bJoin” and “common” in Equations IV.43 and IV.44, respectively, are collectively referred to as the *operation* type.

J. Interactor

The Contrector and τ -new Memory outputs at internal time $t + 1$ are united as

$$\widetilde{NSL}(t + 1) = \widetilde{MEM}^w(t + 1) \cup \widetilde{CON}(t + 1) \triangleq \{\dot{N}_i\} \quad (IV.45)$$

where $\widetilde{MEM}^w(t + 1)$ is defined through Equation IV.30. At $\tau > 0$, $\widetilde{NSL}(t + 1)$ is proven in Theorem E.12 to be comprised of τ -new objects consciously perceived by $3.I^M$ when $\widetilde{XFM}(t + 1) \neq \emptyset$. Its elements are made to interact (in compliance with Feature II.f) with the elements of the Transformer state $\widetilde{XFM}(t + 1) \triangleq \{\dot{T}_j\}$ to obtain the Interactor output at $t + 2$

$$\widetilde{INT}(t + 2) = \bigcup_{j=1}^{NXFM} [\Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{INT}'_j(t + 2)) + \epsilon_j] \quad (IV.46)$$

where

$$\widetilde{INT}'_j(t+2) = \bigcup_{i=1}^{NNSL} \langle \dot{N}_i | \oplus | \dot{T}_j \rangle; \quad (IV.47)$$

$NXFM = |\widetilde{XFM}(t+1)|$ and $NNSL = \widetilde{NSL}(t+1)$. The binary operation $\langle \cdot | \oplus | \cdot \rangle$, referred to as the *pertinence interaction*, is inspired by the ability of infants to compare physical objects [3]; and accounts how similar the transformation outcome \dot{T}_j to the τ -new objects \dot{N}_i . It is defined as

$$\langle \dot{N}_i | \oplus | \dot{T}_j \rangle = \gamma_{i,j} \dot{T}_j \quad (IV.48)$$

where the so called, *scalar consciousness gain* (whose multiplication to any object is implicitly defined in Equation III.51)

$$\gamma_{i,j} = \langle N_i || T_j \rangle \langle \dot{N}_i \rangle_\gamma \quad (IV.49)$$

which implies that the higher the consciousness level of \dot{N}_i and the more \dot{N}_i and \dot{T}_j are similar the more consciousness level amplified the object \dot{T}_j is. The interaction outcomes between all the τ -new objects \dot{N}_i and a given Transformer state element \dot{T}_j constitute $\widetilde{INT}'_j(t+2)$ in Equation IV.47 that is then consolidated as expressed in Equation IV.46. To fulfil Feature II.h, the consolidation result is then added (addition implicitly defined in Equation III.51) with a uniformly distributed random value ϵ_j where $-MXR \leq \epsilon_j \leq MXR$, and $MXR \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is a fixed value. The interactions, consolidation and random value addition are repeated for every element of the Transformer state $\widetilde{XFM}(t+1)$. All the repetition outcomes are then united — thereby implicitly defining $\Gamma_{[INT]}$ in Equation II.13 — to form the Interactor state $\widetilde{INT}(t+2)$ which, together with $\widetilde{NSL}(t+1)$, is feed to Selector.

K. Selector

Inside Selector, objects are processed by the so-called *sigmoid function* (influenced by ANN) defined as

$$SGM(c) = \zeta \tanh\left(\frac{\sigma c}{2}\right) \quad (IV.50)$$

where c is a consciousness level; and σ and ζ are related in Equation A.4 (in Appendix) whereby

$$SGM(THR) = 1.5THR \quad (IV.51)$$

and

$$SGM(THR/3.0) = THR. \quad (IV.52)$$

The sigmoid function is plotted in Figure 4 with abscissa and coordinate in units of THR . It satisfies $SGM(c) < SGM(d)$, \forall consciousness levels c, d with $c < d$, i.e., it is a monotonically increasing function of the consciousness level.

Prior to applying the sigmoid function, the Interactor output objects at internal time $t+2$ are sorted according to their consciousness level to obtain the ordered set

$$\widetilde{SRT} = \left\{ \dot{S}_i \left| \begin{array}{l} \langle \dot{S}_i \rangle_\gamma \geq \langle \dot{S}_j \rangle_\gamma, \\ \forall 1 \leq i < j \leq NINT; \\ \dot{S}_i \in \widetilde{INT}(t+2) \end{array} \right. \right\} \quad (IV.53)$$

where $NINT = |\widetilde{INT}(t+2)|$. Then, the following algorithm, whose first line in C++ syntax and with a loop index i , is executed:

Fig. 4: Sample Sigmoid function

for (int $i = 1$; $i \leq NINT$; $i++$)

- 1) The object $\dot{S}_i \in \widetilde{SRT}$ is inputted to the sigmoid function to obtain the object $\dot{S}'_i = SGM(\dot{S}_i)$.
- 2) If $\langle \dot{S}'_i \rangle_\gamma < THR$ then the loop breaks, at which the loop index is denoted as l .
- 3) The sum of consciousness level $SMC(i) = \sum_{n=1}^i \langle \dot{S}'_n \rangle_\gamma$ is taken.
- 4) If $SMC(i) > LMC$ then the loop breaks, at which the loop index is denoted as g ; the threshold LMC is a constant.

end

if $i > NINT$

As proven in Theorem E.7, all the Sigmoid outputs can be segregated into the set of objects

$$\widetilde{SB}(t+2) = \emptyset \quad (IV.54)$$

subconsciously perceived by $3.I^M$, and the set of objects

$$\widetilde{CN}(t+2) = \{ \dot{S}'_i \mid 1 \leq i \leq NINT \} \quad (IV.55)$$

consciously perceived by $3.I^M$.

else

Each object $\dot{T}_i = \frac{\dot{S}_i}{NRM}$, $\forall i \geq M$, is inputted to the sigmoid function to output the object $\dot{T}'_i = SGM(\dot{T}_i)$ where $M = \min\{l, g+1\}$, $NRM = \langle \dot{S}_M \rangle_\gamma / (THR/3.0 - \epsilon)$, and $\epsilon \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is a fixed value. The objects \dot{T}'_i and \dot{S}'_j , $1 \leq j < M$, are subconsciously and consciously perceived by $3.I^M$, respectively, as proven in Theorem E.7. Thus, the Sigmoid outputs (e.g., \dot{T}'_i and \dot{S}'_j) can be segregated into the set of objects

$$\widetilde{SB}(t+2) = \{ \dot{T}'_i \mid M \leq i \leq NINT \} \quad (IV.56)$$

subconsciously perceived by $3.I^M$, and the set of objects

$$\widetilde{CN}(t+2) = \{ \dot{S}'_j \mid 1 \leq j < M \} \quad (IV.57)$$

consciously perceived by $3.I^M$.

end

Fig. 5: Selector algorithm

Whether $i > NINT$ or otherwise, let us form

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{SEL}'(t+2) &= \widetilde{CN}(t+2) \cup \widetilde{SB}(t+2) \cup \widetilde{NSL}(t+1) \\ &= \widetilde{INT}^{(1)}(t+2) \cup \widetilde{NSL}(t+1). \end{aligned} \quad (IV.58)$$

By Equations II.14, III.45, and IV.54 to IV.57, the Selector output is

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{SEL}(t+2) &= \mathcal{L} \left(\widetilde{INT}(t+2), \widetilde{CON}(t+1), \right. \\ &\quad \left. \widetilde{MEM}(t+1) \right) \\ &= \Gamma_{[CNM]} \left(\widetilde{SEL}'(t+2) \right) \\ &\triangleq \widetilde{SUB}(t+2) \cup \widetilde{CNS}(t+2) \end{aligned} \quad (IV.59)$$

segregated into the exclusive sets $\widetilde{SUB}(t+2)$ and $\widetilde{CNS}(t+2)$ comprised of objects subconsciously and consciously perceived by $3.I^M$, respectively. Equation IV.59 implicitly defines the function \mathcal{L} in Equation II.14.

L. Executioner

At internal time $t+2$, the Selector outputs are inputted to Feedback together with the Executioner generated force

$$\begin{aligned} \mathring{F} &= \{[\text{“force”}, 3] \mid \mathbf{i} : h_f, \mathbf{c} : THR, \\ &\quad \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t+2, \mathbf{o} : \text{“ ”}\} \end{aligned} \quad (IV.60)$$

and intention

$$\begin{aligned} \mathring{I} &= \{[\text{“footIntnt”}, 1] \mid \mathbf{i} : h_i, \mathbf{c} : THR, \\ &\quad \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t+2, \mathbf{o} : \text{“ ”}\} \end{aligned} \quad (IV.61)$$

where h_f and h_i are determined below. The Executioner state is

$$\widetilde{XEC}(t+2) = IDS \left(\mathring{F} \cup \mathring{I}, SID \right) \quad (IV.62)$$

where SID is the maximum ID of the objects in $\widetilde{SEL}(t+2)$; and the function IDS determines h_f and h_i . Equations IV.60 to IV.62 implicitly define the function \mathcal{X} in Equation II.15. The force and intention activate Foot to move $3.I^M$ to location $x(\tau+1)$, according to Equations IV.14 and IV.15, at internal time $(\tau+1)\Delta$. The Executioner output is inputted to Feedback and Actuators at $t+2$.

M. Feedback

In order not to violate the memory constraints of the computing machine that executes $3.I^M$, the number of Feedback output objects is restricted as follows: At internal time $t+2$, if $|\widetilde{SEL}(t+2)| \leq MXS$ then $\widetilde{SEL}(t+2)$ is left unchanged where $MXS \in \mathbb{N}^+$ is fixed. Otherwise, any object $\mathring{S} \in \widetilde{SEL}(t+2)$ with $\langle \mathring{S} \rangle_\gamma < MXC$ is removed from $\widetilde{SEL}(t+2)$ where $MXC \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is a fixed value. Let the reduced $\widetilde{SEL}(t+2)$ be denoted as $\widetilde{SEL}'(t+2)$ whose elements are then consciousness level-sorted from largest to the least. If $|\widetilde{SEL}'(t+2)| > MXS$ still then the first MXS sorted elements of $\widetilde{SEL}'(t+2)$ are retained while the rest are removed from $\widetilde{SEL}'(t+2)$ (the removal is inspired by human forgetfulness). Let the depleted $\widetilde{SEL}'(t+2)$ be denoted as $\widetilde{SEL}^c(t+2)$ and used in

$$\widetilde{FBK}'(t+2) = \widetilde{SEL}^c(t+2) \cup \widetilde{XEC}(t+2). \quad (IV.63)$$

Finally, the Feedback output is

$$\widetilde{FBK}(t+2) = \Gamma_{[CNL]} \left(\widetilde{FBK}'(t+2) \right) \quad (IV.64)$$

that implicitly defines the function $\Gamma_{[FBK]}$ in Equation II.16, and inputted to Sumer. Its elements, consciously perceived by $3.I^M$, constitute the $3.I^M$ output at internal time $t+2$.

The just-presented algorithm of limiting the number of Feedback output objects, the Figure 5 algorithm, and the algorithms in other areas of Section IV, individually transpires only in a fixed and independent internal time interval δ , such that, $3.I^M$ is still considered as dynamical despite its use of algorithmic processes. This completes the specifications of $3.I^M$ whose interactions with Environment are investigated next.

V. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

$3.I^M$ interacts with its environment under parameter values listed in Table I whose first to last columns correspond, respectively, to the parameter symbol, value/s and related reference. In Table I, the parameter MXR is the maximum value the absolute of any random sample ϵ_j (employed in Equation IV.46) can take, and can either be 5×10^{-6} or 0.25. On the contrary, the other Table I parametric values are fixed and endowed to $3.I^M$ on any of the $3.I^M$ -Environment interactions below. At first, MXR is made equal to 5×10^{-6} and then $3.I^M$ is made to interact with each Environment instances. Then, it is changed to 0.25 at which $3.I^M$ is again made to interact with each of the same Environment instances.

TABLE I: Parameters of $3.I^M$

Symbol	Value/s	Reference
Δ	4	Equation II.7
THR	1.0	Item II-B.2
PUF_{\oplus}	2/3	Section III-I
PTN	1/5	Section III-I
MXR	5×10^{-6} , 0.25	Section IV-J
LMC	6.0	Item IV-K.4
ϵ	0.01	Section IV-K
MXS	75	Section IV-M
MXC	0.001	Section IV-M

There are three Environment instances, labelled as ENV_1 , ENV_2 and ENV_3 ; each has location x assigned with a pair of image $IMG(x)$ and affect value $AFX(x)$ presented in Table II where $AFX(x)$ is right above its pair $IMG(x)$. In any column in this table, the second to the last image from the top are derived from the topmost image, such that, all the column images are referred as being *related*. There are 11 sequences of at least three related images (thereby fulfilling Feature II.i) in each of the Environment instances. These instances differ on the location and neighbouring images of each of the sequences as illustrated in Tables III to V which are composed of 3-row blocks where the first to the third row signify the Environment location x , affect value and image at x , respectively. Let us then investigate the $3.I^M$ activities as it interacts with each of the instances.

TABLE II: Images in Environment

Column #	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Affect	2^0	2^4	2^8	2^{12}	2^{16}	2^{20}	-2^1	-2^5	-2^9
Image									
Affect	2^1	2^5	2^9	2^{13}	2^{17}	2^{21}	-2^2	-2^6	-2^{10}
Image									
Affect	2^2	2^6	2^{10}	2^{14}	2^{18}	2^{22}	-2^3	-2^7	-2^{11}
Image									
Affect	2^3	2^7	2^{11}	2^{15}	2^{19}	2^{23}	-2^4	-2^8	-2^{12}
Image									

TABLE III: Environment instance ENV_1

$x = 0$	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
$AFX = 2^4$	-2^2	-2^1	-2^4	2^6	2^7	2^5	2^2	2^3	2^1
$x = 10$	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
$AFX = 2^{11}$	-2^3	-2^6	-2^7	-2^8	-2^1	-2^8	-2^1	-2^8	2^1
$x = 20$	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
$AFX = 2^4$	2^0	2^8	2^9	2^{11}	-2^5	2^{12}	2^{19}	2^{18}	2^{17}
$x = 30$	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39
$AFX = 2^0$	2^8	-2^{12}	-2^{11}	-2^{10}	2^{13}	2^{15}	2^{14}	2^{17}	-2^2
$x = 40$	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49
$AFX = 2^{19}$	-2^3	2^{18}	2^{23}	2^{20}	2^{21}	2^1	2^{10}	2^3	2^{11}
$x = 50$	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59
$AFX = 2^2$	2^9	2^3	2^2	2^1	2^8	-2^7	-2^6	-2^8	2^0

TABLE IV: Environment instance ENV_2

$x = 0$	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
$AFX = 2^0$	2^6	2^9	2^{11}	2^{10}	-2^{12}	2^{20}	2^6	2^5	2^7
$x = 10$	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
$AFX = 2^{19}$	2^{22}	2^{14}	2^{13}	2^{15}	-2^3	-2^8	2^3	2^2	2^1
$x = 20$	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
$AFX = 2^{10}$	2^5	2^9	2^6	2^{11}	2^7	-2^{10}	2^{15}	-2^2	-2^4
$x = 30$	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39
$AFX = -2^3$	2^0	2^{15}	-2^{11}	-2^{10}	-2^{12}	2^{19}	2^9	2^{23}	2^{22}
$x = 40$	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49
$AFX = 2^{21}$	2^8	-2^2	-2^7	-2^8	-2^6	-2^3	2^{20}	2^{19}	2^{17}
$x = 50$	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59
$AFX = 2^{18}$	2^3	2^{11}	2^{15}	-2^3	-2^{12}	-2^2	-2^{11}	-2^4	-2^{10}

A. $3.I^M$ activities

Environment ENV_1 is illustrated in Table III and interacted by $3.I^M$ endowed with $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$. Thereby, $3.I^M$ moves at external time index $\tau = 0$ to the ENV_1 location $x = 0$ (based on the initial condition of Equation IV.14) where its Eye and Foot sensed the pair $IMG(0)$ and $AFX(0)$, respectively. Consequently, at internal time $t = 1$, Foot issues the object $\vec{F}_{afx}(1)$ (defined by Equations IV.18 and IV.19) with affect value of $AFX(0) = 2^4$ and Eye issues the object $\vec{Y}_{vis}(1)$ (defined by Equations IV.24 to IV.26) with image $IMG(0)$ of a house at ENV_1 location $x = 0$ in Table III. **Rule 1:** Any bare object $\langle \hat{O} \rangle_\beta = [“eyeVissn”, IMG(x)]$ issued by Eye at external time index τ has data/image located in any Environment instance at $x = \tau$, $\forall 0 \leq \tau < \infty$, as proven in Theorem E.10. ■ The perceptual act of Eye and Foot triggers Sensors to issue the objects $\vec{F}_{sen}(1)$ (defined by Equations IV.16 and IV.17) and $\vec{Y}_{sen}(1)$ (defined by Equations IV.22 and IV.23). Based on Equation IV.28, the four Sensors-issued objects ($\vec{F}_{afx}(1)$, $\vec{Y}_{vis}(1)$, $\vec{F}_{sen}(1)$ and $\vec{Y}_{sen}(1)$) constitute $\vec{SEN}(\tau\Delta + 1) = \vec{SEN}(1)$ which is united with $\vec{FBK}(\tau\Delta - 2) = \vec{FBK}(-2) = \emptyset$ based on the initial condition stated in Item II-B.1. By Equation II.9, the union yields $\vec{SUM}(1)$ from which Equations II.10 to II.16

are computed to obtain the Executioner and Feedback outputs $\vec{XEC}(\tau\Delta + 2) = \vec{XEC}(2)$ and $\vec{FBK}(2)$, respectively. And by Equation II.6, the Executioner output is fed to Actuators, at internal time $t + 3 = 3$, that by Equation IV.14 moves $3.I^M$ at external time index $\tau = 1$ to the ENV_1 location $1 = x(\tau) = \tau$ (as mentioned in Rule 1). Then, the interaction process (from $3.I^M$ stepping at image $IMG(0)$ to Executioner and Feedback outputting) just described is repeated as the external time index τ progresses until all the pairs in ENV_1 are sequentially sensed by $3.I^M$. In the course of this repetition Sensors may consecutively issue “eyeVissn”-type basic objects with related data/image. Basic objects such as these are referred as being *related* and as Sensors-issued “eyeVissn”-type basic objects (SIETBOs).

B. Object Tabulation rules

Some Feedback-outputted objects from the above interactions are presented in Table VI whose *header* indicates the external time index τ at which they are outputted, and last column lists the table row number. The entries in this table abide by the following: **Rule 2:** Any object symbol with subscript has the latter as its ID, i.e., $\langle \hat{A}_{ID} \rangle_\eta = ID$. ■ **Rule 3:** Any object \hat{A}_{ID} presented under column τ is $\hat{\emptyset}$ and outputted

TABLE V: Environment instance ENV_3

$x = 0$	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
$AFX = -2^6$	-2^{11}	-2^8	-2^{10}	-2^7	-2^{12}	2^3	2^5	2^{13}	2^{15}
$x = 10$	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
$AFX = 2^{14}$	2^{20}	-2^2	2^2	2^1	2^3	2^{19}	2^8	-2^2	-2^3
$x = 20$	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
$AFX = -2^4$	2^{14}	2^{19}	2^{10}	2^9	2^{11}	2^5	-2^{11}	2^{18}	2^{13}
$x = 30$	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39
$AFX = 2^{18}$	2^{14}	2^{19}	2^{15}	-2^9	2^7	2^5	2^6	2^{18}	-2^6
$x = 40$	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49
$AFX = 2^{22}$	2^{23}	2^{21}	-2^7	-2^1	-2^{10}	-2^{11}	-2^{12}	2^0	2^8
$x = 50$	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59
$AFX = 2^{18}$	2^{17}	2^{19}	-2^9	-2^4	-2^8	-2^6	-2^7	2^0	-2^9

by Feedback at internal time $t+2$. ■ Any object \hat{A} is presented as a block of 6 rows which respectively correspond to its ID $\langle \hat{A} \rangle_\eta$, consciousness level $\langle \hat{A} \rangle_\gamma$, internal time label $\langle \hat{A} \rangle_\tau$, bare object $\langle \hat{A} \rangle_\beta$ expression, type $\langle \langle \hat{A} \rangle_\beta \rangle_\rho$ and data $\langle \langle \hat{A} \rangle_\beta \rangle_\delta$. **Rule 4:** The object/s described by the expression “ $(r_1 : r_2, c, T)$ ” is presented at the block of rows r_1 to r_2 and column number c in table T . A specific table location is denoted as (r, c, T) where r is its row number. ■ **Rule 5:** Any bare object $\langle \hat{O} \rangle_\beta$ expressed under column τ as two integers I and J with a binary operator $\omega \in \Omega$ in between them is formed in Transformer at internal time $t+1$ by applying ω to the bare object $\langle \hat{O}_I \rangle_\beta$ and $\langle \hat{O}_J \rangle_\beta$, i.e., $\langle \hat{O} \rangle_\beta = \langle \hat{O}_I \rangle_\beta \omega \langle \hat{O}_J \rangle_\beta \in \langle \widehat{XFM}(\tau\Delta + 1) \rangle_\beta$ based on Equation II.11 ■ For example, the bare object expressed as “ $19 \otimes 40$ ” and presented at (58, 3, VI) is of the object $\hat{O}_{45} \in \widehat{FBK}(3\Delta + 1)$ represented at (55:60, 3, VI) and has $\langle \hat{O}_{45} \rangle_\beta = \langle \hat{O}_{19} \rangle_\beta \otimes \langle \hat{O}_{40} \rangle_\beta \in \langle \widehat{XFM}(3\Delta + 1) \rangle_\beta$.

The first eight blocks (of 6 rows) in Table VI list basic objects with type “eyeSen”, “footSen”, “bJoin”, “common”, “force”, “footIntnt”, “footAffect” and “eyeVissn” respectively. The first four of these basic objects have identical data (listed at rows 6, 12, 18 and 24), as proven in Theorem E.16, for any fixed external time index $0 \leq \tau \leq 7$; except at $\tau = 0$ when the “bJoin” and “common”-type basic objects are absent in

$\widehat{FBK}(2)$. The “force” and “footIntnt”-type basic objects are listed at the fifth and sixth blocks. Each of them has similar data (presented at rows 30 and 36, respectively), as proven in Theorem E.9, $\forall 0 \leq \tau \leq 7$.

Rule 6: The seventh and eighth blocks (of 6 rows) in Table VI present the “footAffect” (could be m^+ or m^-) and “eyeVissn”-type basic objects, respectively. And, as mentioned above, the first two blocks list the “eyeSen” and “footSen”-type basic objects, respectively. These four basic objects are Feedback outputted and issued by Sensors at external time index τ if they are presented under column τ . ■ The blocks below the eighth present objects with ascending ID number.

The just-presented block numbering scheme for Table VI is however different for the object-presenting tables below whose first row after the table header is labelled 37, e.g., in Table VII. The rows supposed to be labelled 1 to 36 in these tables are not shown for brevity as their entries are simply the repetition, as proven in Theorem E.16, of the entries at rows 1 to 36 under columns 2 to 9 of Table VI. However, they are shown in the tables in <https://whizkod.com/ThreeM/Outputs.html>. **Rule 7:** The blocks of the object-presenting table whose labelled 37 first row after the table header are counted starting at 7 (i.e., row 37 belongs to the seventh block). ■

Continued: Feedback output at Environment instance ENV_1 , $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\tau = 0 : 9$

τ	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	#
ID	4	10	21	42	74	126	205	311	448	582	37
Conscious level	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	38
Internal time	1	5	9	13	17	21	25	29	33	37	39
Bare											40
Type	m^+	m^-	m^-	m^-	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^+	41
Data	2^4	2^2	2	2^4	2^6	2^7	2^5	2^2	2^3	2	42
ID	2	8	19	40	72	124	203	309	446	580	43
Conscious level	1	1	1.5	1.4679	1	1	1	1	1	1	44
Internal time	1	5	9	13	17	21	25	29	33	37	45
Bare											46
Type	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	47
Data		48									
ID		12	26	28	76	72	72	392	309	309	49
Conscious level		1	0.084666	1.4252	0.31692	1.2941	1.4647	1	1.4467	1.5103	50
Internal time		5	9	9	17	17	17	29	29	29	51
Bare		$1 \oplus 7$	$2 \oplus 19$	$8 \oplus 19$	$26 \otimes 72$			$204 \oplus 310$			52
Type		eyeSen	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	footSen	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	53
Data		3		54							
ID			27	45	94	127	172	393	449	583	55
Conscious level			1	1.5264	1.1345	1.4112	1.3406	1	1.4864	1.5115	56
Internal time			9	13	17	21	21	29	33	37	57
Bare			$7 \oplus 18$	$19 \otimes 40$	$26 \oplus 72$	$26 \otimes 124$	$72 \oplus 124$	$205 \oplus 311$	$309 \otimes 446$	$309 \otimes 580$	58
Type			eyeSen	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	m^+	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	59
Data			6		60						
ID			28	48	95	171	217		505	608	61
Conscious level			1.5104	1.4684	1.0338	1	1.4904		1.3273	1.4975	62
Internal time			9	13	17	21	25		33	37	63
Bare			$8 \oplus 19$	$28 \otimes 40$	$28 \oplus 72$	$71 \oplus 123$	$72 \otimes 203$		$309 \oplus 446$	$449 \otimes 580$	64
Type			eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeSen	eyeVissn		eyeVissn	eyeVissn	65
Data				66							

Continued: Feedback output at Environment instance ENV_1 , $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\tau = 0 : 9$

τ	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	#
ID			29	60	98	172	218		507	637	67
Conscious level			1	1.3748	1	1.2966	1.5274		1	1.5269	68
Internal time			9	13	17	21	25		33	37	69
Bare			9 \oplus 20	28 \oplus 40	39 \oplus 71	72 \oplus 124	76 \otimes 203		311 \oplus 448	309 \oplus 580	70
Type			footSen	eyeVissn	eyeSen	eyeVissn	eyeVissn		m^+	eyeVissn	71
Data			6		72						
ID			30		99	174	259				73
Conscious level			1		1.0578	1	1.3577				74
Internal time			9		17	21	25				75
Bare			10 \oplus 21		40 \oplus 72	74 \oplus 126	72 \oplus 203				76
Type			m^-		eyeVissn	m^+	eyeVissn				77
Data			$2^2 + 2$						78		

The tabulation Rules 3 to 7 for Table VI also apply to Tables VII to XI and, except for Rule 7, also to the tables in <https://whizkod.com/ThreeM/Outputs.html> that list, \forall external time indices $0 \leq \tau \leq 59$, all the objects in the $3.I^M$ output (comprised of all Feedback output objects consciously perceived by $3.I^M$). Any object-presenting table presents only selected Feedback output objects subconsciously perceived by $3.I^M$ for brevity, e.g., the object \hat{O}_{76} presented at (49:54, 4, VI).

C. Generalization

To help investigate the ability of $3.I^M$ to generalize its sensed objects, let us explore Table XII which presents the generalization outcomes. For a given row R in Table XII, the first column contains the case number. The second column has the data/image of the SIETBO \vec{A} at external time index τ_1 which is indicated in the third column and is equal to the location x_1 (as proven in Theorem E.10) in ENV_1 where the data is sensed by $3.I^M$. The data/image $\langle\langle \vec{A} \rangle\rangle_\delta$ and the location x_1 are also presented in Table III, and their relationship applies to the entries of the fourth and fifth, and the sixth and seventh columns of row R in Table XII. In the latter, the data/images $\langle\langle \vec{A} \rangle\rangle_\delta$, $\langle\langle \vec{B} \rangle\rangle_\delta$ and $\langle\langle \vec{C} \rangle\rangle_\delta$ are presented at the second, fourth and sixth columns, respectively. The column in Table II at which they are found is indicated at the ninth column, labelled *Col*, of row R in Table XII. In the latter, the eighth column contains the data/image $\langle\langle \vec{C}_\otimes \rangle\rangle_\delta$ where $\langle\vec{C}_\otimes\rangle_\beta \in \langle\overline{FBK}(\tau\Delta + 2)\rangle_\beta$ is the generalization of the *BCSIETBOs* (bare component of SIETBOs) $\langle\vec{A}\rangle_\beta$, $\langle\vec{B}\rangle_\beta$ and $\langle\vec{C}\rangle_\beta$; and \vec{C}_\otimes is outputted by $3.I^M$ (i.e., \vec{C}_\otimes is consciously

perceived by $3.I^M$) at external time index τ . The tenth column contains the table location $(r_1 : r_2, \tau, T)$ (nomenclature is based on Rule 4) at which \vec{C}_\otimes is listed.

As an example, at the Case 5 row of Table XII the images in the second, fourth and sixth columns are also found in Environment ENV_1 at locations $x = 1, 2$ and 3 , respectively, as illustrated in Table III. They are the data of the consecutive SIETBOs at external time indices 1, 2 and 3 and presented at (43:48, 1, VI), (43:48, 2, VI) and (43:48, 3, VI), respectively. They are also found at the seventh column of Table II (i.e., they are related), a column number indicated at the Case 5 row and ninth column of Table XII. The generalization of the *BCSIETBOs* has data/image presented at the Case 5 row and eighth column of Table XII; and is a basic object listed at (55:60, 3, VI).

Let us now justify the $3.I^M$ ability to generalize some sets of consecutively issued bare objects by Sensors, the ability supported in Dynamics F.1.

1) *Cases 1 to 4:* Let us investigate Case 1 in Table XII. First, consider the object \hat{O}_{608} presented at (61:66, 9, VI) that, by Rules 2 and 5, has bare component

$$\langle\hat{O}_{608}\rangle_\beta = \langle\hat{O}_{449}\rangle_\beta \otimes \langle\hat{O}_{580}\rangle_\beta \quad (V.1)$$

indicated at (64, 9, VI). The object \hat{O}_{580} is presented at (43:48, 9, VI) (i.e., at the eighth block from the header) which implies, by Rule 6, that there is a SIETBO \hat{O}_{580}^S at $\tau = 9$ where

$$\langle\hat{O}_{580}^S\rangle_\beta = [\text{“eyeVissn”, } I_{580}] = \langle\hat{O}_{580}\rangle_\beta; \quad (V.2)$$

and, by Rule 1, I_{580} is the image at Environment ENV_1 location $x = 9$ and shown in Table III. The object \hat{O}_{449} in Equation V.1

TABLE VII: Feedback output at Environment instance ENV_1 , $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\tau = 10 : 19$

τ	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	#
ID	715	854	984	1121	1257	1392	1533	1678	1819	1956	37
Conscious level	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	38
Internal time	41	45	49	53	57	61	65	69	73	77	39
Bare											40
Type	m^+	m^-	m^-	m^-	m^-	m^-	m^-	m^-	m^-	m^+	41
Data	2^{11}	2^3	2^6	2^7	2^8	2	2^8	2	2^8	2	42
ID	713	852	982	1119	1255	1390	1531	1676	1817	1954	43
Conscious level	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1.0012	1	44
Internal time	41	45	49	53	57	61	65	69	73	77	45
Bare											46
Type	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	47
Data		48									
ID	716	910	1048	982	982	1483	1598	1754	1887	2022	49
Conscious level	1.2021	1	1	1.4514	1.5017	1	1	0.41226	1.202	1	50
Internal time	41	45	49	49	49	61	65	69	73	77	51
Bare	$309 \otimes$ 713	$712 \oplus$ 851	$851 \oplus$ 981			1254 \oplus 1389	1389 \oplus 1530	1531 \oplus 1676	1676 \oplus 1817	1816 \oplus 1953	52
Type	eyeVissn	eyeSen	eyeSen	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeSen	eyeSen	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeSen	53
Data		12	54								
ID	734		1050	1122	1122	1484	1599	1756	1889	2024	55
Conscious level	1.0132		1	1.4767	1.5006	0.16456	1.0293	1.5136	1.5154	1	56
Internal time	41		49	53	53	61	65	69	73	77	57
Bare	$446 \otimes$ 713		$853 \oplus$ 983	$982 \otimes$ 1119	$982 \otimes$ 1119	1255 \oplus 1390	1390 \oplus 1531	1533 \oplus 1678	1678 \oplus 1819	1818 \oplus 1955	58
Type	eyeVissn		footSen	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	m^-	m^-	footSen	59
Data		$2^8 + 2$	$2^8 + 2$	12	60						
ID	797			1179	1258	1486	1600	1805	1908		61
Conscious level	1			1	1.5039	1	1	1.3245	1.0209		62
Internal time	41			53	57	61	65	69	73		63
Bare	$579 \oplus$ 712			$981 \oplus$ 1118	$982 \otimes$ 1255	1257 \oplus 1392	1391 \oplus 1532	1662 \oplus 1678	1741 \oplus 1817		64
Type	eyeSen			eyeSen	eyeVissn	m^-	footSen	m^-	eyeVissn		65
Data	6			48			66				

Continued: Feedback output at Environment instance ENV_1 , $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\tau = 10 : 19$

τ	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	#
ID	799			1180	1285	1513	1601	1808	1942		67
Conscious level	1			1.358	1.5032	0.51649	1.4679	1.1053	1.4177		68
Internal time	41			53	57	61	65	69	73		69
Bare	581 \oplus 714			982 \oplus 1119	1122 \otimes 1255	1343 \oplus 1392	1392 \oplus 1533	1665 \oplus 1678	1805 \oplus 1819		70
Type	footSen			eyeVissn	eyeVissn	m^-	m^-	m^-	m^-		71
Data	6				$2^8 + 2^7 + 2$	$2^8 + 2$	$2^8 + 2^7 + 2^6 + 2$	$2^8 + 2^7 + 2$		72	
ID	800			1182	1343		1662		1945		73
Conscious level	1			1	0.38951		1.0149		1.2011		74
Internal time	41			53	57		65		73		75
Bare	582 \oplus 715			984 \oplus 1121	1121 \oplus 1257		1513 \oplus 1533		1808 \oplus 1819		76
Type	m^+			m^-	m^-		m^-		m^-		77
Data	$2^{11} + 2$			$2^7 + 2^6$	$2^8 + 2^7$		$2^8 + 2^7 + 2$		$2^8 + 2^7 + 2^6 + 2$		78

is presented at (55:60, 8, VI) and, by Rules 2 and 5, has bare component

$$\langle \hat{O}_{449} \rangle_{\beta} = \langle \hat{O}_{309} \rangle_{\beta} \otimes \langle \hat{O}_{446} \rangle_{\beta} \quad (\text{V.3})$$

presented at (58, 8, VI). The object \hat{O}_{446} is presented at (43:48, 8, VI) which implies, by Rule 6, that there is a SIETBO \hat{O}_{446}^S at $\tau = 9$ where

$$\langle \hat{O}_{446}^S \rangle_{\beta} = [\text{"eyeVissn"}, I_{446}] = \langle \hat{O}_{446} \rangle_{\beta}; \quad (\text{V.4})$$

and, by Rule 1, I_{446} is the image at ENV_1 location $x = 8$ and presented in Table III. The object \hat{O}_{309} in Equation V.3 is presented at (43:48, 7, VI) which implies, by Rule 6, that there is a SIETBO \hat{O}_{309}^S at $\tau = 7$ where

$$\langle \hat{O}_{309}^S \rangle_{\beta} = [\text{"eyeVissn"}, I_{309}] = \langle \hat{O}_{309} \rangle_{\beta}; \quad (\text{V.5})$$

and, by Rule 1, I_{309} is the image at ENV_1 location $x = 7$ in Table III.

Now, using Equations III.21, and V.1 to V.5 and Theorem B.13 yields

$$\langle \hat{O}_{608} \rangle_{\beta} = \langle \hat{O}_{580}^S \rangle_{\beta} \otimes \langle \hat{O}_{446}^S \rangle_{\beta} \otimes \langle \hat{O}_{309}^S \rangle_{\beta} \\ = [\text{"eyeVissn"}, I_{580} \otimes I_{446} \otimes I_{309}]. \quad (\text{V.6})$$

Therefore, considering Equation III.25, $3.I^M$ is capable of generalizing the BCSIETBOs $\langle \hat{O}_{309}^S \rangle_{\beta}$, $\langle \hat{O}_{446}^S \rangle_{\beta}$ and $\langle \hat{O}_{580}^S \rangle_{\beta}$ it successively perceived at external time indices $\tau = 7, 8, 9$ through its Sensors; and $\langle \hat{O}_{608} \rangle_{\beta}$ is their generalization, presented at (65:66, 9, VI), that has data/image shown at the Case 1 row and ninth column of Table XII. Within the scope of this conclusion, the definition of generalization in Equation

III.25 is justified as every black pixel in the data/image $\langle \hat{O}_{608} \rangle_{\delta} = I_{580} \otimes I_{446} \otimes I_{309}$ (shown at (66, 9, VI)) is also found in the data/image $\langle \hat{O}_{309} \rangle_{\delta} = I_{309}$, $\langle \hat{O}_{446} \rangle_{\delta} = I_{446}$ and $\langle \hat{O}_{580} \rangle_{\delta} = I_{580}$ (shown at ENV_1 locations $x = 7, 8, 9$ of Table III, respectively) at identical pixel position. Further, the conclusion is made through the above analytical investigation — this exhibits the interpretability of $3.I^M$.

Case 2 pertains to the sequence of icons perceived by $3.I^M$ at $\tau = 12$ to 14 in ENV_1 and illustrated in Table III. The generalization in Case 2 is the bare object listed at (65 : 66, 14, VII) and can be proven as such by applying the analytical scheme undertaken to prove the generalization in Case 1. The image sequences for Cases 1 and 2 are repeated at $\tau = 52$ to 54 and 56 to 58, respectively, with identical generalization results — based on the entries at (65 : 66, 54, XI) and (71 : 72, 58, XI) — but with different neighbouring icons, as depicted in Table III. Thus, for the cited cases, the ability of $3.I^M$ to generalize the images in the sequences is not affected by the neighbouring icons nor by the external time indices of these sequences. Lastly, the generalization in Cases 3 and 4 of Table XII is presented at (67 : 72, 34, IX) and (67 : 72, 37, IX), respectively; and can be justified by applying the last cited analytical scheme.

2) *Cases 5 to 9*: The justification approach for the Case 1 to 4 generalization is unsuitable for the other cases in Table XII, e.g., Case 5 which is dealt as follows: Consider the object \hat{O}_8 presented at (43:48, 1, VI) which implies, by Rule 6, that

TABLE VIII: Feedback output at Environment instance ENV_1 , $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\tau = 20 : 29$

τ	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	#
ID	2084	2221	2356	2493	2627	2760	2886	3021	3160	3296	37
Conscious level	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	38
Internal time	81	85	89	93	97	101	105	109	113	117	39
Bare											40
Type	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^-	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^+	41
Data	2^4	1	2^8	2^9	2^{11}	2^5	2^{12}	2^{19}	2^{18}	2^{17}	42
ID	2082	2219	2354	2491	2625	2758	2884	3019	3158	3294	43
Conscious level	1	1	1	1.5	1.5193	1	1	1	1	1	44
Internal time	81	85	89	93	97	101	105	109	113	117	45
Bare											46
Type	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	47
Data		48									
ID		2282	2432	2508	2491		2948	3022	3019	3297	49
Conscious level		1	1	1.0545	1.4385		1	1.0648	1.0588	1.0841	50
Internal time		85	89	93	93		105	109	109	117	51
Bare		2084 \oplus 2221	2218 \oplus 2353	2375 \otimes 2491			2759 \oplus 2885	2884 \otimes 3019		3019 \otimes 3294	52
Type		m^+	eyeSen	eyeVissn	eyeVissn		footSen	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	53
Data		$2^4 + 1$	96		54						
ID			2434	2550	2644			3083	3161	3355	55
Conscious level			1	1.5176	1.5012			1	1.4185	1.1079	56
Internal time			89	93	97			109	113	117	57
Bare			2220 \oplus 2355	2354 \oplus 2491	2491 \otimes 2625			2885 \oplus 3020	3019 \otimes 3158	3019 \oplus 3294	58
Type			footSen	eyeVissn	eyeVissn			footSen	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	59
Data			96		60						
ID			2435	2551	2682			3084	3218	3369	61
Conscious level			1	1	1.5249			1	1	1	62
Internal time			89	93	97			109	113	117	63
Bare			2221 \oplus 2356	2355 \oplus 2492	2362 \oplus 2625			2886 \oplus 3021	3018 \oplus 3157	3157 \oplus 3293	64
Type			m^+	footSen	eyeVissn			m^+	eyeSen	eyeSen	65
Data			$2^8 + 1$	192				$2^{19} + 2^{12}$	24	48	66

Continued: Feedback output at Environment instance ENV_1 , $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\tau = 20 : 29$

τ	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	#
ID					2699				3219	3370	67
Conscious level					1.2864				1.0802	1.1616	68
Internal time					97				113	117	69
Bare					2491 \oplus 2625				3019 \oplus 3158	3158 \oplus 3294	70
Type					eyeVissn				eyeVissn	eyeVissn	71
Data						72					
ID									3221		73
Conscious level									1		74
Internal time									113		75
Bare									3021 \oplus 3160		76
Type									m^+		77
Data									$2^{19} +$ 2^{18}		78

there is a SIETBO \hat{O}_8^S at $\tau = 1$ where

$$\langle \hat{O}_8^S \rangle_\beta = [\text{“eyeVissn”, } I_8] = \langle \hat{O}_8 \rangle_\beta; \quad (\text{V.7})$$

by Rule 1, I_8 is the image at ENV_1 location $x = 1$ and shown in Table III; by Rule 3, $\hat{O}_8 \in \overline{FBK}(s - 2)$; and $s = 2\Delta$. Next, consider the object \hat{O}_{19} listed at (43:48, 2, VI) which implies, by Rule 6, that there is a \hat{O} SIETBO \hat{O}_{19}^S at $\tau = 2$ where

$$\langle \hat{O}_{19}^S \rangle_\beta = [\text{“eyeVissn”, } I_{19}] = \langle \hat{O}_{19} \rangle_\beta \in \langle \overline{SEN}(s + 1) \rangle_\beta; \quad (\text{V.8})$$

by Rule 1, I_{19} is the image at ENV_1 location $x = 2$ and displayed in Table III. Based on their form the data/images I_8 and I_{19} are different. Further, by executing $I_8 \otimes I_{19} \hat{=} I_{23}$ through Equation III.20 it can be proven that $I_{23} \neq \mathbb{1}$. Therefore, by Theorems E.4 and E.6,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{O}_{23} \rangle_\beta &= \langle \hat{O}_8 \rangle_\beta \otimes \langle \hat{O}_{19}^S \rangle_\beta \overset{\approx}{\approx} \langle \overline{XFM}(s + 1) \rangle_\beta \\ &= [\text{“eyeVissn”, } I_8 \otimes I_{19}] \overset{\approx}{\approx} \langle \overline{INT}(s + 2) \rangle_\beta. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{V.9})$$

The terms $\overset{\approx}{\approx}$ and $\overset{\approx}{\approx}$ express uncertainty, as mentioned in Section III-J. However, $\langle \hat{O}_{23} \rangle_\beta$ is indeed an element of $\langle \overline{XFM}(s + 1) \rangle_\beta$ and $\langle \overline{INT}(s + 2) \rangle_\beta$, although the objects in these bare states are not presented in this paper for brevity. Now, by brute force pixel-by-pixel comparison, the images I_{23} and I_{19} can be shown to be identical, such that, using Equations V.8 and V.9 obtains

$$\langle \hat{O}_{23} \rangle_\beta = \langle \hat{O}_{19} \rangle_\beta. \quad (\text{V.10})$$

Thus, applying the \hat{O} $\langle \hat{O}_{19}^S \rangle_\beta \in \langle \overline{SEN}(s + 1) \rangle_\beta$ and $\langle \hat{O}_{23} \rangle_\beta \in \langle \overline{INT}(s + 2) \rangle_\beta$ to Theorem E.15, the latter bare object is absorbed to the former in, and thus vanishes after, Selector

at internal time $s + 2$. Consequently, the object with ID = 23 is absent in $\overline{FBK}(s + 2)$ and Table VI which only displays Feedback elements.

Consider next the object \hat{O}_{40} presented at (43:48, 3, VI) which implies, by Rule 6, that there is a SIETBO \hat{O}_{40}^S at $\tau = 3$ where

$$\langle \hat{O}_{40}^S \rangle_\beta = [\text{“eyeVissn”, } I_{40}] = \langle \hat{O}_{40} \rangle_\beta; \quad (\text{V.11})$$

and, by Rule 1, I_{40} is the image at ENV_1 location $x = 3$ and shown in Table III. Also consider the object \hat{O}_{45} presented at (55:60, 3, VI) which indicates: it to be consciously perceived by $3.I^M$; by Rule 3, found in $\overline{FBK}(3\Delta + 2)$; and, by Rule 5,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{O}_{45} \rangle_\beta &= \langle \hat{O}_{19} \rangle_\beta \otimes \langle \hat{O}_{40} \rangle_\beta \in \langle \overline{XFM}(3\Delta + 1) \rangle_\beta \\ &= [\text{“eyeVissn”, } I_{19} \otimes I_{40}]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{V.12})$$

Now, applying Equations V.7 to V.12 yields

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{O}_{45} \rangle_\beta &= \langle \hat{O}_8 \rangle_\beta \otimes \langle \hat{O}_{19} \rangle_\beta \otimes \langle \hat{O}_{40} \rangle_\beta \in \langle \overline{XFM}(3\Delta + 1) \rangle_\beta \\ &= \langle \hat{O}_8^S \rangle_\beta \otimes \langle \hat{O}_{19}^S \rangle_\beta \otimes \langle \hat{O}_{40}^S \rangle_\beta \\ &= [\text{“eyeVissn”, } I_8 \otimes I_{19} \otimes I_{40}] \end{aligned}$$

which is the generalization of the BCSIETBOs $\langle \hat{O}_8^S \rangle_\beta$, $\langle \hat{O}_{19}^S \rangle_\beta$ and $\langle \hat{O}_{40}^S \rangle_\beta$. Knowing \hat{O}_{45} to be consciously perceived by $3.I^M$ and found in $\overline{FBK}(3\Delta + 2)$, therefore it is a $3.I^M$ output. Thus, $3.I^M$ is capable of generalizing the BCSIETBOs. The presented analytical approach to justify the generalization can also be used to justify the generalization in Cases 6 to 9.

3) *Other settings:* The last subsection completes the justification of the generalization in all Table XII cases, however only for BCSIETBOs. The authentic generalization of the operation and non-“EyeVissn” sensory type bare basic objects

TABLE IX: Feedback output at Environment instance ENV_1 , $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\tau = 30 : 39$

τ	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	#
ID	3435	3569	3702	3828	3965	4105	4243	4384	4520	4659	37
Conscious level	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	38
Internal time	121	125	129	133	137	141	145	149	153	157	39
Bare											40
Type	m^+	m^+	m^-	m^-	m^-	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^-	41
Data	1	2^8	2^{12}	2^{11}	2^{10}	2^{13}	2^{15}	2^{14}	2^{17}	2^2	42
ID	3433	3567	3700	3826	3963	4103	4241	4382	4518	4657	43
Conscious level	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	44
Internal time	121	125	129	133	137	141	145	149	153	157	45
Bare											46
Type	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	47
Data		48									
ID	3500	3624	3758	3700	3829	4209	4103	4305	4603	4715	49
Conscious level	1.0491	1	1	1.3172	1.4366	1	1.057	1.4304	1	1	50
Internal time	121	125	129	129	133	141	141	145	153	157	51
Bare	3294 \oplus 3433	3432 \oplus 3566	3568 \oplus 3701		3700 \otimes 3826	3962 \oplus 4102		4103 \oplus 4241	4381 \oplus 4517	4517 \oplus 4656	52
Type	eyeVissn	eyeSen	footSen	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeSen	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeSen	eyeSen	53
Data		96	192	54							
ID	3502	3626		3829	3966		4244	4385			55
Conscious level	1	1		1.4906	1.4391		1.3863	1.3971			56
Internal time	121	125		133	137		145	149			57
Bare	3296 \oplus 3435	3434 \oplus 3568		3700 \otimes 3826	3700 \otimes 3963		4103 \otimes 4241	4103 \otimes 4382			58
Type	m^+	footSen		eyeVissn	eyeVissn		eyeVissn	eyeVissn			59
Data	$2^{17} + 1$	192					60				
ID				3887	3985		4305	4397			61
Conscious level				1	1.3412		1.1683	1.4189			62
Internal time				133	137		145	149			63
Bare				3699 \oplus 3825	3826 \otimes 3963		4103 \oplus 4241	4241 \otimes 4382			64
Type				eyeSen	eyeVissn		eyeVissn	eyeVissn			65
Data				3				66			

Continued: Feedback output at Environment instance ENV_1 , $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\tau = 30 : 39$

τ	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	#
ID				3888	3986		4306	4398			67
Conscious level				1.1102	1.4072		1	1.32			68
Internal time				133	137		145	149			69
Bare				3700 \oplus 3826	3829 \otimes 3963		4104 \oplus 4242	4244 \otimes 4382			70
Type				eyeVissn	eyeVissn		footSen	eyeVissn			71
Data							72				
ID				3889	4045			4442			73
Conscious level				1	1.3707			1.2234			74
Internal time				133	137			149			75
Bare				3701 \oplus 3827	3826 \oplus 3963			4103 \oplus 4382			76
Type				footSen	eyeVissn			eyeVissn			77
Data				3				78			

is absent in Tables VI to XI due to the data of the Transformer inputs and not to the generalizing ability of $3.I^M$, as proven in Theorems E.18 and E.19.

Tables 4 to 9 in <https://whizkod.com/ThreeM/Outputs.html> present output objects of $3.I^M$ endowed with $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$. They imply that $3.I^M$ outputs the generalization of every sequence of related BCSIETBOs as it interacts with environment ENV_2 and ENV_3 (illustrated in Tables IV and V, respectively) just as it did with environment ENV_1 , as described above. Thus, in every Environment instance with $3.I^M$ under the parameter settings, $3.I^M$ is 100% successful in generalizing every sequence of related BCSIETBOs.

Tables 10 to 18 in <https://whizkod.com/ThreeM/Outputs.html> list the output objects of $3.I^M$ that has $MXR = .25$. They prove $3.I^M$ to fail to generalize, when interacting with environment ENV_1 , each of the three series of related BCSIETBOs that end at $\tau = 9, 29$ and 37 and have data/image derived from columns 1, 5 and 4 of Table II, respectively. Further, $3.I^M$ fail to generalize, when interacting with environment ENV_2 and ENV_3 , each of the two series of related BCSIETBOs that end at $\tau = 35$ and 25 , and have data/image derived from columns 9 and 3 of Table II, respectively. Considering that there are 11 series of related SIETBOs triggered at every Environment instance, then the generalization ability of $3.I^M$ at $MXR = .25$ succeeds 85% on average over all the Environment instances. All the generalizations presented support Dynamics F.1 which analytically justifies the ability.

D. Join

As articulated below, $3.I^M$ is capable of joining (executing Equation III.18) series of BCSIETBOs triggered by environment ENV_1 . Table XIII illustrates the outcome of these joins and has similar format to Table XII, except on its column headed with \vec{J}_{\oplus} that stands for the join (through Equation III.14) of the images to the left of this column at its given row. Each of its Cases 1 to 4 has related Sensors-perceived icons. On the contrary, each of its Cases 5 to 7 has unrelated icons (i.e., not derived from the same column in Table II), such that for these cases, the mark “x” is indicated under its column labelled “Col”. Case 7 has Sensors-perceived icons that are not consecutively perceived by $3.I^M$, unlike the rest of the cases in Table XIII. There are numerous cases — not found in Table XIII but expressed in Tables VI to XI — that pertain to $3.I^M$ joining series of BCSIETBOs not explored here for brevity. However, they and all the cases in Table XIII have joins which can be justified through the methodology analogous to the justification of the generalization in the Table XII cases presented in Section V-C.

1) *Not derived from SIETBOs:* Unlike the joins dealt thus far, there are $3.I^M$ outputted joins not derived from SIETBOs. One of them is the join \hat{O}_{1945} presented at (73:78, 18, VII) that, by following the justification analogous to that in Section V-C1, can be shown to have a bare component $\langle \hat{O}_{1945} \rangle_{\beta} = \prod_{j \in ID_S}^{[\oplus]} \langle \hat{O}_j \rangle_{\beta}$ where the ordered set $ID_S = \{984, 1121, 1257, 1392, 1533, 1678, 1819\}$. The basic object $\hat{O}_j, j \in ID_S$, is presented at (37:42, τ_j , VII) which implies, by Rule 6, that

TABLE X: Feedback output at Environment instance ENV_1 , $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\tau = 40 : 49$

τ	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	#
ID	4789	4925	5060	5198	5334	5472	5607	5741	5874	6006	37
Conscious level	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	38
Internal time	161	165	169	173	177	181	185	189	193	197	39
Bare											40
Type	m^+	m^-	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^+	41
Data	2^{19}	2^3	2^{18}	2^{23}	2^{20}	2^{21}	2	2^{10}	2^3	2^{11}	42
ID	4787	4923	5058	5196	5332	5470	5605	5739	5872	6004	43
Conscious level	1	1	1	1	1.5	1	1	1	1	1	44
Internal time	161	165	169	173	177	181	185	189	193	197	45
Bare											46
Type	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	47
Data		48									
ID		4984		5260	5393	5332	5663	5742	5928	6063	49
Conscious level		1		1	1	1.3242	1.2853	1.1015	1	1	50
Internal time		165		173	177	177	185	189	193	197	51
Bare		4786 \oplus 4922		5057 \oplus 5195	5195 \oplus 5331		5332 \oplus 5605	5605 \otimes 5739	5738 \oplus 5871	5873 \oplus 6005	52
Type		eyeSen		eyeSen	eyeSen	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeSen	footSen	53
Data		3		12	24		129	3	54		
ID				5263	5394	5475	5664	5799	5929	6064	55
Conscious level				1	1.4285	1.3945	1	1	1.0102	1	56
Internal time				173	177	181	185	189	193	197	57
Bare				5060 \oplus 5198	5196 \oplus 5332	5332 \otimes 5470	5394 \oplus 5605	5607 \oplus 5741	5739 \oplus 5872	5874 \oplus 6006	58
Type				m^+	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	m^+	eyeVissn	m^+	59
Data				$2^{23} + 2^{18}$		$2^{11} + 2^3$	60				
ID					5396	5484	5670		5931		61
Conscious level					1	1.4135	1		1		62
Internal time					177	181	185		193		63
Bare					5198 \oplus 5334	5394 \otimes 5470	5469 \oplus 5604		5741 \oplus 5874		64
Type					m^+	eyeVissn	eyeSen		m^+		65
Data					$2^{23} + 2^{20}$		96		$2^{10} + 2^3$		66

Continued: Feedback output at Environment instance ENV_1 , $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\tau = 40 : 49$

τ	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	#
ID						5532	5671				67
Conscious level						1.3994	1.094				68
Internal time						181	185				69
Bare						5332 \oplus 5470	5470 \oplus 5605				70
Type						eyeVissn	eyeVissn				71
Data										72	
ID						5544	5690				73
Conscious level						1.024	1.2095				74
Internal time						181	185				75
Bare						5394 \oplus 5470	5532 \oplus 5605				76
Type						eyeVissn	eyeVissn				77
Data										78	

there is a long series of Sensors-issued bare objects $\langle \widehat{O}_j^S \rangle_{\beta S}$ at τ, s equal to $11 + \mathcal{O}(j \in IDs)$. Using Equations III.11 and III.15, Theorems B.4 and B.5, and the tabular presentation of \widehat{O}_j , one obtains $\langle \widehat{O}_{1945} \rangle_{\beta} = [m^-, d_{1945}]$ where $d_{1945} = 2^6 \oplus 2^7 \oplus 2^8 \oplus 2 \oplus 2^8 \oplus 2 \oplus 2^8 = 2^8 + 2^7 + 2^6 + 2$ that justifies the data of \widehat{O}_{1945} listed at (78, 18, VII).

2) *Mixed operator action:* The objects investigated thus far are produced by the sole action of either the \otimes or the \oplus operator in Transformer. However, although few, there are $3.I^M$ outputted objects, presented in Tables VI to XI, produced by the mixed action of the \otimes and \oplus operators in Transformer. One of them is the object \widehat{O}_{48} presented at (61:66, 3, VI) that, by employing analogous Section V-C1 justification approach, can be shown to have the bare component $\langle \widehat{O}_{48} \rangle_{\beta} = (\langle \widehat{O}_8 \rangle_{\beta} \oplus \langle \widehat{O}_{19} \rangle_{\beta}) \otimes \langle \widehat{O}_{40} \rangle_{\beta}$. The basic objects \widehat{O}_8 , \widehat{O}_{19} and \widehat{O}_{40} are presented at (43:48, 1, VI), (43:48, 2, VI) and (43:48, 3, VI) that imply, by Rule 6, that there is a series of Sensors-issued basic objects \widehat{O}_8^S , \widehat{O}_{19}^S and \widehat{O}_{40}^S at $\tau = 1$ to 3, respectively.

3) *Object number dynamics:* Let us now investigate the dynamics on the number of $3.I^M$ -outputted objects formed in Transformer solely by either the \otimes or the \oplus operator. Consider the series of $3.I^M$ -outputted basic objects, each presented at (43:48, τ , IX), $35 \leq \tau \leq 37$. These presentations imply that the basic objects have data/image from column 4 of Table II, i.e., they are related. Further, by Rule 6, they imply the existence of SIETBOs which, by applying analogous Section V-C1 justification methodology, can be shown to be processed by Transformer using the \otimes operator

only to form the “eyeVissn”-type bare basic objects $\langle \widehat{O}_{4244} \rangle_{\beta}$, $\langle \widehat{O}_{4385} \rangle_{\beta}$, $\langle \widehat{O}_{4397} \rangle_{\beta}$ and $\langle \widehat{O}_{4398} \rangle_{\beta}$ listed at (55:60, 36, IX), (55:60, 37, IX), (61:66, 37, IX) and (67:72, 37, IX), respectively. The latter listings imply that $3.I^M$ outputted one and three of the \otimes -formed basic objects, corresponding to them, at $\tau = 36$ and 37, respectively. However, at $\tau = 35$ and 38, $3.I^M$ outputs no \otimes -formed “eyeVissn”-type basic objects based on (37:54, 35, IX) and (43:54, 38, IX). A similar scenario also prevails at $\tau = 15$ to 19 as manifested in (49:72, 15, VII), (49:78, 16, VII), (49:72, 17, VII), (49:78, 18, VII) and (49:60, 19, VII). On the other hand, some of the latter table entries show $3.I^M$ outputting several \oplus -formed “eyeVissn”-type basic objects triggered by SIETBOs presented at (43:48, τ , VII), $15 \leq \tau \leq 19$, and have unrelated data/image. This numerical dominance dynamics is generalized as: Among the “eyeVissn”-type basic objects presented in Tables VI to XI, formed by Transformer, and outputted by $3.I^M$, the solely \otimes -formed dominates in number over the solely \oplus -formed at the end of the series of more than two related/unrelated SIETBOs that constitute them.

4) *Other settings:* The investigations in Section V-D thus far are only on $3.I^M$, at $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$, interacting with environment ENV_1 . On the $3.I^M$ interaction with environments ENV_2 and ENV_3 , at the same parameter settings, tables in <https://whizkod.com/ThreeM/Outputs.html> can be used to justify $3.I^M$: (a) to produce the join of some series of Sensors-issued bare basic objects with “eyeVissn” type and also with the other types; (b) to output objects created through the action of the \otimes and/or \oplus operators in Transformer; (c) and to maintain

TABLE XI: Feedback output at Environment instance ENV_1 , $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\tau = 50 : 59$

τ	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	#
ID	6137	6269	6400	6537	6675	6810	6947	7073	7212	7348	37
Conscious level	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	38
Internal time	201	205	209	213	217	221	225	229	233	237	39
Bare											40
Type	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^+	m^-	m^-	m^-	m^+	41
Data	2^2	2^9	2^3	2^2	2	2^8	2^7	2^6	2^8	1	42
ID	6135	6267	6398	6535	6673	6808	6945	7071	7210	7346	43
Conscious level	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	44
Internal time	201	205	209	213	217	221	225	229	233	237	45
Bare											46
Type	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	47
Data		48									
ID	6193	6275		6398	6398	6894		6945	6945	7407	49
Conscious level	1	1.0616		1.4467	1.5036	1		1.4514	1.5013	1.065	50
Internal time	201	205		209	209	221		225	225	237	51
Bare	6003 \oplus 6134	6135 \otimes 6267				6672 \oplus 6807				6945 \oplus 7346	52
Type	eyeSen	eyeVissn		eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeSen		eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeVissn	53
Data	6		54								
ID	6194			6544	6676	6897		7074	7074	7436	55
Conscious level	1.0538			1.5134	1.5059	1		1.4851	1.5013	1	56
Internal time	201			213	217	221		229	229	237	57
Bare	6004 \oplus 6135			6398 \otimes 6535	6398 \otimes 6673	6675 \oplus 6810		6945 \otimes 7071	6945 \otimes 7071	7209 \oplus 7345	58
Type	eyeVissn			eyeVissn	eyeVissn	m^+		eyeVissn	eyeVissn	eyeSen	59
Data		12	60								
ID				6602	6697			7133	7213	7438	61
Conscious level				1.3586	1.499			1.3375	1.5072	1	62
Internal time				213	217			229	233	237	63
Bare				6398 \oplus 6535	6544 \otimes 6673			6945 \oplus 7071	6945 \otimes 7210	7211 \oplus 7347	64
Type				eyeVissn	eyeVissn			eyeVissn	eyeVissn	footSen	65
Data					12	66					

Continued: Feedback output at Environment instance ENV_1 , $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\tau = 50 : 59$

τ	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	#
ID				6624	6730			7135	7240		67
Conscious level				1.3492	1.527			1	1.5036		68
Internal time				213	217			229	233		69
Bare				6464 \oplus 6535	6398 \oplus 6673			6947 \oplus 7073	7074 \otimes 7210		70
Type				eyeVissn	eyeVissn			m^-	eyeVissn		71
Data						72					
ID				6650				7176			73
Conscious level				1.3193				1.0859			74
Internal time				213				229			75
Bare				6508 \oplus 6535				7022 \oplus 7071			76
Type				eyeVissn				eyeVissn			77
Data							78				

the aforementioned number dominance dynamics. Based on the same tables, this enumeration can also be proven true for $3.I^M$, at $MXR = .25$, interacting with any of the three Environment instances.

E. Consciousness Level Dynamics

Let us now investigate the consciousness level dynamics of the objects moving inside the $3.I^M$ architecture under $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ and interacting with environment ENV_1 . Some $3.I^M$ outputs of this interaction are the objects in the set $\bar{O} = \{\bar{O}_i \mid i \in NDX\}$ with \bar{O}_i presented at (43:48, τ_i , VI), and labelled in accord with Rule 2 using the ordered set $NDX = \{1255, 1390, 1531, 1676, 1817\}$ where $\tau_i = 13 + \emptyset (i \in NDX)$. Thus, by Rule 6, there are SIETBOs at τ_i in the set $\bar{S} = \{\bar{O}_i^S \mid i \in NDX\}$ where

$$\langle \bar{O}_i^S \rangle_\beta = [\text{“eyeVissn”}, I_i] = \langle \bar{O}_i \rangle_\beta, \quad i \in NDX; \quad (\text{V.13})$$

and, by Rule 1, the image I_i is found at the ENV_1 location $x_i = \tau_i$ in Table III. Further, the tabular presentations at (43:48, τ_i , VI), $\forall i \in NDX$, manifest that $\langle \bar{O}_{1255} \rangle_\beta = \langle \bar{O}_{1531} \rangle_\beta = \langle \bar{O}_{1817} \rangle_\beta$ and $\langle \bar{O}_{1390} \rangle_\beta = \langle \bar{O}_{1676} \rangle_\beta$.

The bare objects $\langle \bar{O}_{1255} \rangle_\beta$ and $\langle \bar{O}_{1390} \rangle_\beta$ are used by Transformer in order for Feedback to output the basic object \bar{O}_{1484} tabulated at (55:60, 15, VI). The latter expresses: \bar{O}_{1484} to have consciousness level of 0.16456 (i.e., \bar{O}_{1484} is subconsciously perceived by $3.I^M$); by Rule 3, $\bar{O}_{1484} \in \overline{FBK}(15\Delta + 2)$; and by

Rule 5 and Equations III.15 and V.13

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \bar{O}_{1484} \rangle_\beta &= \langle \bar{O}_{1255} \rangle_\beta \oplus \langle \bar{O}_{1390} \rangle_\beta \\ &= \langle \bar{O}_{1255}^S \rangle_\beta \oplus \langle \bar{O}_{1390}^S \rangle_\beta \\ &= [\text{“eyeVissn”}, I_{1255} \oplus I_{1390}]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{V.14})$$

The object \bar{O}_{1599} is similar to the object \bar{O}_{1484} (i.e., $\langle \bar{O}_{1484} \rangle_\beta = \langle \bar{O}_{1599} \rangle_\beta$) based on its presentation at (55:60, 16, VI) which indicates it to have consciousness level of 1.0293. Further, by Rule 3, $\bar{O}_{1599} \in \overline{FBK}(16\Delta + 2)$; and by Rule 5 and Equation V.13

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \bar{O}_{1599} \rangle_\beta &= \langle \bar{O}_{1390} \rangle_\beta \oplus \langle \bar{O}_{1531} \rangle_\beta \\ &= \langle \bar{O}_{1390}^S \rangle_\beta \oplus \langle \bar{O}_{1531}^S \rangle_\beta. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{V.15})$$

As mentioned, $\langle \bar{O}_{1484} \rangle_\beta = \langle \bar{O}_{1599} \rangle_\beta \in \langle \overline{FBK}(16\Delta + 2) \rangle_\beta$, i.e., $\langle \bar{O}_{1484} \rangle_\beta$ moves from being in $\langle \overline{FBK}(15\Delta + 2) \rangle_\beta$ to $\langle \overline{FBK}(16\Delta + 2) \rangle_\beta$ and changing its consciousness level attribute from 0.16456 to 1.0293 in the process.

The object \bar{O}_{1754} is similar to the object \bar{O}_{1484} based on its presentation at (49:54, 17, VI) which shows it to have consciousness level of 0.41226. By Rule 3, $\bar{O}_{1754} \in \overline{FBK}(17\Delta + 2)$; and by Rule 5 and Equation V.13

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \bar{O}_{1754} \rangle_\beta &= \langle \bar{O}_{1531} \rangle_\beta \oplus \langle \bar{O}_{1676} \rangle_\beta \\ &= \langle \bar{O}_{1531}^S \rangle_\beta \oplus \langle \bar{O}_{1676}^S \rangle_\beta. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{V.16})$$

The similarity implies that $\langle \bar{O}_{1754} \rangle_\beta = \langle \bar{O}_{1484} \rangle_\beta \in \langle \overline{FBK}(17\Delta + 2) \rangle_\beta$, i.e., $\langle \bar{O}_{1484} \rangle_\beta$ arrives at $\langle \overline{FBK}(17\Delta + 2) \rangle_\beta$.

The object \bar{O}_{1887} is also similar to the object \bar{O}_{1484} based on its presentation at (49:54, 18, VI) which shows it to have consciousness level of 1.202. By Rule 3, $\bar{O}_{1887} \in \overline{FBK}(18\Delta + 2)$

TABLE XII: Generalization of images at ENV_1 and $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$

Case #	$\langle\langle \vec{A} \rangle\rangle_\beta$	τ_1	$\langle\langle \vec{B} \rangle\rangle_\beta$	τ_2	$\langle\langle \vec{C} \rangle\rangle_\beta$	τ_3	$\langle\langle \vec{C}_\otimes \rangle\rangle_\beta$	Col	Location
1		7		8		9		1	(61 : 66, 9, VI)
2		12		13		14		8	(61 : 66, 14, VII)
3		32		33		34		9	(67 : 72, 34, IX)
4		35		36		37		4	(67 : 72, 37, IX)
5		1		2		3		7	(55 : 60, 3, VI)
6		22		23		24		3	(55 : 60, 24, VIII)
7		43		44		45		6	(55 : 60, 45, X)
8		27		28		29		5	(49 : 54, 29, VIII)
9		4		5		6		2	(67 : 72, 6, VI)

2); and by Rule 5 and Equation V.13

$$\begin{aligned} \langle\dot{O}_{1887}\rangle_\beta &= \langle\dot{O}_{1817}\rangle_\beta \oplus \langle\dot{O}_{1676}\rangle_\beta \\ &= \langle\dot{O}_{1817}^S\rangle_\beta \oplus \langle\dot{O}_{1676}^S\rangle_\beta. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{V.17})$$

The similarity implies that $\langle\dot{O}_{1887}\rangle_\beta = \langle\dot{O}_{1484}\rangle_\beta \in \langle\widetilde{FBK}(18\Delta + 2)\rangle_\beta$, i.e., $\langle\dot{O}_{1484}\rangle_\beta$ arrives at $\langle\widetilde{FBK}(18\Delta + 2)\rangle_\beta$.

In summary, the bare object $\langle\dot{O}_{1484}\rangle_\beta$ goes from being subconsciously, to consciously, back to subconsciously, and finally to consciously perceived by $3.I^M$ at $\tau = 15$ to 18 with consciousness level of 0.16456, 1.0293, 0.41226 and 1.202, respectively. This consciousness level dynamics is influenced by the $3.I^M$ -perceived SIETBOs (e.g., $\dot{O}_i^S, i \in NDX$, employed in Equations V.13 to V.17), and supports Dynamics E.1 which analytical justifies it.

1) *Formation of a complex object*: Let us now explore a consciousness level dynamics where an object subconsciously perceived by $3.I^M$ is transformed over a range of external time indices to become a *complex object* (created through a series of binary operator actions in Transformer) consciously perceived by $3.I^M$. First, consider the objects in the set $\bar{O} = \{\dot{O}_i \mid i \in LBL\}$ with \dot{O}_i presented at (37:42, τ_i , VI), and labelled in accord with Rule 3 using the ordered set $LBL = \{1121, 1257, 1392, 1533\}$ where $\tau_i = 12 + \mathcal{O}(i \in LBL)$. Thus, by Rule 6, there are Sensors-issued objects, each at τ_i ,

in the set $\bar{S} = \{\dot{O}_i^S \mid i \in LBL\}$ where

$$\langle\dot{O}_i^S\rangle_\beta = [m^-, \langle\dot{O}_i\rangle_\beta] = \langle\dot{O}_i\rangle_\beta, \quad i \in LBL. \quad (\text{V.18})$$

The bare objects $\langle\dot{O}_{1121}\rangle_\beta$ and $\langle\dot{O}_{1257}\rangle_\beta$ are used by Transformer at $\tau = 14$ in order for Feedback to output the object \dot{O}_{1343} listed at (73:78, 14, VI) which expresses \dot{O}_{1343} to have consciousness level of 0.38951 (i.e., \dot{O}_{1343} is subconsciously perceived by $3.I^M$). By Rule 3, $\dot{O}_{1343} \in \widetilde{FBK}(14\Delta + 2)$; and by Rule 5 and Equations III.11, III.15 and V.18

$$\begin{aligned} \langle\dot{O}_{1343}\rangle_\beta &= \langle\dot{O}_{1121}\rangle_\beta \oplus \langle\dot{O}_{1257}\rangle_\beta \\ &= \langle\dot{O}_{1121}^S\rangle_\beta \oplus \langle\dot{O}_{1257}^S\rangle_\beta \\ &= [m^-, 2^8 + 2^7]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{V.19})$$

The bare object $\langle\dot{O}_{1343}\rangle_\beta$ is in turn used by Transformer at $\tau = 15$, together with $\langle\dot{O}_{1392}\rangle_\beta$, for Feedback to output the object \dot{O}_{1513} listed at (67:72, 15, VI) which indicates \dot{O}_{1513} to have consciousness level of 0.51649. By Rule 3, $\dot{O}_{1513} \in \widetilde{FBK}(15\Delta + 2)$; and by Rule 5 and Equations III.11, III.15 and V.18

$$\begin{aligned} \langle\dot{O}_{1513}\rangle_\beta &= \langle\dot{O}_{1343}\rangle_\beta \oplus \langle\dot{O}_{1392}\rangle_\beta \\ &= \langle\dot{O}_{1343}^S\rangle_\beta \oplus \langle\dot{O}_{1392}^S\rangle_\beta \\ &= [m^-, 2^8 + 2^7 + 2]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{V.20})$$

TABLE XIII: Join of images at ENV_1 and $MXR = 5 \times 10^{-6}$

Case #	$\langle\langle \vec{A} \rangle\rangle_{\beta} \rangle_{\delta}$	τ_1	$\langle\langle \vec{B} \rangle\rangle_{\beta} \rangle_{\delta}$	τ_2	$\langle\langle \vec{C} \rangle\rangle_{\beta} \rangle_{\delta}$	τ_3	$\langle\langle \vec{D} \rangle\rangle_{\beta} \rangle_{\delta}$	τ_4	$\langle\langle \vec{E} \rangle\rangle_{\beta} \rangle_{\delta}$	τ_5	$\langle\langle \vec{J} \rangle\rangle_{\beta} \rangle_{\delta}$	Col	Location
1		1	(67 : 72, 9, VI)										
2		3	(61 : 66, 24, VIII)										
3		4	(73 : 78, 37, IX)										
4		6	(73 : 78, 45, X)										
5		x	(73 : 78, 53, XI)										
6		x	(73 : 78, 57, XI)										
7		x	(61 : 66, 18, VII)										

The bare object $\langle \hat{O}_{1513} \rangle_\beta$ is in turn used by Transformer at $\tau = 16$, together with $\langle \hat{O}_{1533} \rangle_\beta$, for Feedback to output the object \hat{O}_{1662} presented at (73:78, 16, VI) which indicates \hat{O}_{1662} to have consciousness level of 1.10149. By Rule 3, $\hat{O}_{1662} \in \overline{FBK}(16\Delta + 2)$; and by Rule 5 and Equations III.11, III.15 and V.18

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{O}_{1662} \rangle_\beta &= \langle \hat{O}_{1513} \rangle_\beta \oplus \langle \hat{O}_{1533} \rangle_\beta \\ &= \langle \hat{O}_{1513}^S \rangle_\beta \oplus \langle \hat{O}_{1533}^S \rangle_\beta \\ &= [m^-, 2^8 + 2^7 + 2]. \end{aligned} \quad (V.21)$$

In summary, the subconscious level-attributed object \hat{O}_{1343} is manipulated over the range of external time indices, 13 to 16, through the Transformer \oplus operator for $3.I^M$ to eventually output \hat{O}_{1662} (i.e., consciously perceived by $3.I^M$). This consciousness level dynamics is influenced by the Sensors-issued basic objects as depicted in Equations V.19 to V.21; and, as mentioned in Section III-A, corresponds to the dynamics of the occurrence probability of stochastic neural network activation state.

F. Limitations

$3.I^M$ is the first version of 3^M and, being as such, mostly intended to introduce in a simple manner the 3^M foundational principles. This simplicity is made by restricting some $3.I^M$ characteristics that resulted to the following $3.I^M$ limitations: (a) For any given external time index τ , the Sensors-issued basic objects of type “eyeSen” and “footSen”, and the Contrector-issued basic objects of operation type have identical data, except at $\tau = 0$ and 1, that repeats every 8 external time index units, and have zero measure of similarity with the basic objects of the same type but outputted at $\tau \pm 1$, $\tau > 1$. (b) The Executioner-issued action type basic objects have external time index-invariant data. (c) The images below the topmost image in any given column in Table II are derived by adding black or white pixels to the topmost image. If after the addition they are shifted, rotated and/or scaled with respect to the topmost image $3.I^M$ may not be able to generalize the BCSJETBOs with data being the transformation outcomes. (d) There are only few Table XIII cases having joined images belonging to the same Table II column. (e) Some $3.I^M$ -outputted joins have meaningless data/image, e.g., the data of the object presented at (55:60, 29, VIII). (f) $3.I^M$ does not join Sensors-issued basic objects of different types.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, an overview of Developmental Psychology is provided as potentially relevant for modelling AGI. Also, the dynamical method is supported to be appropriate for the design of real time-transpiring AI agents [10] but criticized as unsuitable for modelling reasoning and abstract concepts [24] [25]. Some dynamical cognitive models are contrasted to the interpretable (facilitates humanly comprehensible internal processes), but expected to be less environmental change adaptive [47], algorithmic developmental AI architectures. From this contrast, the need for an interpretable developmental dynamical AI agent is identified. This need is addressed by proposing the novel AI agent $3.I^M$ modelled as a set of dynamical

difference equations containing Developmental Psychology-based and direct concept-representing mathematical operators. $3.I^M$ is the first implementation of the AI design principles, collectively referred to as 3^M , and made to interact with not purely random artificial environments.

The interactions prove the following paper contributions: (a) $3.I^M$ has the ability to generalize or fuse series of related information it extracted from its environment. (b) This ability mostly persists over various environment configurations and values of a stochastic $3.I^M$ parameter. (c) The information produced by one $3.I^M$ mathematical operator widely inhibits those of the other to become the $3.I^M$ output. (d) The $3.I^M$ interpretability facilitates the mathematical investigation and justification of its dynamics and characteristics.

In its future versions, 3^M will possess reinforcement and associative learning abilities by adding new Developmental Psychology-based mathematical operators to itself; simulate new types of sensations, especially fringe sensation [87] (e.g. sense of truth and beauty, and boredom); acquire general intelligence, which is the ultimate 3^M design goal; and not possess the limitations elaborated in Section V-F.

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APPENDIX

A. Parameters σ and ζ

The sigmoid parameters σ and ζ in Equation IV.50 are computed by first taking the substitution of

$$z = \exp(-\sigma) \quad (A.1)$$

to Equation IV.50 to obtain

$$SGM(x) = \zeta \frac{1 - z^x}{1 + z^x} = \zeta \tanh(\sigma x / 2).$$

Next, it is demanded that setting $x = THR$ yields $SGM(THR) = MXC$, i.e.,

$$MXC = \zeta \frac{1 - z^{THR}}{1 + z^{THR}}; \quad (A.2)$$

and that setting $x = LMT = THR/3.0$ obtains $SGM(x) = THR$, i.e.,

$$THR = \zeta \frac{1 - z^{LMT}}{1 + z^{LMT}}. \quad (A.3)$$

Dividing Equation A.2 by A.3 eliminates ζ to produce

$$\frac{MXC}{THR} = m' = \left(\frac{1 - z^{THR}}{1 + z^{THR}} \right) \left(\frac{1 + z^{LMT}}{1 - z^{LMT}} \right)$$

that simplifies to

$$z^{THR+LMT} + \alpha (z^{LMT} - z^{THR}) - 1 = 0 \quad (A.4)$$

where $\alpha = \frac{m'+1}{m'-1}$. Finally, the root of Equation A.4 is used to find σ and ζ via Equations A.1 and A.3, respectively.

B. Operator Algebra

Let us now investigate the algebraic properties of the \oplus and \otimes operators.

1) *Join*: We begin by exploring the theorems on space \mathbb{Z}_0^+ under the \oplus operator.

Theorem B.1: Under the \oplus operator, the space \mathbb{Z}_0^+ is closed and each of its elements is idempotent to itself. Further, the \oplus operator is commutative and associative over \mathbb{Z}_0^+ .

Proof Consider any two \mathbb{Z}_0^+ elements A, B expressed as in Equations III.12 and III.13, respectively. Thus, $e_n \stackrel{\Delta}{=} a_n \text{ OR } b_n$ takes boolean values $\forall 0 \leq n < NBT$. By using Equation III.11 one arrives at

$$A \oplus B = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n e_n \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Therefore, \mathbb{Z}_0^+ is closed under the \oplus operator.

Setting $A = B$ in Equation B.1 and using the properties of the boolean OR operator obtains $A \oplus A = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n (a_n \text{ OR } a_n) = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n a_n = A$. Thus, any element of \mathbb{Z}_0^+ is idempotent to itself under the \oplus operator.

Interchanging A and B in Equation B.1 yields $B \oplus A = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n (b_n \text{ OR } a_n) = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n (a_n \text{ OR } b_n) = A \oplus B$. Therefore, the \oplus operator is commutative over \mathbb{Z}_0^+ .

Consider another \mathbb{Z}_0^+ element $C = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n c_n$ and take $A \oplus (B \oplus C) = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n (a_n \text{ OR } (b_n \text{ OR } c_n))$. By the associativity of the boolean OR operator over boolean values, one obtains $A \oplus (B \oplus C) = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n ((a_n \text{ OR } b_n) \text{ OR } c_n) = (A \oplus B) \oplus C$. Therefore, the \oplus operator is associative over \mathbb{Z}_0^+ . ■

Lemma B.1: $ENT = \{1, 3\} \subset \mathbb{Z}_0^+$.

Proof Consider $A \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$ expressed as in Equation III.12. Using Equation III.1 shows that if $a_0 = \text{TRUE}$ and $a_n = \text{FALSE} \forall 0 < n < NBT$ then $A = 1 \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$. Further, if $a_0, a_1 = \text{TRUE}$ and $a_n = \text{FALSE} \forall 1 < n < NBT$ then $A = 3 \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$. Thus, $ENT \subset \mathbb{Z}_0^+$. ■

Lemma B.2: If $A, B \in ENT = \{1, 3\}$ then $A \oplus B \in ENT$.

Proof Lemma B.1 allows us to use the elements of ENT as operands of \oplus in Equation III.11. Now, let any two \mathbb{Z}_0^+ elements A, B be expressed as in Equations III.12 and III.13, respectively. Consequently, with the help of Equations III.2 and III.11:

- 1) $A = 1$ and $B = 1 \implies A \oplus B = 1 \in ENT$.
- 2) $A = 1$ and $B = 3 \implies A \oplus B = 2^0(\text{TRUE OR TRUE}) + 2^1(\text{FALSE OR TRUE}) = 3 \in ENT$.
- 3) $A = 3$ and $B = 1 \implies A \oplus B = 2^0(\text{TRUE OR TRUE}) + 2^1(\text{TRUE OR FALSE}) = 3 \in ENT$.
- 4) $A = 3$ and $B = 3 \implies A \oplus B = 2^0(\text{TRUE OR TRUE}) + 2^1(\text{TRUE OR TRUE}) = 3 \in ENT$.

Thus, in any of the cases, $A \oplus B \in ENT$. ■

Theorem B.2: Under the \oplus operator, the space \mathbb{M} is closed and each of its elements is idempotent to itself. Further, the \oplus operator is commutative and associative over \mathbb{M} .

Proof Consider any two matrices $M = [m_{r,c}], N = [n_{r,c}] \in \mathbb{M}$ where $m_{r,c}, n_{r,c} \in ENT, \forall 1 \leq r \leq NROW, 1 \leq c \leq NCOL$

as defined in Section III; and $ENT \subset \mathbb{Z}_0^+$ by Lemma B.1. It follows from Lemma B.2 that $m_{r,c} \oplus n_{r,c} \stackrel{\Delta}{=} o_{r,c} \in ENT$. Thus, by Equation III.14,

$$M \oplus N = [m_{r,c} \oplus n_{r,c}] = [o_{r,c}] \in \mathbb{M}. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Therefore, \mathbb{M} is closed under the \oplus operator.

Lemma B.1 implies that $m_{r,c} \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$, such that by Theorem B.1, $m_{r,c} \oplus m_{r,c} = m_{r,c}$. Now, setting $M = N$ in Equation B.2 obtains $M \oplus M = [m_{r,c} \oplus m_{r,c}] = [m_{r,c}] = M$. Thus, any element of \mathbb{M} is idempotent to itself under the \oplus operator.

By Lemma B.1, $n_{r,c} \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$, such that by Theorem B.1, $n_{r,c} \oplus m_{r,c} = m_{r,c} \oplus n_{r,c}$. Thus, $N \oplus M = [n_{r,c} \oplus m_{r,c}] = [m_{r,c} \oplus n_{r,c}] = M \oplus N$. Therefore, the \oplus operator is commutative over \mathbb{M} .

Let us now consider another matrix $O = [o_{r,c}] \in \mathbb{M}$. Again, by Lemma B.1, $o_{r,c} \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$, such that by Theorem B.1, $(m_{r,c} \oplus n_{r,c}) \oplus o_{r,c} = m_{r,c} \oplus (n_{r,c} \oplus o_{r,c})$. Let us then take $(M \oplus N) \oplus O = [(m_{r,c} \oplus n_{r,c}) \oplus o_{r,c}] = [m_{r,c} \oplus (n_{r,c} \oplus o_{r,c})] = M \oplus (N \oplus O)$. Therefore, the \oplus operator is associative over \mathbb{M} . ■

Lemma B.3: If $A, B \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ then $A \oplus B \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

Proof Let A, B be expressed as in Equations III.12 and III.13, respectively. Considering that $A, B \neq 0$ then there exists at least one $a_m = \text{TRUE}$ and $b_n = \text{TRUE}, \exists 0 \leq m, n < NBT$. Using Equations III.2 and III.11 obtains $A \oplus B = \sum_{i \neq n, m}^{NBT-1} 2^i (a_i \text{ OR } b_i) + 2^m (\text{TRUE OR } b_m) + 2^n (a_n \text{ OR TRUE}) = \sum_{i \neq n, m}^{NBT-1} 2^i (a_i \text{ OR } b_i) + 2^m + 2^n > 0$. It then follows from Theorem B.1 that $A \oplus B \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. ■

Lemma B.4: If $A, B \in \mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$ then $A \oplus B \neq 1$.

Proof Given that $A, B \neq 1$ then there are entries $A[r, c] = B[s, d] = 3, \exists 1 \leq r, s \leq NROW, 1 \leq c, d \leq NCOL$. Employing Equations III.11 and III.14 obtains $A \oplus B \stackrel{\Delta}{=} C$ where $C[r, c] = A[r, c] \oplus B[r, c] = 3 \oplus B[r, c] = 3$ and $C[s, d] = A[s, d] \oplus B[s, d] = A[s, d] \oplus 3 = 3$. Thus, $C = A \oplus B \neq 1$. ■

Theorem B.3: The join of any two $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects of the same type ψ is also a $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic object of the same type.

Proof Consider any $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects $\widehat{A} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta]$ and $\widehat{B} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta]$ of type ψ where $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta, \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Note that $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta, \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta > 0$, otherwise \widehat{A} and/or $\widehat{B} = \hat{\otimes}$ based on Definition 2. Now, employing Equation III.15 yields $\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{B} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \oplus \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta]$. It follows from Lemma B.3 that $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \oplus \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \stackrel{\Delta}{=} C \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Thus, $\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{B} = [\psi, C] \neq \hat{\otimes}$ is a bare basic object of type similar to those of \widehat{A} and \widehat{B} .

Next, consider the bare basic objects $\widehat{F} = [\rho, \langle \widehat{F} \rangle_\delta]$ and $\widehat{G} = [\rho, \langle \widehat{G} \rangle_\delta]$ of type ρ where $\langle \widehat{F} \rangle_\delta, \langle \widehat{G} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$ (otherwise, \widehat{A} and/or $\widehat{B} = \hat{\otimes}$ based on Definition 2). By Lemma B.4 $\langle \widehat{F} \rangle_\delta \oplus \langle \widehat{G} \rangle_\delta \stackrel{\Delta}{=} H \neq 1$ and by Theorem B.2, $H \in \mathbb{M}$. Using Equation III.15 yields, $\widehat{F} \oplus \widehat{G} = [\rho, H] \neq \hat{\otimes}$ that is a $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic object of type similar to those of \widehat{F} and \widehat{G} . ■

Theorem B.4: Any bare basic object is idempotent to itself under the \oplus operator.

Proof Suppose $\widehat{A} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta] \neq \widehat{\emptyset}$. Setting $\widehat{B} = \widehat{A}$ in Equation III.15 produces $\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{A} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \oplus \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta]$ where either $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \subset \mathbb{Z}_0^+$ or $\in \mathbb{M}_{\neq 1} \subset \mathbb{M}$. Considering that any element of \mathbb{Z}_0^+ or \mathbb{M} is proven in Theorem B.1 or B.2, respectively, to be idempotent to itself under the \oplus operator then $\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{A} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta] = \widehat{A}$.

Now, if $\widehat{A} = \widehat{\emptyset}$ then $\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{A} = \widehat{\emptyset}$, based on Equation III.17. Therefore, in any case, $\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{A} = \widehat{A}$. ■

Lemma B.5: The $\widehat{\emptyset}$ bare basic objects of the same type are commutative and associative under the \oplus operator.

Proof Consider any bare basic objects $\widehat{A} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta] \neq \widehat{\emptyset}$ and $\widehat{B} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta] \neq \widehat{\emptyset}$, of the same type ψ . Thus, by Equation III.15, $\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{B} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \oplus \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta]$. Considering their similarity in type and being $\widehat{\emptyset}$, if $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta$ is an element of \mathbb{Z}^+ or $\mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$ then $\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta$ is an element of \mathbb{Z}^+ or $\mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$, respectively, based on Definition 1. Thus, by the commutativity of the elements of \mathbb{Z}_0^+ or \mathbb{M} under the \oplus operator proven in Theorems B.1 or B.2, respectively, $\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{B} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \oplus \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta] = [\psi, \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \oplus \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta] = \widehat{B} \oplus \widehat{A}$. Therefore, $\widehat{\emptyset}$ bare basic objects of the same type are commutative under the \oplus operator.

Now, let $\widehat{C} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\delta] \neq \widehat{\emptyset}$ and form $\beta = \widehat{A} \oplus (\widehat{B} \oplus \widehat{C})$. By Equation III.15 and Theorem B.3, $\beta = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \oplus (\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \oplus \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\delta)]$. Again, considering their similarity in type and being $\widehat{\emptyset}$, if $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta$ is an element of \mathbb{Z}^+ or $\mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$ then $\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta, \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\delta$ are elements of \mathbb{Z}^+ or $\mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$, respectively, based on Definition 1. Thus, by the associativity of the elements of \mathbb{Z}_0^+ or \mathbb{M} under the \oplus operator proven in Theorem B.1 or B.2, respectively, $\beta = [\psi, (\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \oplus \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta) \oplus \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\delta] = (\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{B}) \oplus \widehat{C}$. Therefore, $\widehat{\emptyset}$ bare basic objects of the same type are associative under the \oplus operator. ■

Theorem B.5: The $\widehat{\emptyset}$ operator is commutative and associative over the space $\widehat{\Phi}$ of bare basic objects.

Proof Lemma B.5 proves this theorem for any $\widehat{\emptyset}$ bare basic objects in $\widehat{\Phi}$ with identical type. Now, if any two $\widehat{\emptyset}$ elements of $\widehat{\Phi}$ are not of the same type then the \oplus operator is defined in Item III-C.e to be commutative over them. If any three $\widehat{\emptyset}$ elements of $\widehat{\Phi}$ are not all of the same type then the \oplus operator is defined in Item III-C.f to be associative over them. By using Equation III.16, the \oplus operator is also commutative/associative over any two/three elements of $\widehat{\Phi}$ when some or all of them are $\widehat{\emptyset}$. Therefore, the \oplus operator is commutative and associative over $\widehat{\Phi}$. ■

2) *Common:* Let us now prove theorems related to the \otimes operator.

Theorem B.6: Under the \otimes operator, the space \mathbb{Z}_0^+ is closed and each of its elements is idempotent to itself. Further, \otimes operator is commutative and associative over \mathbb{Z}_0^+ .

Proof Let $A, B \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$ and be expressed as in Equations III.12 and III.13, respectively. Thus, $e_n \triangleq a_n \text{ AND } b_n$ also takes boolean values $\forall 0 \leq n < NBT$. Substituting A, B to Equation III.19 yields

$$A \otimes B = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n e_n \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Therefore, \mathbb{Z}_0^+ is closed under the \otimes operator.

Setting $A = B$ in Equation B.3 and using the properties of the boolean AND operator yields $A \otimes A = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n (a_n \text{ AND } a_n) = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n a_n = A$. Thus, any element of \mathbb{Z}_0^+ is idempotent to itself under the \otimes operator.

By the commutativity of the boolean AND operator over boolean values, one obtains $B \otimes A = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n (b_n \text{ AND } a_n) = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n (a_n \text{ AND } b_n) = A \otimes B$. Therefore, the \otimes operator is commutative over \mathbb{Z}_0^+ .

Consider $C = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n c_n \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$ and let us take $A \otimes (B \otimes C) = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n (a_n \text{ AND } (b_n \text{ AND } c_n))$. By the associativity of the boolean AND operator over boolean values, one yields $A \otimes (B \otimes C) = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n ((a_n \text{ AND } b_n) \text{ AND } c_n) = (A \otimes B) \otimes C$. Therefore, the \otimes operator is associative over \mathbb{Z}_0^+ . ■

Lemma B.6: If $A, B \in ENT = \{1, 3\}$ then $A \otimes B \in ENT$.

Proof Let any two \mathbb{Z}_0^+ elements A, B be expressed as in Equations III.12 and III.13, respectively. Now, Lemma B.1 implies that the elements of ENT can be used as operands of \otimes in Equation III.19 which, together with Equation III.2, yields the following cases:

- 1) $A = 1$ and $B = 1 \implies A \otimes B = 1 \in ENT$.
- 2) $A = 1$ and $B = 3 \implies A \otimes B = 2^0(\text{TRUE AND TRUE}) + 2^1(\text{FALSE AND TRUE}) = 1 \in ENT$.
- 3) $A = 3$ and $B = 1 \implies A \otimes B = 2^0(\text{TRUE AND TRUE}) + 2^1(\text{TRUE AND FALSE}) = 1 \in ENT$.
- 4) $A = 3$ and $B = 3 \implies A \otimes B = 2^0(\text{TRUE AND TRUE}) + 2^1(\text{TRUE AND TRUE}) = 3 \in ENT$.

Thus, in any case, $A \otimes B \in ENT$. ■

Theorem B.7: Under the \otimes operator, the space \mathbb{M} is closed and each of its elements is idempotent to itself. Further, the \otimes operator is commutative and associative over \mathbb{M} .

Proof Consider any two matrices $M = [m_{r,c}], N = [n_{r,c}] \in \mathbb{M}$ where $m_{r,c}, n_{r,c} \in ENT, \forall 1 \leq r \leq NROW, 1 \leq c \leq NCOL$; and $ENT \subset \mathbb{Z}_0^+$ by Lemma B.1. It follows from Lemma B.6 that $m_{r,c} \otimes n_{r,c} \triangleq o_{r,c} \in ENT$. Thus by Equation III.20,

$$M \otimes N = [m_{r,c} \otimes n_{r,c}] = [o_{r,c}] \in \mathbb{M}. \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Therefore, \mathbb{M} is closed under the \otimes operator.

Lemma B.1 implies that $m_{r,c} \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$, such that by Theorem B.6, $m_{r,c} \otimes m_{r,c} = m_{r,c}$. Now, setting $M = N$ in Equation B.4 obtains $M \otimes M = [m_{r,c} \otimes m_{r,c}] = [m_{r,c}] = M$. Thus, any element of \mathbb{M} is idempotent to itself under the \otimes operator.

By Lemma B.1, $n_{r,c} \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$, such that by Theorem B.6, $n_{r,c} \otimes m_{r,c} = m_{r,c} \otimes n_{r,c}$. Thus, $N \otimes M = [n_{r,c} \otimes m_{r,c}] = [m_{r,c} \otimes n_{r,c}] = M \otimes N$. Therefore, the \otimes operator is commutative over \mathbb{M} .

Let us now consider another matrix $O = [o_{r,c}] \in \mathbb{M}$. Again, by Lemma B.1, $o_{r,c} \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$, such that by Theorem B.6, $(m_{r,c} \otimes n_{r,c}) \otimes o_{r,c} = m_{r,c} \otimes (n_{r,c} \otimes o_{r,c})$. Let us then take $(M \otimes N) \otimes O = [(m_{r,c} \otimes n_{r,c}) \otimes o_{r,c}] = [m_{r,c} \otimes (n_{r,c} \otimes o_{r,c})] = M \otimes (N \otimes O)$. Therefore, the \otimes operator is associative over \mathbb{M} . ■

Theorem B.8: The common operator \otimes distributes to the join operator \oplus , and vice versa, over \mathbb{Z}_0^+ .

Proof Consider any three \mathbb{Z}_0^+ elements $A = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n a_n$, $B = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n b_n$ and $C = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n c_n$, where a_n, b_n, c_n are boolean values. Using Equations III.11 and III.19 obtains $A \oplus (B \otimes C) = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n (a_n \text{ OR } (b_n \text{ AND } c_n))$. From Boolean Algebra, the boolean OR operator left-distribute to the AND operator over boolean values, such that, $A \oplus (B \otimes C) = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n ((a_n \text{ OR } b_n) \text{ AND } (a_n \text{ OR } c_n)) = (A \oplus B) \otimes (A \oplus C)$.

Following similar approach, one obtains $(A \otimes B) \oplus C = (A \oplus C) \otimes (B \oplus C)$; $A \otimes (B \oplus C) = (A \otimes B) \oplus (A \otimes C)$; and $(A \oplus B) \otimes C = (A \otimes C) \oplus (B \otimes C)$. Therefore, over \mathbb{Z}_0^+ , the \oplus operator left and right-distribute to the \otimes operator, and vice versa. ■

Theorem B.9: The common operator \otimes distributes to the join operator \oplus , and vice versa, over \mathbb{M} .

Proof Consider any three matrices $E = [e_{r,c}]$, $F = [f_{r,c}]$ and $G = [g_{r,c}] \in \mathbb{M}$ where $e_{r,c}, f_{r,c}, g_{r,c} \in ENT$, $\forall 1 \leq r \leq NROW, 1 \leq c \leq NCOL$; and $ENT \subset \mathbb{Z}_0^+$ by Lemma B.1. Employing Equations III.14 and III.20 yields $E \oplus (F \otimes G) \triangleq X = [e_{r,c} \oplus (f_{r,c} \otimes g_{r,c})]$. In view of Theorem B.8, $X = [(e_{r,c} \oplus f_{r,c}) \otimes (e_{r,c} \oplus g_{r,c})]$; and by Theorems B.2 and B.7, $X \in \mathbb{M}$. Employing Equations III.14 and III.20 again obtains $(E \oplus F) \otimes (E \oplus G) = X$, i.e., the \oplus operator left-distributes to the \otimes operator.

Following similar method yields, $(E \otimes F) \oplus G = (E \oplus G) \otimes (F \oplus G)$; $E \otimes (F \oplus G) = (E \otimes F) \oplus (E \otimes G)$; and $(E \oplus F) \otimes G = (E \otimes G) \oplus (F \otimes G)$. Therefore, over the elements of \mathbb{M} , the \oplus operator left and right-distribute to the \otimes operator, and vice versa. ■

Lemma B.7: Any two elements $A, B \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$ yields $A \oplus (A \otimes B) = A$.

Proof Let A, B be expressed as in Equations III.12 and III.13, respectively. Using Equations III.11 and III.19, yields $A \oplus (A \otimes B) = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n (a_n \text{ OR } (a_n \text{ AND } b_n))$. Considering a_n and b_n are boolean values, then it follows from the boolean identity $a_n \text{ OR } (a_n \text{ AND } b_n) = a_n$ that $A \oplus (A \otimes B) = \sum_{n=0}^{NBT-1} 2^n a_n = A$. ■

Lemma B.8: Any two elements $A, B \in \mathbb{M}$ yields $A \oplus (A \otimes B) = A$.

Proof Consider any two matrices $A = [a_{r,c}]$ and $B = [b_{r,c}] \in \mathbb{M}$ where $a_{r,c}, b_{r,c} \in ENT$, $\forall 1 \leq r \leq NROW, 1 \leq c \leq NCOL$; and $ENT \subset \mathbb{Z}_0^+$ by Lemma B.1. Employing Equations III.14 and III.20 yields $A \oplus (A \otimes B) = [a_{r,c} \oplus (a_{r,c} \otimes b_{r,c})]$. Given that $a_{r,c}, b_{r,c} \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$ then by Lemma B.7 $A \oplus (A \otimes B) = [a_{r,c}] = A$. ■

Theorem B.10: The Absorption Law applies over each of \mathbb{Z}_0^+ and \mathbb{M} .

Proof Lemmas B.7 and B.8 prove this theorem. ■

Lemma B.9: There exists elements $A, B \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ and yet $C = A \otimes B = 0$.

Proof Consider $A = 1$ and $B = 2$, i.e., $0 < A, B \leq \mathbb{Z}^\infty$. Employing Equation III.19 yields $C = A \otimes B = (\text{TRUE AND FALSE}) 2^0 + (\text{FALSE AND TRUE}) 2^1 = 0$. ■

Lemma B.10: There exists elements $A, B \in \mathbb{M}$ and not equal to $\mathbb{1}$, yet $C = A \otimes B = \mathbb{1}$.

Proof Given that $1 \leq r \leq NROW$ and $1 \leq c \leq NCOL$, suppose $A[r, c] = 1$ when $r = c = 1$ and $A[r, c] = 3$ otherwise, i.e., $A \neq \mathbb{1}$. Further, suppose $B[r, c] = 3$ when $r = c = 1$ and $B[r, c] = 1$ otherwise, i.e., $B \neq \mathbb{1}$. Employing Equation III.19 yields $1 \otimes 3 = (\text{TRUE AND TRUE}) 2^0 + (\text{FALSE AND TRUE}) 2^1 = 1$. By Equation III.19, $3 \otimes 1 = 1$. Thus, using Equation III.20 obtains $A[i, j] \otimes B[i, j] = 1, \forall 1 \leq i \leq NROW, 1 \leq j \leq NCOL$, such that $A \otimes B = \mathbb{1}$. ■

Lemma B.11: The common of any two $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects of the same type is either $\hat{\otimes}$ or a $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic object of the same type.

Proof Consider any $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects $\widehat{A} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta]$ and $\widehat{B} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta]$ of type ψ where $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta, \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Using Equation III.21 yields $\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta]$. It is possible that $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta = 0$ based on Lemma B.9, such that by Definition 2, $\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B} = \hat{\otimes}$. Now, suppose $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \neq 0$. Thereby, in conjunction with Theorem B.6, $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \triangleq C \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Therefore, $\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B} = [\psi, C] \neq \hat{\otimes}$ is a $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic object of type similar to those of \widehat{A} and \widehat{B} .

Consider now the bare basic objects $\widehat{F} = [\rho, \langle \widehat{F} \rangle_\delta]$ and $\widehat{G} = [\rho, \langle \widehat{G} \rangle_\delta]$ of type ρ where $\langle \widehat{F} \rangle_\delta, \langle \widehat{G} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$. There is a scenario where $\langle \widehat{F} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{G} \rangle_\delta = \mathbb{1}$ based on Lemma B.10, such that by Definition 2, $\widehat{F} \otimes \widehat{G} = [\rho, \langle \widehat{F} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{G} \rangle_\delta] = \hat{\otimes}$. Now, suppose $\langle \widehat{F} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{G} \rangle_\delta \neq \mathbb{1}$. Thereby, in conjunction with Theorem B.7, $\langle \widehat{F} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{G} \rangle_\delta \triangleq H \in \mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$. Therefore, $\widehat{F} \otimes \widehat{G} = [\rho, H] \neq \hat{\otimes}$ is a $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic object of type similar to those of \widehat{F} and \widehat{G} . ■

Theorem B.11: The set $\widehat{\Phi}$ is closed under the \otimes operator.

Proof In view of Lemma B.11, for any two $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects \widehat{A} and \widehat{B} of similar type $\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}$ is either $\hat{\otimes}$ or a $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic object of the same type, i.e., in either case $\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B} \in \widehat{\Phi}$. Now, if \widehat{A} and \widehat{B} are of different type then by Equation III.22, $\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B} = \hat{\otimes} \in \widehat{\Phi}$. If either or both of them are empty objects then by Equations III.23 and III.24, $\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B} = \hat{\otimes} \in \widehat{\Phi}$. Therefore, the common of any two elements of $\widehat{\Phi}$ is also an element of $\widehat{\Phi}$. ■

Theorem B.12: Any bare basic object is idempotent to itself under the \otimes operator.

Proof Given a type ψ , substituting $\widehat{A} \triangleq [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta] \triangleq \widehat{B} \neq \hat{\otimes}$ in Equation III.21 produces $\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{A} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta]$ where $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta$ could either be an element of \mathbb{Z}^+ or $\mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$. Considering that any element of \mathbb{Z}^+ or $\mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$ is proven in Theorems B.6 or B.7, respectively, to be idempotent to itself under the \otimes operator then $\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{A} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta] = \widehat{A} \neq \hat{\otimes}$.

If $\widehat{A} = \hat{\otimes}$ then $\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{A} = \hat{\otimes} = \widehat{A}$, by Equation III.24. Therefore, in any case, $\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{A} = \widehat{A}$. ■

Lemma B.12: The \otimes operator is commutative and associative over the $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects of the same type.

Proof Consider any $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects $\widehat{A} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta]$ and $\widehat{B} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta]$ of the same type ψ . Thus, by Equation

III.21, $\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta]$. Considering the similarity in type and being $\hat{\otimes}$, if $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta$ is an element of \mathbb{Z}^+ or $\mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$ then $\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta$ is an element of \mathbb{Z}^+ or $\mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$, respectively, based on Definition 1. Thus, by the commutativity of \otimes over $\mathbb{Z}_0^+ \supset \mathbb{Z}^+$ or $\mathbb{M} \supset \mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$ proven respectively in Theorem B.6 or B.7, $\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta] = \widehat{B} \otimes \widehat{A}$. Therefore, the \otimes operator is commutative over $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects of the same type.

Now, let $\widehat{C} = [\psi, \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\delta]$ and form $\beta = \widehat{A} \otimes (\widehat{B} \otimes \widehat{C})$. Applying Equation III.21 yields $\beta = [\psi, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \otimes (\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\delta)]$. Again, considering the similarity in type, if $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta$ is an element of \mathbb{Z}^+ or $\mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$ then $\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta, \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\delta$ are elements of \mathbb{Z}^+ or $\mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$, respectively. Thus, by the associativity of \otimes over \mathbb{Z}_0^+ or \mathbb{M} proven respectively in Theorem B.6 or B.7, $\beta = [\psi, (\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta) \otimes \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\delta]$, i.e., $\beta = (\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}) \otimes \widehat{C}$. Therefore, the \otimes operator is associative over $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects of the same type. ■

Theorem B.13: The \otimes operator is commutative and associative over the space $\widehat{\Phi}$ of bare basic objects.

Proof By Lemma B.12, the \otimes operator is commutative and associative over $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects of identical type.

Consider now any two $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects \widehat{A} and $\widehat{B} \in \widehat{\Phi}$ of different type. By Equation III.22, $\alpha = \widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B} = \hat{\otimes}$ and $\beta = \widehat{B} \otimes \widehat{A} = \hat{\otimes}$, i.e., $\alpha = \beta$. And by Equations III.23 and III.24, if $\widehat{A} = \hat{\otimes}$ and/or $\widehat{B} = \hat{\otimes}$ then $\alpha = \hat{\otimes}$ and $\beta = \hat{\otimes}$, i.e., $\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B} = \widehat{B} \otimes \widehat{A}$. Therefore, the \otimes operator is commutative over $\widehat{\Phi}$.

Consider any three $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects $\widehat{A} = [\alpha, \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta]$, $\widehat{B} = [\beta, \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta]$ and $\widehat{C} = [\gamma, \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\delta]$ with type configuration $\alpha = \gamma \neq \beta$. It follows from Equations III.22 and III.23 that $\widehat{A} \otimes (\widehat{B} \otimes \widehat{C}) = \widehat{A} \otimes \hat{\otimes} = \hat{\otimes}$; and $(\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}) \otimes \widehat{C} = \hat{\otimes} \otimes \widehat{A} = \hat{\otimes}$. Thus, in this type configuration, \otimes is associative over the three $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects. Following similar approach, \otimes can be proven associative over three $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects with type not all the same, and over three bare basic objects at least one is $\hat{\otimes}$. Therefore, the \otimes operator is associative over the space $\widehat{\Phi}$. ■

Theorem B.14: Any two bare basic objects in $\widehat{\Phi}$ satisfy the Absorption Law.

Proof Consider the $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects \widehat{A} and \widehat{B} of the same type ψ and take $\widehat{A} \oplus (\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}) \stackrel{\Delta}{=} C$ which is a bare basic object based on Theorem B.3 and Lemma B.11, i.e., $C = [\langle C \rangle_\rho, \langle C \rangle_\delta]$. Applying Equations III.15 and III.21 yields $\langle C \rangle_\rho = \psi$; and $\langle C \rangle_\delta = \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \oplus (\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta)$. Knowing that \widehat{A} and \widehat{B} are of the same type and $\hat{\otimes}$, and using Definition 1, if $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ then $\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \subset \mathbb{Z}_0^+$; and if $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$ then $\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{M}_{\neq 1} \subset \mathbb{M}$. Thus, by Theorem B.10, $\langle C \rangle_\delta = \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta$. Therefore, $\widehat{A} \oplus (\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}) = \widehat{A}$.

It follows from Equations III.22 and III.23 that: if $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\rho \neq \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\rho$ then $C = \widehat{A} \oplus \hat{\otimes} = \widehat{A}$; if $\widehat{A} = \hat{\otimes}$ and $\widehat{B} \neq \hat{\otimes}$ then $C = \hat{\otimes} \oplus \hat{\otimes} = \widehat{A}$; and if $\widehat{B} = \hat{\otimes}$ and $\widehat{A} \neq \hat{\otimes}$ then $C = \widehat{A} \oplus \hat{\otimes} = \widehat{A}$. Therefore, in any case, $C = \widehat{A} \oplus (\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}) = \widehat{A}$.

Following the same approach, it is straightforward to prove that $\widehat{A} \otimes (\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{B}) = \widehat{A}$ ■

Theorem B.15: The \otimes operator distributes to the \oplus operator, and vice versa, over $\widehat{\Phi}$.

Proof Consider any three $\hat{\otimes}$ bare basic objects \widehat{A}, \widehat{B} and \widehat{C} with type configuration $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\rho = \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\rho = \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\rho = \psi$ and form $E \stackrel{\Delta}{=} (\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{B}) \otimes \widehat{C}$ and $F \stackrel{\Delta}{=} (\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{C}) \oplus (\widehat{B} \otimes \widehat{C})$ that are bare basic objects based on Theorem B.3 and Lemma B.11. Employing the distributive property of \otimes and \oplus over \mathbb{Z}_0^+ and \mathbb{M} , respectively proven in Theorems B.8 and B.9, yields $E_d \stackrel{\Delta}{=} (\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \oplus \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta) \otimes \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\delta = (\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\delta) \oplus (\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\delta) \stackrel{\Delta}{=} F_d$. Supposing $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, then by Definition 1 and Theorems B.1 and B.6, $\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta, \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\delta, E_d, F_d \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$. If $E = \hat{\otimes}$ then by Definition 2 and Equations III.15 and III.21, $\langle E \rangle_\delta = E_d = 0 = F_d = \langle F \rangle_\delta$ and hence $F = \hat{\otimes} = E$. Now, if $E \neq \hat{\otimes}$ then by Definition 2, $E_d = F_d > 0$. Hence, using Equations III.15 and III.21 one obtains, $E = [\psi, E_d] = [\psi, F_d] = F$. Following similar approach, it can be proven that if $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{M}_{\neq 1}$ then $E = F$. Therefore, in any of the cases, $(\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{B}) \otimes \widehat{C} = (\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{C}) \oplus (\widehat{B} \otimes \widehat{C})$. Following analogous procedure, one obtains $(\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}) \oplus \widehat{C} = (\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{C}) \otimes (\widehat{B} \oplus \widehat{C})$.

For any type configuration of \widehat{A}, \widehat{B} and \widehat{C} different to the last, the \otimes operator distributes over the \oplus operator, and vice versa, based on Definition 4.

Now, consider the scenario where $\widehat{A} = \hat{\otimes}, \widehat{B}, \widehat{C} \neq \hat{\otimes}$ and $\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\rho = \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\rho$, and then form $G \stackrel{\Delta}{=} (\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}) \oplus \widehat{C}$ and $H \stackrel{\Delta}{=} (\widehat{A} \oplus \widehat{C}) \otimes (\widehat{B} \oplus \widehat{C})$. By using Equations III.16 and III.23 one obtains, $G = (\hat{\otimes} \otimes \widehat{B}) \oplus \widehat{C} = \hat{\otimes} \oplus \widehat{C} = \widehat{C}$. Applying Theorem B.14 yields, $H \stackrel{\Delta}{=} (\hat{\otimes} \oplus \widehat{C}) \otimes (\widehat{B} \oplus \widehat{C}) = \widehat{C} \otimes (\widehat{B} \oplus \widehat{C}) = \widehat{C}$. Therefore, $G = H$.

Following the same procedure, it can be proven that $E = F$ when $\widehat{A} = \hat{\otimes}, \widehat{B}, \widehat{C} \neq \hat{\otimes}$ and $\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\rho = \langle \widehat{C} \rangle_\rho$; and that \otimes distributes to \oplus , and vice versa, when at least one of the bare basic objects \widehat{A}, \widehat{B} and \widehat{C} is $\hat{\otimes}$. ■

C. Measures

Let us now prove theorems on the measure of the bare basic objects in $\widehat{\Phi}$.

Theorem C.1: Any object has zero or positive consciousness measure.

Proof Based on Definition 2, if an object has negative or zero consciousness level it is set to $\hat{\otimes}$ whose measure is zero by Definition 6. And, if it has positive consciousness level then its consciousness measure is its consciousness level, based on Definition 5. Thus, any object has zero or positive consciousness measure. ■

Theorem C.2: Any $\widehat{\Phi}$ element has positive data measure if and only if it is not equal to $\hat{\otimes}$.

Proof Consider any bare basic object $\widehat{A} = [\psi, A]$ of type ψ with data $A = \langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$ that is expressed in Equation III.12. If $\widehat{A} \neq \hat{\otimes}$ then by Definition 2 $A > 0$ which implies that there is at least one $a_m = \text{TRUE} \exists 0 \leq m < NBT$. In view of Equation III.27 $\#_Z(A) > 0$, such that from Equation III.26, $\|\widehat{A}\| > 0$.

Now, suppose $\|\widehat{A}\| > 0$ which, by Equations III.26 and III.27, implies that $\#_A(A) > 0$ that in turn implies that there is at least one $a_m = \text{TRUE} \exists 0 \leq m < NBT$. Consequently, by Equation III.1, $A > 0$. Therefore, by Definition 2, $\widehat{A} \neq \hat{\otimes}$.

Consider now the case where $A \in \mathbb{M}$. If $\widehat{A} \neq \widehat{\theta}$ then by Definition 2, $A \neq \mathbb{1}$ which implies that there is at least one entry $A[r, c] = 3$, $\exists 1 \leq r \leq NROW, 1 \leq c \leq NCOL$. It then follows from Equation III.27 that $\#_A(A) > 0$, such that from Equation III.26, $\|\widehat{A}\| > 0$.

Finally, suppose $A \in \mathbb{M}$ and $\|\widehat{A}\| > 0$. Thus, by Equations III.26 and III.27, $\#_A(A) > 0$ which implies that there is at least one entry $A[r, c] = 3$, $\exists 1 \leq r \leq NROW, 1 \leq c \leq NCOL$. It follows that $A \neq \mathbb{1}$, such that by Definition 2, $\widehat{A} \neq \widehat{\theta}$. ■

Lemma C.1: If any two elements $A, B \in \mathbb{Z}_0^+$ are equal then $\alpha \triangleq \|A \otimes B\| = \|A\| = \|B\|$; otherwise, either $\alpha = \|A\| < \|B\|$, $\alpha = \|B\| < \|A\|$ or, $\alpha < \|A\|, \|B\|$.

Proof Consider any two \mathbb{Z}_0^+ elements A, B expressed as in Equations III.12 and III.13, respectively. And, let us study the case where $A = 0$ and $B > 0$. Using Equation III.19 yields, $A \otimes B = 0 = A < B$. Following similar approach, if $A > 0$ and $B = 0$ then $A \otimes B = 0 = B < A$; and if $A = 0$ and $B = 0$ then $A \otimes B = 0 = A = B$.

Let us now deal with the case where $A \neq B$ and $A, B > 0$; and segregate the summation terms in Equation III.12 as

$$A = \sum_{o \in I_1} 2^o a_o + \sum_{z \in I_2} 2^z a_z + \sum_{o \in I_3} 2^o a_o + \sum_{z \in I_4} 2^z a_z \quad (\text{C.1})$$

where the set of indices $I_1 = \{o \mid a_o = \text{TRUE}; a_o = b_o; o \in I\}$, $I_2 = \{z \mid a_z = \text{FALSE}; a_z = b_z; z \in I\}$, $I_3 = \{o \mid a_o = \text{TRUE}; a_o \neq b_o; o \in I\}$, $I_4 = \{z \mid a_z = \text{FALSE}; a_z \neq b_z; z \in I\}$ and $I = \{i \mid 1 \leq i < NBT\}$. The definition $a_n, b_n \in \{\text{TRUE}, \text{FALSE}\}$ implies that, $I_i \cap I_j = \emptyset$, $\forall i \neq j, 1 \leq i, j \leq 4$ and $I = \bigcup_{i=1}^4 I_i$. Let us segregate the summation terms in Equation III.13 as

$$B = \sum_{o \in I_1} 2^o b_o + \sum_{z \in I_2} 2^z b_z + \sum_{z \in I_3} 2^z b_z + \sum_{o \in I_4} 2^o b_o. \quad (\text{C.2})$$

The set of indices $I_i, 1 \leq i \leq 4$, in Equations C.1 and C.2 could have a status of being empty (\emptyset) or not (\emptyset). Their various status combinations, referred as scenarios, are illustrated in Table XIV where the last column contains the metric relationships to be justified below.

Consider Table XIV Scenario 1 where $I_1, I_2, I_4 = \emptyset$ and $I_3 = \emptyset$, i.e., the remaining coefficients in Equation C.1 (other coefficients do not exist due to the empty index set they belong to) are all TRUE ($a_o = \text{TRUE}, \forall o \in I_3$), hence the remaining coefficients in Equation C.2 are all FALSE ($b_z = \text{FALSE}, \forall z \in I_3$). Thus, by Equation III.2, $B = 0$ that contradicts the assumption $B > 0$. Hence, Scenario 1 contradicts the assumption $A, B > 0$. Following similar approach, Scenarios 2 to 4 can be proven to contradict similarly.

Let us then deal with Scenario 5 where $I_1, I_3 = \emptyset$ but $I_2, I_4 = \emptyset$. Based on the definition of I_1 and I_3 above, the number of remaining coefficients equal to TRUE in Equations C.1 and C.2 is $|I_1 \cup I_3|$ and $|I_3|$, respectively. Thus, by Equation III.27, $\|B\| < \|A\|$. Now, applying Equation III.19 and the boolean AND operator properties to Equations C.1 and C.2 obtains $A \otimes B = \sum_{o \in I_1} 2^o (\text{TRUE AND TRUE}) + \sum_{o \in I_3} 2^o (\text{TRUE AND FALSE}) = \sum_{o \in I_1 \cap I_3} 2^o \text{TRUE} = B$. Therefore,

TABLE XIV: Coefficient Scenarios

Scenario	I_1	I_2	I_3	I_4	α
1	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	N/A
2	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	N/A
3	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	N/A
4	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	N/A
5	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	$= \ B\ < \ A\ $
6	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	$= \ B\ < \ A\ $
7	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	$= \ A\ < \ B\ $
8	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	$= \ A\ < \ B\ $
9	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	$< \ A\ , \ B\ $
10	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	$< \ A\ , \ B\ $
11	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	$< \ A\ , \ B\ $
12	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	\emptyset	$< \ A\ , \ B\ $

by Equation III.27, $\|A \otimes B\| = \|B\| < \|A\|$. Employing similar methodology can justify Scenario 6.

In Scenario 7, $I_1, I_4 = \emptyset$ and $I_2, I_3 = \emptyset$. From the definition of I_1 and I_4 above, the number of coefficients equal to TRUE in Equations C.1 and C.2 is $|I_1|$ and $|I_1 \cup I_4|$, respectively. Thus, by Equation III.27, $\|A\| < \|B\|$. Applying Equation III.19 and the boolean AND operator properties to Equations C.1 and C.2 yields $A \otimes B = \sum_{o \in I_1} 2^o (\text{TRUE AND TRUE}) + \sum_{o \in I_4} 2^o (\text{FALSE AND TRUE}) = \sum_{o \in I_1} 2^o \text{TRUE} = A$. Therefore, $\|A \otimes B\| = \|A\| < \|B\|$. Scenario 8 can be justified by employing similar approach.

In Scenario 9, $I_i = \emptyset, \forall 1 < i < 4$. Using the definition of I_i above, the number of coefficients equal to TRUE in Equations C.1 and C.2 is $|I_1 \cup I_3|$ and $|I_1 \cup I_4|$, respectively. Applying Equation III.19 and the boolean AND operator properties to Equations C.1 and C.2 one obtains $A \otimes B = \sum_{o \in I_1} 2^o (\text{TRUE AND TRUE}) + \sum_{o \in I_2} 2^o (\text{FALSE AND FALSE}) + \sum_{o \in I_3} 2^o (\text{TRUE AND FALSE}) + \sum_{o \in I_4} 2^o (\text{FALSE AND TRUE}) = \sum_{o \in I_1} 2^o \text{TRUE}$. Therefore, $\|A \otimes B\| < \|A\|, \|B\|$. Similar approach can justify Scenarios 10 to 12.

Table XIV presents Scenarios for $A \neq B$. However, it does not present Scenarios for $A = B$, e.g., $I_1, I_2 = \emptyset$ and $I_3, I_4 = \emptyset$. If $A = B$ then $\|A \otimes B\| = \|A\| = \|B\|$ by using Theorem B.6. ■

Lemma C.2: If any two elements $A, B \in \mathbb{M}$ are equal then $\alpha \triangleq \|A \otimes B\| = \|A\| = \|B\|$; otherwise, either $\alpha = \|A\| < \|B\|$, $\alpha = \|B\| < \|A\|$ or, $\alpha < \|A\|, \|B\|$.

Proof Let $A = [a_{r,c}]$ and $B = [b_{r,c}]$ where $a_{r,c}, b_{r,c} \in ENT = \{1, 3\}, \forall r \in R, c \in C, R = \{r \mid 1 \leq r \leq NROW\}$, and $C = \{c \mid 1 \leq c \leq NCOL\}$. Thus, \exists sets of matrix coordinates $X = \{(r, c) \mid r \in R, c \in C, a_{r,c} = 3\}$ and $Y = \{(r, c) \mid r \in R, c \in C, b_{r,c} = 3\}$. As follows from Equation III.27 $\|A\| = |X|$ and $\|B\| = |Y|$. Now, applying Theorem B.7 obtains $E \triangleq [e_{r,c}] = A \otimes B \in \mathbb{M}$, such that, \exists a set of matrix coordinates $Z = \{(r, c) \mid r \in R, c \in C, e_{r,c} = 3\}$.

If a coordinate $(r, c) \in X$ but $\notin Y$ then $a_{r,c} = 3$ and $b_{r,c} = 1$, such that, $(r, c) \notin Z$ by using Equation III.19. If $(r, c) \notin X$ but $\in Y$ then $a_{r,c} = 1$ and $b_{r,c} = 3 \implies (r, c) \notin Z$. If $(r, c) \notin X, Y$ then $a_{r,c} = 1$ and $b_{r,c} = 1 \implies (r, c) \notin Z$. If $(r, c) \in X, Y$ then $a_{r,c} = 3$ and $b_{r,c} = 3 \implies (r, c) \in Z$. Hence, the only scenario a coordinate $(r, c) \in Z$ is when it is found in both X and Y ,

i.e., $Z = X \cap Y$.

It follows that if $X \subset Y$ then $Z = X$ and hence $|Z| = |X| < |Y| \implies \|E\| = \|A\| < \|B\|$ according to Equation III.27. Following similar procedure proves that if $Y \subset X$ then $\|E\| = \|B\| < \|A\|$; and if $X \not\subset Y$ and $Y \not\subset X$ then $\|E\| < \|A\|, \|B\|$. If $A = B$ then $X = Y \implies |Z| = |X| = |Y|$ and hence $\|E\| = \|A\| = \|B\|$. ■

Lemma C.3: If any two $\hat{\circ}$ bare basic objects $\widehat{A}, \widehat{B} \in \widehat{\Phi}$ are equal then $\alpha \triangleq \|\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}\| = \|\widehat{A}\| = \|\widehat{B}\|$; otherwise, either $\alpha = \|\widehat{A}\| < \|\widehat{B}\|$, $\alpha = \|\widehat{B}\| < \|\widehat{A}\|$ or, $\alpha < \|\widehat{A}\|, \|\widehat{B}\|$.

Proof Consider the $\hat{\circ}$ bare basic objects \widehat{A} and \widehat{B} of the same type and have data $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta, \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. If $\widehat{A} = \widehat{B}$ (i.e., $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta = \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta$) then it follows from Lemma C.1 that $\gamma \triangleq \|\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta\| = \|\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta\| = \|\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta\|$ which, in view of Equations III.21 and III.26, implies that $\gamma \triangleq \|\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}\| = \|\widehat{A}\| = \|\widehat{B}\|$; otherwise, either $\gamma = \|\widehat{A}\| < \|\widehat{B}\|$, $\gamma = \|\widehat{B}\| < \|\widehat{A}\|$ or, $\gamma < \|\widehat{A}\|, \|\widehat{B}\|$.

Let us next consider the $\hat{\circ}$ bare basic objects \widehat{A} and \widehat{B} of the same type and have data $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta, \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{M}_{\mathcal{G}_1}$. If $\widehat{A} = \widehat{B}$ then applying Lemma C.2 yields $\gamma \triangleq \|\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \otimes \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta\| = \|\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta\| = \|\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta\|$ which, based on Equations III.21 and III.26, implies that $\gamma \triangleq \|\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}\| = \|\widehat{A}\| = \|\widehat{B}\|$; otherwise, either $\gamma = \|\widehat{A}\| < \|\widehat{B}\|$, $\gamma = \|\widehat{B}\| < \|\widehat{A}\|$ or, $\gamma < \|\widehat{A}\|, \|\widehat{B}\|$.

Finally, consider the bare basic objects \widehat{A} and \widehat{B} of different type, i.e., $\widehat{A} \neq \widehat{B}$. Thus, by Equation III.22, $\chi = \|\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}\| = \|\hat{\emptyset}\| = 0$ according to Definition 6. It follows from Theorem C.2 that $\chi < \|\widehat{A}\|, \|\widehat{B}\|$. ■

Lemma C.4: If any two $\hat{\circ}$ bare basic objects \widehat{A}, \widehat{B} are equal or not then $SIM(\widehat{A}, \widehat{B}) = 1$ or $0 \leq SIM(\widehat{A}, \widehat{B}) < 1$, respectively.

Proof If $\widehat{A} = \widehat{B}$ then $\|\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}\| = \|\widehat{A}\| = \|\widehat{B}\|$ can be deduced from Lemma C.3. Given that $\widehat{A}, \widehat{B} \neq \hat{\emptyset}$ then $0 < \|\widehat{A}\|, \|\widehat{B}\|$ based on Theorem C.2. Thus, by Equation III.30, $SIM(\widehat{A}, \widehat{B}) = 1$.

If $\widehat{A} \neq \widehat{B}$ then from Equation III.22 it is possible that $\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B} = \hat{\emptyset}$, such that, $\|\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}\|$ can be equal to $\|\hat{\emptyset}\| = 0$ as per Definition 6, otherwise, is greater than zero as follows from Theorem C.2. Now, by Lemma C.3, either $\|\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}\| = \|\widehat{A}\| < \|\widehat{B}\|$, $\|\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}\| = \|\widehat{B}\| < \|\widehat{A}\|$ or $\|\widehat{A} \otimes \widehat{B}\| < \|\widehat{A}\|, \|\widehat{B}\|$. Thus, in any case, $0 \leq SIM(\widehat{A}, \widehat{B}) < 1$ by using Equation III.30. ■

Theorem C.3: If any two $\hat{\circ}$ “eyeVissn”-type bare basic objects $\widehat{A}, \widehat{B} \in \widehat{\Phi}$ are similar then $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta = \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta$.

Proof Given that $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\rho = \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\rho = \text{“eyeVissn”}$ then $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \triangleq A$ and $\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \triangleq B \in \mathbb{M}_{\mathcal{G}_1}$. Now, consider any black pixel $A[r, c] — \exists r \in R, c \in C$ where $R = \{r \mid 1 \leq r \leq NROW\}$, and $C = \{c \mid 1 \leq c \leq NCOL\} —$ with at least one white pixel neighbour $A[s, d]$, $\exists s \in R, d \in C$, in the data/image A , i.e., it is an edge as defined in Section III-F. Knowing that $\widehat{A} = \widehat{B}$, then the pixel $B[r, c]$ is black and also has a white neighbour $B[s, d]$,

i.e., it is an edge in B . Thus, any edge in A has a counterpart edge in B at the same pixel location (r, c) .

Following the logic in the last argument with \widehat{A} and \widehat{B} juxtaposed, it can be shown that any edge in B has a counterpart edge in A at the same pixel location. Therefore, $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta = \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta$. ■

Theorem C.4: If any two $\hat{\circ}$ bare basic objects $\widehat{A}, \widehat{B} \in \widehat{\Phi}$ are similar or different then $\langle \widehat{A} \parallel \widehat{B} \rangle = 1$ or $0 \leq \langle \widehat{A} \parallel \widehat{B} \rangle < 1$, respectively.

Proof Consider first any two $\hat{\circ}$ bare basic objects $\widehat{A}, \widehat{B} \in \widehat{\Phi}$ of the same “eyeVissn” type, i.e., $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta, \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{M}_{\mathcal{G}_1}$. If \widehat{A} and \widehat{B} are similar (i.e., $\widehat{A} = \widehat{B}$ and $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta \neq \hat{\emptyset}$ as per Definition 7) then by Lemma C.4, Theorem C.3 and Equation III.32, $SIM(\widehat{A}, \widehat{B}) SIM(\widehat{A}, \widehat{B}) = 1 = \langle \widehat{A} \parallel \widehat{B} \rangle$.

Now, suppose \widehat{A} and \widehat{B} are different. By Definition 7, this implies the following scenarios: (a) $\widehat{A} \neq \widehat{B}$, $\widehat{A} \neq \widehat{B}$ and $\widehat{A} \neq \widehat{B}$; (b) $\widehat{A} \neq \widehat{B}$, $\widehat{A} = \widehat{B}$ and $\widehat{A} \neq \widehat{B}$; (c) $\widehat{A} \neq \widehat{B}$, $\widehat{A} = \widehat{B}$ and $\widehat{A} = \widehat{B}$ (e.g., when $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta$ and $\langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta$ are all black and white images, respectively); (d) and $\widehat{A} = \widehat{B} = \hat{\emptyset}$. It follows from Lemma C.4, Theorem C.3 and Equation III.32 that the first two items yield $0 \leq \langle \widehat{A} \parallel \widehat{B} \rangle < 1$ while the last two items yield $\langle \widehat{A} \parallel \widehat{B} \rangle = 0$ based on Equations III.30 and III.32. Therefore, for \widehat{A} and \widehat{B} being different, $0 \leq \langle \widehat{A} \parallel \widehat{B} \rangle < 1$.

Next, consider any two $\hat{\circ}$ bare basic objects $\widehat{A}, \widehat{B} \in \widehat{\Phi}$ of the same non-“eyeVissn” type, i.e., $\langle \widehat{A} \rangle_\delta, \langle \widehat{B} \rangle_\delta \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. By employing Equation III.31 and Lemma C.4 one obtains $\langle \widehat{A} \parallel \widehat{B} \rangle = 1$ or $0 \leq \langle \widehat{A} \parallel \widehat{B} \rangle < 1$ if \widehat{A} and \widehat{B} are similar or different, respectively. ■

D. Consolidator

Let us now prove theorems related to the consolidator.

Theorem D.1: If \widetilde{S} is a set of objects then $\Gamma_{[CN]}(\widetilde{S})$ is a bare unique set.

Proof Let \widetilde{P}_i be a partition of \widetilde{S} whereby $\widetilde{S} = \bigcup_{i=1}^{NPAR(\widetilde{S})} \widetilde{P}_i$. Further, let \widehat{C}_i and \widehat{C}_j be elements of \widetilde{P}_i and \widetilde{P}_j , respectively, for $i \neq j$. Furthermore, let $\Gamma_{[CN]}(\widetilde{P}_k) = \widehat{E}_k$ that by Equation III.41, $\langle \widehat{E}_k \rangle_\delta = \langle \widehat{C}_k \rangle_\delta$, $\forall 1 \leq k \leq NPAR(\widetilde{S})$. The definition for the Equation III.47 terms implies that any element of any partition is different to any element of another partition. Thus, $\langle \widehat{C}_i \rangle_\delta$ is different to $\langle \widehat{C}_j \rangle_\delta \forall i \neq j$. It follows that \widehat{E}_i is different to $\widehat{E}_j \forall i \neq j$. Employing Equation III.49 obtains $\Gamma_{[CN]}(\widetilde{S}) = \bigcup_{i=1}^{NPAR(\widetilde{S})} \widehat{E}_i$ that is therefore a bare unique set. ■

Theorem D.2: If \widetilde{S} is a set of objects then $\langle \widetilde{S} \rangle_\beta = \bigcup_{k=1}^{NPAR(\widetilde{S})} \langle \widetilde{P}_k \rangle_\beta = \bigcup_{k=1}^{NPAR(\widetilde{S})} \langle \widehat{E}_k \rangle_\beta$ where \widetilde{P}_k is a partition of \widetilde{S} ; and \widehat{E}_k is any element of \widetilde{P}_k .

Proof Consider the partition $\widetilde{P}_k = \bigcup_{i \in NDX_k} \widehat{S}_{k(i)}$ where $\widehat{S}_{k(i)} \in \widetilde{S}$; $NDX_k = \{i \mid 1 \leq i \leq |\widetilde{P}_k|\}$; and the function $k(i)$ satisfies $1 \leq k(i) \leq |\widetilde{S}|$. It follows from Equation III.10 that $\langle \widetilde{P}_k \rangle_\beta = \bigcup_{i \in NDX_k} \langle \widehat{S}_{k(i)} \rangle_\beta$. By the definition of partition, $\langle \widehat{S}_{k(i)} \rangle_\beta$ are all similar $\forall i \in NDX_k$. Thus, by the idempotency of similar bare components under the union operator implied by Definition 3,

$\langle \tilde{P}_k \rangle_\beta = \langle \tilde{E}_k \rangle_\beta$ where \tilde{E}_k is any $\tilde{S}_{k(i)}$, $\exists i \in NDX_k$. By Equation III.10, one obtains $\langle \tilde{S} \rangle_\beta = \cup_{k=1}^{NPS} \langle \tilde{P}_k \rangle_\beta = \cup_{k=1}^{NPS} \langle \tilde{E}_k \rangle_\beta$. ■

Theorem D.3: If a $\hat{\theta}$ object \hat{O} in the set \tilde{S} is different to all other elements of \tilde{S} then it is in $\Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{S})$.

Proof A partition is defined in Section III-J as a set of similar objects. Given that the $\hat{\theta}$ \hat{O} is different to all the other element of \tilde{S} , then it is alone in the partition \tilde{P} of \tilde{S} where it belongs, i.e., $\tilde{P} = \{\hat{O}\}$. Let the consolidation of \tilde{P} be denoted as $\hat{A} = \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{P})$. Thus, in view of Equations III.39 and III.41 $\langle \hat{A} \rangle_\delta = \langle \hat{O} \rangle_\delta$; of Equations III.42, III.44 and III.45 $\langle \hat{A} \rangle_\gamma = \langle \hat{O} \rangle_\gamma$; and of Equation III.43 $\langle \hat{A} \rangle_\tau = \langle \hat{O} \rangle_\tau$. By the procedures explained in Section III-J to determine the purity, ID and forming operator label descriptors of the consolidation outcome, $\langle \hat{A} \rangle_\eta = \langle \hat{O} \rangle_\eta$, $\langle \hat{A} \rangle_\pi = \langle \hat{O} \rangle_\pi$ and $\langle \hat{A} \rangle_\omega = \langle \hat{O} \rangle_\omega$. Thus, employing Equations III.40 and III.41 yields $\hat{A} = \hat{O}$. The latter is different, by Theorem D.1, to the consolidation outcome of every \tilde{S} partition not \tilde{P} . Therefore, based on Equation III.49, $\hat{O} = \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{P}) \in \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{S})$, i.e. it is preserved by the consolidator. ■

Theorem D.4: If for every partition \tilde{P}_k , $1 \leq k \leq NPAR(\tilde{S})$, of the set \tilde{S} of objects there is a similar partition \tilde{Q}_i , $1 \leq i \leq NPAR(\tilde{T})$, of the set \tilde{T} of objects, and vice versa, then \exists a bijective function $k(i)$ that maps the index i to the index k ; and $NPAR(\tilde{S}) = NPAR(\tilde{T}) \triangleq NP$.

Proof The definition for the Equation III.47 terms implies that all partitions of \tilde{S} are different, such that, \tilde{Q}_i is similar only to $\tilde{P}_{k(i)}$. Likewise, all partitions of \tilde{T} are different, such that, $\tilde{P}_{k(i)}$ is similar only to \tilde{Q}_i . Thus, the function $k(i)$ is bijective and hence $NPAR(\tilde{S}) = NPAR(\tilde{T}) \triangleq NP$.

Theorem D.5: If for any partition of the set \tilde{S} of objects there is a partition of the set \tilde{T} of objects similar to it, but not vice versa, then $\langle \tilde{S} \rangle_\beta \subset \langle \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{T}) \rangle_\beta$.

Proof Consider the similar partitions \tilde{Q}_i and $\tilde{P}_{k(i)}$ of \tilde{T} and \tilde{S} , respectively, where $i \in NDXQ = \{l \mid \tilde{Q}_l \text{ is similar to } \tilde{P}_{k(l)}; 1 \leq l \leq NPAR(\tilde{T})\}$; and $k(i)$ is a function that maps index i to an index $1 \leq k \leq NPAR(\tilde{S})$, and is bijective based on Theorem D.4. It follows from the given that \exists partitions \tilde{R}_j different to $\tilde{P}_{k(i)}$, $\forall i \in NDXQ$, where $j \in NDXR = \{l \mid l \notin NDXQ, 1 \leq l \leq NPAR(\tilde{T})\}$. Thus, applying Equation III.48 yields $\tilde{T} = \cup_{i \in NDXQ} \tilde{Q}_i \cup_{j \in NDXR} \tilde{R}_j$ while $\tilde{S} = \cup_{i \in NDXQ} \tilde{P}_{k(i)}$. In view of Theorem D.2, $\langle \tilde{S} \rangle_\beta = \cup_{i \in NDXQ} \langle \tilde{P}_{k(i)} \rangle_\beta = \cup_{i \in NDXQ} \langle \tilde{F}_{k(i)} \rangle_\beta$ where $\tilde{F}_{k(i)}$ is any element of $\tilde{P}_{k(i)}$; and $\langle \tilde{T} \rangle_\beta = \cup_{i \in NDXQ} \langle \tilde{Q}_i \rangle_\beta \cup_{j \in NDXR} \langle \tilde{R}_j \rangle_\beta = \cup_{i \in NDXQ} \langle \tilde{C}_i \rangle_\beta \cup_{j \in NDXR} \langle \tilde{E}_j \rangle_\beta$ where \tilde{C}_i and \tilde{E}_j are any element of \tilde{Q}_i and \tilde{R}_j , respectively.

Knowing that \tilde{Q}_i and $\tilde{P}_{k(i)}$ are similar then their elements are similar as well, i.e., $\langle \tilde{C}_i \rangle_\beta = \langle \tilde{F}_{k(i)} \rangle_\beta \forall i \in NDXQ$. Thus, applying Equations III.40 and III.41 yields $\langle \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{Q}_i) \rangle_\beta = \langle \tilde{C}_i \rangle_\beta$, $\langle \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{R}_j) \rangle_\beta = \langle \tilde{E}_j \rangle_\beta$ and $\langle \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{P}_{k(i)}) \rangle_\beta = \langle \tilde{C}_i \rangle_\beta$. Employing Equations III.10 and III.49 obtains $\langle \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{T}) \rangle_\beta = \cup_{i \in NDXQ} \langle \tilde{C}_i \rangle_\beta \cup_{j \in NDXR} \langle \tilde{E}_j \rangle_\beta$; and $\langle \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{S}) \rangle_\beta = \cup_{i \in NDXQ} \langle \tilde{C}_i \rangle_\beta = \cup_{i \in NDXQ} \langle \tilde{F}_{k(i)} \rangle_\beta = \langle \tilde{S} \rangle_\beta$. From the definition of partition, $\langle \tilde{E}_j \rangle_\beta \neq \hat{\theta}$, $\forall j \in NDXR$, such that, $\langle \tilde{S} \rangle_\beta \subset \langle \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{T}) \rangle_\beta$. ■

Theorem D.6: Let $\Gamma_{[CNM]}$ be either $\Gamma_{[CNL]}$ or $\Gamma_{[CNM]}$. Given the set $\tilde{S} = \{\hat{\theta}\}$ of objects containing the $\hat{\theta}$ object \hat{O} , the consolidation output $\Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{S})$ contains the object \hat{C} that has $\langle \hat{C} \rangle_\beta = \langle \hat{O} \rangle_\beta$ and $\langle \hat{C} \rangle_\gamma \geq \langle \hat{O} \rangle_\gamma$. Further, if $\langle \hat{O} \rangle_\tau = \max\{\langle \hat{S}_i \rangle_\tau \mid \hat{S}_i \in \tilde{S}\}$ then $\langle \hat{C} \rangle_\tau = \langle \hat{O} \rangle_\tau$.

Proof Given that $\hat{O} \neq \hat{\theta}$ then \exists a partition $\tilde{P}_i \ni \hat{O}$, $1 \leq i \leq NPAR(\tilde{S})$, of $\tilde{S} = \cup_{i=1}^{NPAR(\tilde{S})} \tilde{P}_i$ where, by Equation III.49, $\Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{S}) = \cup_{i=1}^{NPAR(\tilde{S})} \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{P}_i)$. Let $\hat{C} = \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{P}_i)$, i.e., $\hat{C} \in \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{S})$. Considering that $\hat{O} \in \tilde{P}_i$ then, by Equations III.40 and III.41, $\langle \hat{C} \rangle_\beta = \langle \hat{O} \rangle_\beta$.

Any partition is defined to contain $\hat{\theta}$ objects. Thus, by Definition 2, all of its elements have positive consciousness level. Thus, applying Equations III.41 and III.45 yields $\langle \hat{C} \rangle_\gamma \geq \langle \hat{O} \rangle_\gamma$. Also, using Equation III.43 and the given obtains $\langle \hat{C} \rangle_\tau = \langle \hat{O} \rangle_\tau$. ■

Theorem D.7: Any non-empty subset \tilde{S} of a bare unique set \tilde{X} of basic objects is also a bare unique set of basic objects, and $\Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{S}) = \tilde{S}$. Further, with $t = \tau\Delta$, if $\tilde{X} = \{X \mid \mathbf{T} :< t\}$ is τ -old then so as $\tilde{S} = \{S \mid \mathbf{T} :< t\}$.

Proof Consider the bare unique set $\tilde{X} = \cup_{i=1}^{|\tilde{X}|} \tilde{x}_i$ of different τ -old basic objects \tilde{x}_i . It follows that $\langle \tilde{x}_i \rangle_\tau < t$ (or $NTOX(\langle \tilde{x}_i \rangle_\tau) < \tau$), $\forall 1 \leq i \leq |\tilde{X}|$. Take any non-empty subset $\tilde{S} = \cup_{j=1}^{|\tilde{S}|} \tilde{s}_{i(j)} \subset \tilde{X}$ where $i(j)$ is an injective function that maps j to $1 \leq i \leq |\tilde{X}|$. Knowing that $\tilde{s}_{i(j)} \in \tilde{X}$ then $\langle \tilde{s}_{i(j)} \rangle_\tau < t$ (or $NTOX(\langle \tilde{s}_{i(j)} \rangle_\tau) < \tau$) and all $\tilde{s}_{i(j)}$ are different $\forall 1 \leq j \leq |\tilde{S}|$. Therefore, $\tilde{S} = \{S \mid \mathbf{T} :< t\}$ is a bare unique set of τ -old basic objects.

It follows that every element $\tilde{s}_{i(j)}$ is a partition \tilde{P}_j (i.e., $\{\tilde{s}_{i(j)}\} = \tilde{P}_j$) of \tilde{S} . Applying Equation III.49 obtains $\Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{S}) = \cup_{j=1}^{|\tilde{S}|} \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{P}_j) = \cup_{j=1}^{|\tilde{S}|} \tilde{s}_{i(j)} = \tilde{S}$. ■

Theorem D.8: If the set $\tilde{S} = \tilde{O} \cup \tilde{N}$ has different subsets \tilde{O} and \tilde{N} then $\Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{S}) = \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{O}) \cup \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{N})$ where $\Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{O})$ and $\Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{N})$ are different.

Proof Let $\tilde{O} = \cup_{i=1}^{NPAR(\tilde{O})} \tilde{P}_i$ and $\tilde{N} = \cup_{j=1}^{NPAR(\tilde{N})} \tilde{Q}_j$ where \tilde{P}_i and \tilde{Q}_j are their respective partitions. Given that \tilde{O} and \tilde{N} are different then \tilde{P}_i is different to \tilde{Q}_j , $\forall 1 \leq i \leq NPAR(\tilde{O}), 1 \leq j \leq NPAR(\tilde{N})$. Thus, by Equation III.49, $\Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{S}) = \cup_{i=1}^{NPAR(\tilde{O})} \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{P}_i) \cup_{j=1}^{NPAR(\tilde{N})} \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{Q}_j) = \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{O}) \cup \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{N})$. As mentioned, \tilde{P}_i is different to \tilde{Q}_j , such that, $\Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{O})$ is different to $\Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{N})$. ■

Theorem D.9: If for every object in the bare unique set \tilde{S} there is an object in the bare unique set \tilde{U} similar to it then $\Gamma_{[CNM]}(\tilde{S} \cup \tilde{U}) = \tilde{U}^{(1)}$. Further, if \tilde{S} and \tilde{U} are τ -old and τ -new, respectively, then $\tilde{U}^{(1)}$ is τ -new.

Proof Let $\tilde{S} = \cup_{s=1}^{|\tilde{S}|} \tilde{S}_s$, $\tilde{U} = \cup_{u=1}^{|\tilde{U}|} \tilde{U}_u$ and $\tilde{N} = \tilde{S} \cup \tilde{U} = \cup_{p=1}^{NPAR(\tilde{N})} \tilde{P}_p$ where \tilde{P}_p is a partition of \tilde{N} . As given, for every element $\tilde{S}_s \in \tilde{S}$, $s \in T = \{s \mid 1 \leq s \leq |\tilde{S}|\}$, there exists an element $\tilde{U}_{u(s)} \in \tilde{U}$ similar to it where $u(s)$ is a function that maps s to an element of $V = \{u \mid 1 \leq u \leq |\tilde{U}|\}$.

Further, \widetilde{S} and \widetilde{U} are bare unique sets, such that, \dot{S}_s is the only element of \widetilde{S} similar to \dot{U}_b , and vice versa, where $b \in B = \{b \mid b = u(s); s \in T\}$. Thus, \widetilde{N} has partitions either of the form $\widetilde{P}_s = \dot{S}_s \cup \dot{U}_{u(s)}$, $\forall s \in T$, or $\widetilde{P}_d = \dot{U}_d$ where \dot{U}_d is different to any element of \widetilde{S} , $\forall d \in D = \{d \mid d \in (V - B)\}$. Evidently, the set of indices D has no common element with B (i.e., $D \cap B = \emptyset$) and satisfies $D \cup B = V$. Applying Equations III.40 and III.41 yields $\Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{P}_d) = \dot{U}_d \triangleq \dot{U}_d^{(1)}$, $\forall d \in D$ and $\Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{P}_b) = \dot{U}_b^{(1)}$, $\forall b \in B$. Therefore, $\Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{N}) = \widetilde{U}^{(1)}$.

As given, \widetilde{S} and \widetilde{U} are τ -old and τ -new respectively, such that, using Equation III.43 obtains, $NTOX(\langle \dot{U}_b^{(1)} \rangle_\tau) = NTOX(\langle \dot{U}_d^{(1)} \rangle_\tau) = \tau$, $\forall b \in B$, $d \in D$. Therefore, $\Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{N})$ is τ -new. ■

E. Dynamics

Let us explore the following theorems useful to investigate the behaviours of $3.I^M$.

Theorem E.1: At any external time index $\tau \geq 0$, the Sensors state $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1) = \{SEN(t+1) \mid \mathbf{C} : THR, \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ is a bare unique set of τ -new basic objects of different sensory type, and at consciousness level of THR .

Proof From the explanation in Sections IV-E and IV-F, at any internal time $t+1$, Environment triggers Sensors to a state $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1) = \cup_{i=1}^4 \widetilde{S}_{i,t+1}$ where the basic object $\widetilde{S}_{i,t+1} = \{\widetilde{S}_{i,t+1}(\tau) \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t+1, \mathbf{o} : \text{" "}\}$; $\widetilde{S}_{1,t+1}$ to $\widetilde{S}_{4,t+1}$ are equal to \widehat{F}_{sen} , \widehat{F}_{afx} , \widehat{Y}_{sen} and \widehat{Y}_{vis} defined in Equations IV.17, IV.19, IV.23 and IV.25, respectively; and $\widetilde{S}_{i,t+1}(\tau)$ denotes a function of τ . Thus, at any τ , $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1) = \{SEN(t+1) \mid \mathbf{C} : THR, \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ is a set of basic objects of different sensory type (that makes it bare unique), and at consciousness level of THR . Further, the basic objects have internal time label $t+1$, such that by Equation II.1, $NTOX(t+1) = \tau$ that makes them τ -new. ■

Let us now consider the following set segregations. At external time index $\tau > 0$, let the Memory state be split as

$$\widetilde{MEM}(t+1) = \widetilde{MEM}^o(t+1) \cup \widetilde{MEM}^w(t+1) \quad (E.1)$$

where the different sets $\widetilde{MEM}^o(t+1)$ and $\widetilde{MEM}^w(t+1)$ are comprised of τ -old and τ -new basic objects, respectively. Further, let the Feedback state be split as

$$\widetilde{FBK}(t-2) = \widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t-2) \cup \widetilde{FBK}^s(t-2) \quad (E.2)$$

where

$$\widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t-2) = \vec{F}_{t-2} \cup \vec{T}_{t-2} \cup \widetilde{FBK}^d(t-2); \quad (E.3)$$

\vec{F}_{t-2} and \vec{T}_{t-2} are different basic objects of action type which is not the type of the objects in $\widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t-2)$, $\widetilde{FBK}^s(t-2)$ and $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$; $\widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t-2)$ (and hence $\widetilde{FBK}^d(t-2)$) is different to $\widetilde{FBK}^s(t-2)$ and $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$; and for every element of $\widetilde{FBK}^s(t-2)$ there is an element of $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$ similar to it. Furthermore, let the Transformer state be split as

$$\widetilde{XFM}(t+1) = \vec{F}_{t-2} \cup \vec{T}_{t-2} \cup \widetilde{XFM}^c(t+1) \quad (E.4)$$

where \vec{F}_{t-2} and \vec{T}_{t-2} have type different to that of any element of the set $\widetilde{XFM}^c(t+1)$.

Theorem E.2: Suppose at external time index $\tau > 0$ the Sensors and Feedback states, $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1) = \{SEN(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ and $\widetilde{FBK}(t-2) = \{FBK(t-2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t-2\}$, are τ -new and τ -old bare unique sets of basic objects, respectively. Then the Memory state $\widetilde{MEM}(t+1) = \widetilde{MEM}^o(t+1) \cup \widetilde{MEM}^w(t+1) = \{MEM(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$ where the different bare unique sets $\widetilde{MEM}^o(t+1) = \widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t-2) = \{FBK^\delta(t-2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t-2\}$ and $\widetilde{MEM}^w(t+1) = \widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1) = \{MEM^w(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$; and the bare unique set $\widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t-2) \subseteq \widetilde{FBK}(t-2)$ is composed of τ -old basic objects.

Proof Let $\widetilde{N}(t+1) = \widetilde{SEN}(t+1) \cup \widetilde{FBK}^s(t-2)$, such that, $\widetilde{SUM}(t+1) = \widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t-2) \cup \widetilde{N}(t+1)$ based on Equations II.9 and E.2. Knowing $\widetilde{FBK}(t-2)$ to be a bare unique set of τ -old basic objects then, by Equation E.2, so is its subset $\widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t-2) = \{FBK^\delta(t-2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t-2\}$. Thus, applying Theorem D.7 yields

$$\Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t-2)) = \widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t-2) \quad (E.5)$$

and hence is also a bare unique set of τ -old basic objects.

As mentioned above, $\widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t-2)$ is different to $\widetilde{FBK}^s(t-2)$ and $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$, i.e., $\widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t-2)$ is different to $\widetilde{N}(t+1)$. It then follows from Theorem D.8 and Equation IV.29 that

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{SUM}(t+1)) &= \widetilde{MEM}(t+1) \\ &= \Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t-2)) \cup \Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{N}(t+1)) \end{aligned} \quad (E.6)$$

where $\Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t-2))$ and $\Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{N}(t+1))$ yield different sets.

As provided, $\widetilde{FBK}(t-2)$ is a bare unique set of τ -old basic objects then, by Equation E.2, so is its subset $\widetilde{FBK}^s(t-2)$. Further, for every element of $\widetilde{FBK}^s(t-2)$ there is an element of $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$ similar to it. Furthermore, $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$ is τ -new and bare unique. Thus, by Theorem D.9, $\Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{N}(t+1)) = \widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1)$ is τ -new and bare unique. It follows from Equations E.5 and E.6 that $\widetilde{MEM}(t+1) = \{MEM(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\} = \widetilde{MEM}^o(t+1) \cup \widetilde{MEM}^w(t+1)$ where $\widetilde{MEM}^o(t+1) = \widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t-2) = \{FBK^\delta(t-2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t-2\}$ and $\widetilde{MEM}^w(t+1) = \widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1) = \{MEM^w(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ are different and bare unique. ■

Theorem E.3: Suppose at external time index $\tau > 1$ the sets of basic objects $\widetilde{MEM}^o(t+1) = \{MEM^o(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t-2\} = \vec{F}_{t-2} \cup \vec{T}_{t-2} \cup \widetilde{FBK}^d(t-2)$, $\widetilde{MEM}^w(t+1) = \{MEM^w(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ and $\widetilde{FBK}^d(t-2)$ are bare unique; and the different basic objects \vec{F}_{t-2} and \vec{T}_{t-2} have type not found in the basic objects that comprised the bare unique set $\widetilde{MEM}^w(t+1)$. Then $\widetilde{XFM}^c(t+1) = \{XFM^c(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$ is a bare unique set of basic objects.

Proof Consider the basic objects $\vec{M}_i^o \in \widetilde{FBK}^d(t-2) \subseteq \widetilde{MEM}^o(t+1)$, $1 \leq i \leq |\widetilde{MEM}^o(t+1)|$, and $\vec{M}_j^w \in \widetilde{MEM}^w(t+1)$, $1 \leq j \leq |\widetilde{MEM}^w(t+1)|$, with type different to that of \vec{F}_{t-2} and \vec{T}_{t-2} and, based on the given, $\langle \vec{M}_i^o \rangle_\tau \leq t-2$ and

$\langle \vec{M}_j^w \rangle_\tau = t + 1$. Then apply Equations IV.34 to IV.37 to obtain $\Theta(\vec{M}_i^o, \vec{M}_j^w, \Omega) = \dot{X}_{k(i,j)}$ where Ω is either \oplus or \otimes , and $k(i, j)$ is a function that maps i and j to $1 \leq k \leq |\widehat{XFM}''(t+1)|$. If \vec{M}_i^o and \vec{M}_j^w have similar type then, by Equations III.36 and IV.37, $\dot{X}_{k(i,j)} = \{X_{k(i,j)} \mid \mathbf{t} : t+1\}$ may not be $\hat{\theta}$. If so, by Theorem B.3 and Lemma B.11, $\dot{X}_{k(i,j)}$ is a basic object of similar type to \vec{M}_j^w , i.e., it has type different to that of \vec{F}_{t-2} and \vec{I}_{t-2} . On the other hand, using Equation IV.37 yields $\Theta(\vec{F}_{t-2}, \vec{M}_j^w, \Omega) = \Theta(\vec{I}_{t-2}, \vec{M}_j^w, \Omega) = \hat{\theta}$, $\forall \vec{M}_j^w \in \widehat{MEM}^w(t+1)$.

Applying the results obtained thus far to Equations IV.35 and IV.36 then feed this application outcome to Equation IV.34 yields $\widehat{XFM}''(t+1) = \{XFM''(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : t+1\} = \{\dot{X}_{k(i,j)}\}$ which is a set of basic objects with type different to the types $\langle \vec{F}_{t-2} \rangle_\rho$ and $\langle \vec{I}_{t-2} \rangle_\rho$. Consequently, the last two types are also absent in the objects in each partition of $\widehat{XFM}''(t)$, such that by Equations III.43 and III.50 and the above result, this absence also occurs in the set $\Gamma_{[CNM]}(\widehat{XFM}''(t)) = \{XFM^l(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ of basic objects.

The absence also prevails in the set of basic objects $\widehat{FBK}^d(t-2) = \{FBK^d(t-2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t-2\}$ based on the definition of the terms in Equation E.3. Thus, it likewise occurs in,

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{XFM}^c(t) &\triangleq \widehat{FBK}^d(t-2) \cup \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\widehat{XFM}''(t)) \\ &= \{XFM^c(t) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.7})$$

which is therefore a set of basic objects. It follows that $\Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widehat{XFM}^c(t)) \triangleq \widehat{XFM}^c(t)$ is composed of basic objects with type found only in the basic objects of $\widehat{XFM}^c(t)$, such that, the absence ensues in it. Applying Equations III.43 yields $\widehat{XFM}^c(t) = \{XFM^c(t) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$ which, based on the action of the consolidator $\Gamma_{[CNL]}$, is a bare unique set of basic objects.

Using the given $\widehat{MEM}^o(t+1) = \vec{F}_{t-2} \cup \vec{I}_{t-2} \cup \widehat{FBK}^d(t-2)$ and Equations IV.33 and E.7 yields $\widehat{XFM}'(t+1) = \vec{F}_{t-2} \cup \vec{I}_{t-2} \cup \widehat{XFM}^c(t)$, and $\langle \vec{F}_{t-2} \rangle_\tau, \langle \vec{I}_{t-2} \rangle_\tau \leq t-2$. Considering that \vec{F}_{t-2} is different to \vec{I}_{t-2} and both are different to $\widehat{XFM}^c(t)$ (as mentioned above) then by Theorem D.8 and Equation IV.32, $\widehat{XFM}(t+1) = \Gamma_{[CNL]}(\vec{F}_{t-2} \cup \vec{I}_{t-2}) \cup \Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widehat{XFM}^c(t)) = \vec{F}_{t-2} \cup \vec{I}_{t-2} \cup \widehat{XFM}^c(t) = \{XFM(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$ that is bare unique due to the action of $\Gamma_{[CNL]}$, and compose of basic objects based on the nature of \vec{F}_{t-2} , \vec{I}_{t-2} and $\widehat{XFM}^c(t)$. ■

Theorem E.4: Suppose at external time index $\tau > 1$ the Sensors state $\widehat{SEN}(t+1) = \{SEN(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ and the Feedback state $\widehat{FBK}(t-2)$ are τ -new and τ -old bare unique sets of basic objects, respectively. Further, suppose the $\hat{\theta}$ basic object $\vec{O} \in \widehat{FBK}(t-2)$ is different, but of similar type, to $\vec{N} \in \widehat{SEN}(t+1)$. If $\vec{O} \otimes \vec{N} \neq \hat{\theta}$ then $\langle \vec{O} \otimes \vec{N} \rangle_\beta \approx \langle \widehat{XFM}(t+1) \rangle_\beta$.

Proof Considering that \vec{O} is different, but of similar type, to \vec{N} , and that $\widehat{SEN}(t+1)$ is composed of basic objects of different type (based on Theorem E.1) then it is different to all elements of $\widehat{SEN}(t+1)$. Knowing $\vec{O} \in \widehat{FBK}(t-2)$ then, by Equation E.2, $\vec{O} \in \widehat{FBK}^d(t-2)$. By Theorem E.2, $\vec{O} \in$

$\widehat{MEM}^o(t+1)$ and $\vec{N}^{(1)} \in \widehat{MEM}^w(t+1)$. Thus, by Equation IV.36, $\vec{O} \otimes \vec{N}^{(1)} \in \widehat{CMN}(t+1)$. As implied by the given, $\vec{O} \otimes \vec{N}^{(1)} \neq \hat{\theta}$, such that applying Theorem D.6 to Equations IV.32 to IV.37 proves $\langle \vec{O} \otimes \vec{N}^{(1)} \rangle_\beta$ to be produced in Transformer at τ .

Now, there could be a $\hat{\theta}$ basic object $\vec{P} \in \widehat{FBK}(t-2)$ different, but of similar type, to \vec{O} and \vec{N} and yet $\langle \vec{P} \otimes \vec{N}^{(1)} \rangle_\beta = \langle \vec{O} \otimes \vec{N}^{(1)} \rangle_\beta$. Following the above explanation using \vec{P} instead of \vec{O} , it can be proven that $\langle \vec{P} \otimes \vec{N}^{(1)} \rangle_\beta$ can also be in $\widehat{CMN}(t+1)$. Hence, the two similar bare basic objects, $\vec{O} \otimes \vec{N}^{(1)}$ and $\vec{P} \otimes \vec{N}^{(1)}$, could both be in $\widehat{CMN}(t+1)$. By the action of consolidators in Equations IV.32 and IV.33, either or both of them can be absorbed. Therefore, $\langle \vec{O} \otimes \vec{N}^{(1)} \rangle_\beta = \langle \vec{O} \otimes \vec{N} \rangle_\beta \approx \langle \widehat{XFM}(t+1) \rangle_\beta$. ■

Theorem E.5: At any external time index $\tau > 0$ and given $\widehat{XFM}(t+1)$, the Contrector state $\widehat{CON}(t+1) = \{CON(t+1) \mid \mathbf{C} : THR, \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ is either empty or bare unique and comprised of operation type basic objects defined in Equations IV.43 and IV.44.

Proof If $\widehat{XFM}(t+1)$ contains only objects not consciously perceived by $3.I^M$ and/or not formed by any operator (e.g., $\vec{X} = \{X \mid \mathbf{o} : \text{" "}\}$) then, based on Equation IV.38, Contrector produces nothing, i.e., $\widehat{CON}(t+1) = \emptyset$.

Now, suppose $\widehat{XFM}(t+1)$ contains a $\hat{\theta}$ element \dot{X}_j , $j \in NDX_\oplus = \{j \mid \langle \dot{X}_j \rangle_\gamma \geq THR; \langle \dot{X}_j \rangle_\omega = \text{"bJoin"}; 1 \leq j \leq |\widehat{XFM}(t+1)|\}$. In response, through Equations IV.39 and IV.40, Contrector produces the basic object $\vec{C}'_\oplus = \{\widehat{C}'_\oplus \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t+1, \mathbf{o} : \text{" "}\}$ where $\widehat{C}'_\oplus = [\text{"bJoin"}, CAL(\tau)]$. It follows that for each \dot{X}_j , $j \in NDX_\oplus$, Contrector produces identical basic object \vec{C}'_\oplus , i.e., these products form a partition $\vec{P}_\oplus(t+1)$. By the same token, for each element $\dot{Y}_k \in \widehat{XFM}(t+1)$, $k \in NDX_\otimes = \{k \mid \langle \dot{Y}_k \rangle_\gamma \geq THR; \langle \dot{Y}_k \rangle_\omega = \text{"common"}; 1 \leq k \leq |\widehat{XFM}(t+1)|\}$, Contrector forms identical basic object $\vec{C}'_\otimes = \{\widehat{C}'_\otimes \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t+1, \mathbf{o} : \text{" "}\}$ where $\widehat{C}'_\otimes = [\text{"common"}, CAL(\tau)]$, such that, the latest outcomes form a partition $\vec{P}_\otimes(t+1)$.

The difference between \vec{C}'_\otimes and \vec{C}'_\oplus proves the partitions $\vec{P}_\otimes(t+1)$ and $\vec{P}_\oplus(t+1)$ to be different. Further, for each element of $\widehat{XFM}(t+1)$ not consciously perceived by $3.I^M$ and/or not formed by any operator, Contrector creates $\hat{\theta}$ (by Equation IV.38). Thus, Contrector only produces $\widehat{CON}'(t) = \vec{P}_\otimes(t+1) \cup \vec{P}_\oplus(t+1)$. Hence, by Theorem D.8 and Equations III.43 and III.44, $\widehat{CON}(t+1) = \Gamma_{[CMA]}(\widehat{CON}'(t)) = \vec{C}'_\oplus \cup \vec{C}'_\otimes = \{CON(t+1) \mid \mathbf{C} : THR, \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ where \vec{C}'_\oplus and \vec{C}'_\otimes are similar to \vec{C}_\oplus and \vec{C}_\otimes in Equations IV.43 and IV.44, respectively. The latter equations show $\widehat{CON}(t+1)$ to be τ -new, bare unique and composed of the two operation type basic objects \vec{C}'_\oplus and \vec{C}'_\otimes consciously perceived by $3.I^M$.

Lastly, if either of the partitions $\vec{P}_\otimes(t+1)$ and $\vec{P}_\oplus(t+1)$ is empty then either \vec{C}'_\oplus or \vec{C}'_\otimes is absent in the Contrector output at τ . ■

Theorem E.6: Suppose at external time index $\tau > 0$ the set

$\widetilde{NSL}(t+1) = \widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1) \cup \widetilde{CON}(t+1)$ where $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$ and $\widetilde{CON}(t+1)$ are the Sensors and Contrector states, respectively. Further, suppose $\widetilde{XFM}^c(t+1) = \{\dot{X}_j^c \mid 1 \leq j \leq |\widetilde{XFM}^c(t+1)|\}$ is a bare unique set. Then, the interaction between $\widetilde{NSL}(t+1)$ and $\widetilde{XFM}(t+1) = \{XFM(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$ yields $\widetilde{INT}(t+2) = \{INT(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\} \subseteq \widetilde{XFM}^{c(1)}(t+1)$ that is a bare unique set of non-action type basic objects.

Proof In view of Theorem E.5, the Contrector state $\widetilde{CON}(t+1)$ is a set of non-action type basic objects. Thus, $\widetilde{NSL}(t+1) = \widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1) \cup \widetilde{CON}(t+1) \triangleq \{\dot{N}_i\}$ is also a set of non-action type basic objects. It follows from Equations III.22, III.30 to III.32, IV.48 and IV.49 that $\langle \dot{N}_i \mid \oplus \mid \vec{F}_{t-2} \rangle = \langle \dot{N}_i \mid \oplus \mid \vec{T}_{t-2} \rangle = \hat{\theta}$, $\forall \dot{N}_i \in \widetilde{NSL}(t+1)$, where \vec{F}_{t-2} and \vec{T}_{t-2} are action type basic objects related in Equation E.4.

Considering that $\dot{X}_j^c \in \widetilde{XFM}^c(t+1) \subset \widetilde{XFM}(t+1)$ then, by the provided information, $\langle \dot{X}_j^c \rangle_\tau \leq t+1$. Now, the interaction $\langle \dot{N}_i \mid \oplus \mid \dot{X}_j^c \rangle$ of \dot{N}_i to every $\dot{X}_j^c \in \widetilde{XFM}^c(t+1)$ yields $\gamma_{i,j} \dot{X}_j^c$ — where $\gamma_{i,j}$ as defined in Equation IV.49 — that could be $\hat{\theta}$ when $\gamma_{i,j} = 0$ by using Equation III.51 and Definition 2. According to Equations IV.47 and IV.48, the union of the outcomes $\gamma_{i,j} \dot{X}_j^c$ in the interaction between all the $\dot{N}_i \in \widetilde{NSL}(t+1)$ to a fixed \dot{X}_j forms a partition $\widetilde{P}_j = \widetilde{INT}'_j(t+2) \ni \gamma_{i,j} \dot{X}_j^c$. And hence, by applying Equations III.40, III.41 and III.51, one obtains $\Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{P}_j) + \epsilon_j = \dot{X}_j^{c(1)}$ which could be $\hat{\theta}$ when $\gamma_{i,j} \dot{X}_j^c = \hat{\theta}$ based on Equation III.8. Applying Equation III.51 obtains $\langle \dot{X}_j^{c(1)} \rangle_\tau = \langle \dot{X}_j^c \rangle_\tau \leq t+1$, $\forall \dot{X}_j^c \in \widetilde{XFM}^c(t+1)$. Therefore, the Interactor state $\widetilde{INT}(t+2) = \{INT(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\} = \{\dot{X}_j^{c(1)} \mid 1 \leq j \leq |\widetilde{XFM}^c(t+1)|\}$ is a set of non-action type basic objects.

Considering that $\langle \dot{X}_j^{c(1)} \rangle_\beta = \langle \dot{X}_j^c \rangle_\beta \in \langle \widetilde{XFM}^c(t+1) \rangle_\beta$, where $\dot{X}_j^{c(1)}$ could be $\hat{\theta}$, then $\widetilde{INT}(t+2) \subseteq \widetilde{XFM}^{c(1)}(t+1)$. Lastly, given that $\widetilde{XFM}^c(t+1)$ is a bare unique set then, by Theorem D.7, $\widetilde{INT}(t+2)$ is also a bare unique set. ■

Theorem E.7: At any external time index $\tau > 0$, Selector processes all Interactor output objects in $\widetilde{INT}(t+2)$ to obtain objects segregated in either Equations IV.54 and IV.55 or in Equations IV.56 and IV.57.

Proof Inside Selector, all the Interactor output objects are sorted with respect to their consciousness level to form the ordered set $\widetilde{SRT} = \{\dot{S}_i\}$ where \dot{S}_i is defined in Equation IV.53. Now, suppose that the for-loop in the Figure 5 algorithm is never broken. The algorithm then implies that the final loop index $i > NINT = |\widetilde{INT}(t+2)|$, and that there is no sigmoid output $\dot{S}'_i = SGM(\dot{S}_i)$ which has $\langle \dot{S}'_i \rangle_\gamma < THR$ or $SMC(i) > LMC$ in its Step 2 or 4, respectively. Thus, all the sigmoid outputs are consciously perceived by $3.I^M$ that justifies Equation IV.55, and none of them is subconsciously perceived by $3.I^M$ that justifies Equation IV.54.

Suppose now that the for-loop in the Figure 5 algorithm breaks either at Step 2 or 4 with loop index M : Based on the algorithm, $\langle \frac{\dot{S}_i}{\dot{S}_M} \rangle_\gamma \leq 1$, $\forall i \in NDX \triangleq \{i \mid M \leq i \leq NINT\}$,

such that by using Equation III.51, one obtains

$$\langle \dot{T}_i \rangle_\gamma = \left\langle \frac{\dot{S}_i ([(THR/3.0] - \epsilon)}{\dot{S}_M} \right\rangle_\gamma < THR/3.0,$$

$\forall i \in NDX$. Feeding \dot{T}_i to the Sigmoid function in Equation IV.50 and using Equation IV.52 obtain $\langle \dot{T}'_i \rangle_\gamma < THR$, i.e., \dot{T}'_i is subconsciously perceived by $3.I^M$, $\forall i \in NDX$, that justifies Equation IV.56.

On the other hand, with the for-loop broken at loop index M , the Figure 5 algorithm implies that $\langle \dot{S}'_i \rangle_\gamma \geq THR$, $\forall 1 \leq i < M$, i.e., \dot{S}'_i is consciously perceived by $3.I^M$ that justifies Equation IV.57. ■

Theorem E.8: Suppose at external time index τ that $\widetilde{NSL}(t+1) = \widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1) \cup \widetilde{CON}(t+1) = \{NSL(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ and $\widetilde{INT}(t+2) = \{INT(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$, where $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$, $\widetilde{CON}(t+1)$ and $\widetilde{INT}(t+2)$ are the Sensors, Contrector and Interactor states, respectively. Then the Selector state $\widetilde{SEL}(t+2) = \{SEL(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$ is a bare unique set. If $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$, $\widetilde{CON}(t+1)$ and $\widetilde{INT}(t+2)$ do not contain any action type basic objects then so as $\widetilde{SEL}(t+2)$.

Proof The elements of $\widetilde{INT}(t+2)$ only have their consciousness level changed through the Figure 5 algorithm to form the sets $\widetilde{SB}(t+2)$ (defined in either Equation IV.54 or IV.56) and $\widetilde{CN}(t+2)$ (defined in either Equation IV.55 or IV.57), such that, $\widetilde{SB}(t+2) \cup \widetilde{CN}(t+2) = \widetilde{INT}^{(1)}(t+2) = \{INT(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$. Thus, by Equation IV.58, $\widetilde{SEL}'(t+2) \triangleq \widetilde{NSL}(t+1) \cup \widetilde{SB}(t+2) \cup \widetilde{CN}(t+2) = \{SEL'(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$. By the consolidator action in Equation IV.59 on the $\widetilde{SEL}'(t+2)$ elements one obtains, through Equation III.43, the Selector state $\widetilde{SEL}(t+2) = \{SEL(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$ as a bare unique set.

As provided, $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$, $\widetilde{CON}(t+1)$ and $\widetilde{INT}(t+2)$ do not contain any action type basic object. Further, the Figure 5 algorithm and the Equation IV.59 consolidator $\Gamma_{[CNM]}$ do not create any action type basic object if none is found in $\widetilde{INT}(t+2)$ and $\widetilde{SEL}'(t+2)$. Thus, $\widetilde{SEL}(t+2)$ does not contain any action type basic object. ■

Theorem E.9: Suppose at external time index τ the Selector state $\widetilde{SEL}(t+2) = \{SEL(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$ does not contain action type basic objects. Then, the Feedback state $\widetilde{FBK}(t+2) = \vec{F}_{t+2} \cup \vec{T}_{t+2} \cup \widetilde{FBK}^c(t+2) = \{FBK(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+2\}$ where $\widetilde{FBK}^c(t+2) = \{FBK^c(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$ is a bare unique set of non-action type basic objects; $\vec{F}_{t+2} = \{[["force", 3] \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{t} : t+2]\}$; and $\vec{T}_{t+2} = \{[["footIntnt", 1] \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{t} : t+2]\}$.

Proof As implied in Section IV-K, the elements of $\widetilde{SEL}(t+2)$ may or may not be allowed to become elements of the Feedback output. Let the allowed elements comprise the set $\widetilde{SEL}^c(t+2) \subseteq \widetilde{SEL}(t+2) = \{SEL(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$. Given that $\widetilde{SEL}(t+2)$ does not contain any action type basic object and is bare unique then so as $\widetilde{SEL}^c(t+2)$. Thus, by Theorem D.7, $\Gamma_{[CNL]}(\widetilde{SEL}^c(t+2)) = \widetilde{SEL}^c(t+2) \triangleq \widetilde{FBK}^c(t+2) = \{FBK^c(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$. From Equations IV.60 and IV.61, Executioner always outputs only $\vec{F}_{t+2} = \{[["force", 3] \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{t} : t+2]\}$ and $\vec{T}_{t+2} = \{[["footIntnt", 1] \mid$

$\mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{t} : t + 2$, i.e., \vec{F}_{t+2} and \vec{T}_{t+2} are different and both are different to $\vec{SEL}^c(t + 2)$. Thus, by Theorem D.8 and Equations IV.63 and IV.64, $\vec{FBK}(t + 2) = \Gamma_{[CNL]}(\vec{SEL}^c(t + 2)) \cup \Gamma_{[CNL]}(\vec{F}_{t+2} \cup \vec{T}_{t+2}) = \vec{F}_{t+2} \cup \vec{T}_{t+2} \cup \vec{FBK}^c(t + 2)$. Considering the time labels of \vec{F}_{t+2} , \vec{T}_{t+2} and $\vec{SEL}^c(t + 2)$ one obtains $\vec{FBK}(t + 2) = \{FBK(t + 2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t + 2\}$. ■

1) *Induction:* The recursive nature of the $3.I^M$ defining equations (e.g., Equations II.9 to II.16) entails mathematical inductive proofs to $3.I^M$ dynamics. To explore these proofs, Figure XV is utilized where its first column signifies the internal time at which the events comprising the episode below transpired; and, for each of its non-temporal columns, its non-header row entries are elements of the header entry at internal time indicated in the same row. It is a depiction of the episode which is itemized below. Now, let the integer-labelled enumeration item below (e.g. [7]) describes one of the events that occurs at internal time equal to this integer. The episode comprising events are as follows:

[0] At external time index $\tau = 0$, $3.I^M$ location in Environment is at $x(0) = 0$ according to the initial condition of Equation IV.14. Thus, Environment issues to Sensors the information $ENV(0, 0)$ defined in Equation IV.1.

[1] This information is processed as follows:

(s) Environment triggers Sensors to a state $\vec{SEN}(1) = \cup_{i=1}^4 \vec{S}_{i,1}$ where the basic object $\vec{S}_{i,1} = \{\widehat{S}_{i,1} \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : 1, \mathbf{o} : \text{" "}\}$; $\widehat{S}_{1,1}$ to $\widehat{S}_{4,1}$ is equal to $\widehat{F}_{sen}, \widehat{F}_{afx}, \widehat{Y}_{sen}$ and \widehat{Y}_{vis} defined in Equations IV.17, IV.19, IV.23 and IV.25, respectively; and, by Theorem E.1, $\vec{SEN}(1)$ is a bare unique set of 0-new basic objects of different sensory type.

(σ) Feedback state is empty according to the initial condition defined in Item II-B.1. Thus, from Equation II.9 and Item E1.1.s (sub-item (s) of item [1] in Section E1), $\vec{SUM}(1) = \vec{SEN}(1)$.

(m) Employing the results in Items E1.1.s and 1. σ (the reference "E1." is assumed to prefix "1. σ " to avoid its repetition) to Theorem E.2 obtains the sets $\vec{MEM}^o(1) = \emptyset$ and $\vec{MEM}^w(1) = \vec{SEN}(1)$ defined in Section IV-G.

(t) Using the conclusions in Item E1.1.m to Equations IV.32 to IV.37 yields $\vec{XFM}(1) = \emptyset$.

(c) Utilizing the outcome in Item E1.1.t to Equation IV.38 produces $\vec{CON}(1) = \emptyset$. Thus, by Equation IV.45, $\vec{NSL}(1) = \vec{SEN}(1)$ that is thus bare unique.

[2] The last Memory, Transformer and Contrector outputs are processed as follows:

(n) Applying the results in Items E1.1.t and 1.c to Equations IV.46 to IV.49 proves $\vec{INT}(2) = \emptyset$.

(l) Using the outcomes in Items E1.1.m, 1.c and 2.n to Figure 5 algorithm and Equations IV.58 and IV.59 yields $\vec{SEL}(2) = \vec{NSL}(1) = \vec{SEN}(1)$ that is thus a bare unique set of non-action type basic objects.

(x) As explained in Section IV-L, Executioner produces the action type basic objects $\vec{F}_2 = \{[\text{"force"}, 3] \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : 2, \mathbf{o} : \text{" "}\}$ and $\vec{T}_2 = \{[\text{"footIntnt"}, 1] \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : 2, \mathbf{o} : \text{" "}\}$ both consciously perceived by

$3.I^M$ and comprise $\vec{XEC}(2)$.

(f) As implied in Section IV-K, elements of $\vec{SEL}(2)$ may or may not be allowed to become elements of the Feedback output. Let the allowed elements comprise the set $\vec{SEL}^c(2) \subseteq \vec{SEN}(1)$. Applying the outcomes in Items E1.2.l and 2.x to Equation IV.63 obtains $\vec{FBK}'(2) = \vec{F}_2 \cup \vec{T}_2 \cup \vec{FBK}^c(2)$ where $\vec{FBK}^c(2) = \vec{SEL}^c(2) \subseteq \vec{SEN}(1)$ that therefore does not contain any action type basic object. Now, based on Item E1.1.s, $\vec{SEN}(1)$ is a set of sensory type 0-new basic objects, i.e., not of action type. Thus, $\vec{FBK}'(2)$ is a bare unique set of 0-new (or 1-old) basic objects and includes only one "force" and "footIntnt" type basic objects. It follows from Theorem D.7 that $\vec{FBK}(2) = \vec{FBK}'(2)$, i.e., it is composed of 1-old basic objects.

[3] By Equation IV.12, Actuators acquires \vec{F}_2 and \vec{T}_2 only.

[4] Using the details in Items E1.0 and 3 to Equations IV.14 and IV.15 proves Foot moves $3.I^M$ to location $x(1) = 1$. Thus, by Equation IV.1, Environment issues to Sensors the information $ENV(1, 1)$.

Theorem E.10: At any external time index $\tau > 0$, $3.I^M$ is at Environment location $x(\tau) = \tau$. Further, the Feedback state $\vec{FBK}(t - 2) = \{FBK(t - 2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t - 2\} = \vec{F}_{t-2} \cup \vec{T}_{t-2} \cup \vec{FBK}^c(t - 2)$ is a bare unique set of τ -old basic objects, and includes only one "force" and "footIntnt" type basic objects \vec{F}_{t-2} and \vec{T}_{t-2} , respectively, where these types are not found in the objects of $\vec{FBK}^c(t - 2)$.

Proof Let us assume that at a fixed external time index $k > 0$ $3.I^M$ is at Environment location $x(k) = k = NTOX(t)$ where $t = k\Delta$. And, the bare unique Feedback state $\vec{FBK}(t - 2) = \{FBK(t - 2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t - 2\}$ is composed of k -old basic objects that includes at most one "force" and "footIntnt" type basic objects, \vec{F}_{t-2} and \vec{T}_{t-2} , respectively.

In the following itemized episode, also presented in Figure XV, let the integral item label be added to t to obtain the internal time (e.g. $t + 2$) at which the event described at the item occurs. The episode comprising events are as follows:

[0] As being assumed, $3.I^M$ is at location k in Environment which then issues to Sensors the information $ENV(k, k)$ defined in Equation IV.1.

[1] This information is processed as follows:

(s) Theorem E.1 shows that Environment triggers Sensors to a bare unique state $\vec{SEN}(t + 1) = \{\vec{SEN}(t + 1) \mid \mathbf{T} : t + 1\}$ composed of k -new sensory type basic objects at THR consciousness level.

(σ) By Equation II.9, $\vec{SUM}(t + 1) = \vec{SEN}(t + 1) \cup \vec{FBK}(t - 2)$.

(m) Applying the above assumptions and the result in Theorem item E.10.1.s (sub-item (s) of item [1] in Theorem E.10) to Theorem E.2 obtains $\vec{MEM}(t + 1) = \Gamma_{[CNL]}(\vec{SUM}(t + 1)) = \vec{MEM}^o(t + 1) \cup \vec{MEM}^w(t + 1)$ where the two bare unique different sets $\vec{MEM}^o(t + 1) = \vec{F}_{t-2} \cup \vec{T}_{t-2} \cup \vec{FBK}^d(t - 2) = \{MEM^o(t + 1) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t - 2\}$ and $\vec{MEM}^w(t + 1) = \vec{SEN}^{(1)}(t + 1)$ are composed of k -old and k -new basic objects, respectively. Both $\vec{FBK}^d(t - 2)$ and $\vec{MEM}^w(t + 1)$ do not contain any action type basic object since the former is defined through Equation E.3

TABLE XV: object flow for Section E1

t	$\widetilde{SEN}(t)$	$\widetilde{SUM}(t)$	$\widetilde{MEM}^o(t)$	$\widetilde{MEM}^w(t)$	$\widetilde{XFM}(t)$	$\widetilde{NSL}(t)$
1	$\vec{S}_{i,1}$	$\widetilde{SEN}(1)$	\emptyset	$\widetilde{SEN}(1)$	\emptyset	$\widetilde{SEN}(1)$
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
$t+1$	$\vec{S}_{i,t+1}$	$\widetilde{SEN}(t+1), \vec{F}_{t-2}, \vec{I}_{t-2}, \vec{FBK}^c(t-2)$	$\vec{F}_{t-2}, \vec{I}_{t-2}, \vec{FBK}^d(t-2)$	$\widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1)$	$\vec{F}_{t-2}, \vec{I}_{t-2}, \vec{XFM}^c(t+1)$	$\widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1), \vec{C}_{j,t+1}$
t		$\widetilde{INT}(t)$	$\widetilde{SEL}(t)$	$\widetilde{XEC}(t)$	$\widetilde{FBK}(t)$	$\widetilde{ACT}(t)$
2		\emptyset	$\widetilde{SEN}(1)$	\vec{F}_2, \vec{I}_2	$\vec{F}_2, \vec{I}_2, \widetilde{SEN}'(1)$	
3						\vec{F}_2, \vec{I}_2
\vdots		\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
$t+2$		$\subseteq \widetilde{XFM}^{c(1)}(t+1), \vec{F}_{t-2}, \vec{I}_{t-2}$	$\widetilde{SEN}^{(2)}(t+1), \vec{F}_{t-2}, \vec{I}_{t-2}$	$\vec{F}_{t+2}, \vec{I}_{t+2}$	$\vec{F}_{t+2}, \vec{I}_{t+2}, \vec{FBK}^c(t+2)$	
$t+3$						$\vec{F}_{t+2}, \vec{I}_{t+2}$

as such, and the latter is equal to the set $\widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1)$ of sensory type basic objects.

- (t) Applying the results in Theorem item E.10.1.m to Theorem E.3 yields $\widetilde{XFM}(t+1) = \vec{F}_{t-2} \cup \vec{I}_{t-2} \cup \vec{XFM}^c(t+1) = \{XFM(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$ where $\vec{XFM}^c(t+1) = \{XFM^c(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$ is a bare unique set of non-action type basic objects.
- (c) Employing the details in Theorem item E.10.1.t to Theorem E.5 proves the Contrector state $\widetilde{CON}(t+1) = \{CON(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ as a set of k -new operation type basic objects, and could be empty. Applying the results in Theorem items E.10.1.s and 1.m (the reference ‘‘E.10.’’ is assumed to prefix ‘‘1.m’’ to avoid its repetition) to Equation IV.45 obtains $\widetilde{NSL}(t+1) = \widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1) \cup \widetilde{CON}(t+1) = \{NSL(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ which thus contains k -new non-action type basic objects.

[2] The Memory, Transformer and Contrector states at internal time $t+1$ are processed as follows:

- (n) Applying the results in Theorem items E.10.1.m, 1.t and 1.c to Theorem E.6 yields the Interactor state $\widetilde{INT}(t+2) = \{INT(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\} \subseteq \widetilde{XFM}^{c(1)}(t+1)$ as a bare unique set of non-action type basic objects where $\widetilde{XFM}^c(t+1)$ is defined through Equation E.4. The non-existence of a basic object is indicated in Table XV as a backslash across the variable representing the basic object, e.g., \vec{F}_{t-2} denotes \vec{F}_{t-2} is non-existent.
- (l) Using the results in Theorem items E.10.1.s, 1.c and 2.n to Theorem E.8 proves the Selector state $\widetilde{SEL}(t+2) = \{SEL(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$ as a bare unique set of non-action type basic objects.
- (x) As explained in Section IV-L, Executioner produces the action type basic objects $\vec{F}_{t+2} = \{[‘‘force’’, 3] \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t+2, \mathbf{o} : ‘‘ ’’\}$ and $\vec{I}_{t+2} = \{[‘‘foot-Intnt’’, 1] \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t+2, \mathbf{o} : ‘‘ ’’\}$, both consciously perceived by $3.I^M$ and comprise $\widetilde{XEC}(t+2) = \{XEC(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : t+2\}$.

- (f) Using the details in Theorem items E.10.2.l and 2.x to Theorem E.9, one obtains the Feedback state $\widetilde{FBK}(t+2) = \vec{F}_{t+2} \cup \vec{I}_{t+2} \cup \vec{FBK}^c(t+2) = \{FBK(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+2\}$ as a $(k+1)$ -old (i.e., $k+1 < NTOX(t+2)$) set of basic objects where $\vec{FBK}^c(t+2) = \{FBK^c(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$ is a bare unique set of non-action type basic objects, and \vec{F}_{t+2} and \vec{I}_{t+2} are ‘‘force’’ and ‘‘footIntnt’’ type basic objects, respectively, with time label of $t+2$.

[3] Equation IV.12 implies that Actuators acquires \vec{F}_{t+2} and \vec{I}_{t+2} .

[4] Employing the assumed $3.I^M$ location at k in Environment at internal time t and the results in Theorem items E.10.2.x and E.10.3 to Equations IV.14 and IV.15 proves Foot moves $3.I^M$ to location $k+1$ at external time index $k+1 = NTOX(t+4)$. Thus, Environment issues the information $ENV(k+1, k+1)$ to Sensors.

Notice that, at external time index $k+1$, the Feedback state mentioned in Theorem item E.10.2.f can be expressed as $\widetilde{FBK}(t'-2) = \{FBK(t'-2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t'-2\}$ where $t' = (k+1)\Delta$. Further, in the same item, the action type basic objects becomes $\vec{F}_{t'-2}$ and $\vec{I}_{t'-2}$.

In summary, Items E1.2.f and E1.4 prove this theorem true only for external time index 1. This theorem is assumed true above only for a fixed external time index $k > 0$. And using this assumption obtains the details in Theorem items E.10.2.f and E.10.4 that prove the theorem true for external time index $k+1$. Thus, by mathematical induction [88], the theorem is true for any external time index $k > 0$. ■

Theorem E.11: At any external time index $\tau \geq 0$, $\widetilde{MEM}^w(t+1) = \widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1)$ and $\widetilde{SEN}^{(2)}(t+1) \subseteq \widetilde{SEL}(t+2)$.

Proof For $\tau = 0$, Items E1.1.m and 1.l prove $\widetilde{MEM}^w(1) = \widetilde{SEN}(1)$ and $\widetilde{SEN}(1) = \widetilde{SEL}(t+2)$, respectively.

For any $\tau > 0$, Theorems E.1 and E.10 prove that the Sensors and Feedback states, $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$ and $\widetilde{FBK}(t-2)$, are bare unique sets of τ -new and τ -old basic objects, respectively. Therefore, by Theorem E.2, $\widetilde{MEM}^w(t+1) = \widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1)$.

Applying Equations IV.45, IV.58 and IV.59 and Theorem D.5 yields $\overline{SEN}^{(2)}(t+1) \subseteq \overline{SEL}(t+2)$. ■

Theorem E.12: At any external time index $\tau > 0$, all objects in $\overline{NSL}(t+1) = \{NSL(t+1) \mid \mathbf{C} : THR, \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ are τ -new and consciously perceived by $3.I^M$.

Proof For any $\tau > 0$: Theorem E.1 shows that $\overline{SEN}(t+1) = \{SEN(t+1) \mid \mathbf{C} : THR, \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ is composed of τ -new objects consciously perceived by $3.I^M$; Theorem E.11 proves that $\overline{MEM}^w(t+1) = \overline{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1)$; and Theorem E.5 justifies $\overline{CON}(t+1) = \{CON(t+1) \mid \mathbf{C} : THR, \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ that can be empty or composed of τ -new objects consciously perceived by $3.I^M$. Therefore, by Equation IV.45, $\overline{NSL}(t+1) = \{NSL(t+1) \mid \mathbf{C} : THR, \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ is composed of τ -new objects consciously perceived by $3.I^M$. ■

Theorem E.13: At any external time index $\tau > 0$, each of the Memory, Transformer, Interactor and Selector states is composed of objects with time label lesser than or equal to $t+1$.

Proof At any external time index $\tau > 0$, the bare unique Sensors and Feedback states $\overline{SEN}(t+1) = \{SEN(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$ and $\overline{FBK}(t-2) = \{FBK(t-2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t-2\} = \overline{FBK}^o(t-2) \cup \overline{FBK}^s(t-2)$ based on Theorems E.1 and E.10, respectively, where $\overline{FBK}^o(t-2) = \{FBK^o(t-2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t-2\} = \overline{F}_{t-2} \cup \overline{I}_{t-2} \cup \overline{FBK}^d(t-2)$ and $\overline{FBK}^s(t-2)$ are defined through Equations E.2 and E.3. Employing Theorem E.2 shows the Memory state $\overline{MEM}(t+1) = \{MEM(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\} = \overline{MEM}^o(t+1) \cup \overline{MEM}^w(t+1)$ where $\overline{MEM}^o(t+1) = \overline{FBK}^o(t-2)$ and $\overline{MEM}^w(t+1) = \overline{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1) = \{MEM^w(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$, i.e., $\overline{MEM}^w(t+1)$ does not contain action type basic object.

It follows from Theorem E.3 that $\overline{XFM}(t+1) = \{XFM(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\} = \overline{F}_{t-2} \cup \overline{I}_{t-2} \cup \overline{XFM}^c(t+1)$ where $\overline{XFM}^c(t+1) = \{XFM^c(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$ is a bare unique set of non-action type basic objects and defined through Equation E.4.

Theorem E.5 justifies $\overline{CON}(t+1) = \{CON(t+1) \mid \mathbf{T} : t+1\}$. Thus, applying Theorems E.6 and E.12 obtains $\overline{INT}(t+2) = \{INT(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$.

Finally, by Theorems E.6 and E.8 $\overline{SEL}(t+2) = \{SEL(t+2) \mid \mathbf{T} : \leq t+1\}$. ■

Theorem E.14: For any $\hat{\phi}$ Sensors-issued basic object \overrightarrow{S} at external time index $\tau > 0$, Memory and Selector output the τ -new basic objects $\overrightarrow{M} \in \overline{MEM}^w(t+1)$ and $\overrightarrow{L} \in \overline{SEL}(t+2)$, respectively, where $\langle \overrightarrow{M} \rangle_\beta = \langle \overrightarrow{L} \rangle_\beta = \langle \overrightarrow{S} \rangle_\beta$ and $\langle \overrightarrow{M} \rangle_\gamma, \langle \overrightarrow{L} \rangle_\gamma \geq THR$.

Proof By Theorems E.1, any Sensors-issued basic object \overrightarrow{S} has time label $t+1$ and consciousness level of THR at external time index $\tau > 0$. Theorem E.10 proves Feedback state as $\overline{FBK}(t-2)$ defined in Equations E.2 and E.3. It then follows from Theorem E.2 that $\overline{MEM}^w(t+1) \ni \overrightarrow{M} = \overrightarrow{S}^{(1)}$ where, by Theorem D.6, $\langle \overrightarrow{M} \rangle_\gamma \geq THR$. From Theorem E.13, any element of Memory at $t+1$ has time label lesser than or equal to $t+1$. Thus, by Theorem D.6, \overrightarrow{M} is a τ -new basic object.

Now, Equation IV.45 implies that $\overrightarrow{M} \in \overline{NSL}(t+1)$, such that by Equations IV.58 and IV.59, Selector processes \overrightarrow{M} at $t+2$ to output the basic object $\overrightarrow{L} = \overrightarrow{S}^{(2)}$, i.e., $\langle \overrightarrow{L} \rangle_\beta = \langle \overrightarrow{S} \rangle_\beta$. Thus, by Theorem D.6, $\langle \overrightarrow{L} \rangle_\gamma \geq THR$. From Theorem E.13, any element of Selector at $t+2$ has time label lesser than or equal to $t+1$. Thus, by Theorem D.6, \overrightarrow{L} is a τ -new basic object. ■

Theorem E.15: At external time index $\tau > 0$, any $\hat{\phi}$ Sensors-issued basic object \overrightarrow{S} at $t+1$ is absorbed in Selector at $t+2$ to the Interactor output object \overrightarrow{I} at $t+2$, or vice versa, if $\langle \overrightarrow{S} \rangle_\beta = \langle \overrightarrow{I} \rangle_\beta$.

Proof According to Theorem E.14, Memory outputs the basic object $\overrightarrow{M} \in \overline{MEM}^w(t+1)$ where $\langle \overrightarrow{M} \rangle_\beta = \langle \overrightarrow{S} \rangle_\beta$, such that, by Equation IV.45 $\overrightarrow{M} \in \overline{NSL}(t+1)$, and by Equation IV.58 $\overrightarrow{M} \in \overline{SEL}(t+2)$. The latter also contains $\overrightarrow{I}^{(1)}$ based on the Figure 5 algorithm where, using the given, $\langle \overrightarrow{I}^{(1)} \rangle_\beta = \langle \overrightarrow{I} \rangle_\beta = \langle \overrightarrow{S} \rangle_\beta$. Thus, considering the consolidator $\Gamma_{[CNM]}$ action in Equation IV.59, $\langle \overrightarrow{S} \rangle_\beta$ is absorbed in Selector at $t+2$ to $\langle \overrightarrow{I} \rangle_\beta$, or vice versa. ■

Theorem E.16: At external time index $\tau > 0$, it is possible that the union $\langle \overline{SEN}(t+1) \rangle_\beta \cup \langle \overline{CON}(t+1) \rangle_\beta \subset \langle \overline{FBK}(t+2) \rangle_\beta$. And when realized, the elements of $\langle \overline{SEN}^c(t+1) \rangle_\beta \cup \langle \overline{CON}(t+1) \rangle_\beta \subset \langle \overline{FBK}(t+2) \rangle_\beta$ have data identical at each τ and repeats every eight external time indices, where $\overline{SEN}^c(t+1) = \overline{F}_{sen} \cup \overline{Y}_{sen}$, and \overline{F}_{sen} and \overline{Y}_{sen} are defined in Equations IV.16 and IV.22, respectively. At $\tau = 0$, if $|\overline{SEN}(1)| < MXS$ then $\langle \overline{FBK}(2) \rangle_\beta = \langle \overline{SEN}(1) \rangle_\beta \cup \langle \overline{XEC}(2) \rangle_\beta$.

Proof Given the Sensors state $\overline{SEN}(t+1)$, Theorem E.11 implies that $\langle \overline{SEN}(t+1) \rangle_\beta \subset \langle \overline{SEL}(t+2) \rangle_\beta$ at any given external time index $\tau > 0$. By Equations IV.63 and IV.64, it is possible that $\langle \overline{SEN}(t+1) \rangle_\beta \subset \langle \overline{FBK}(t+2) \rangle_\beta$.

Given the Contructor state $\overline{CON}(t+1)$, Equations IV.45, IV.58 and IV.59 imply that $\langle \overline{CON}(t+1) \rangle_\beta \subset \langle \overline{SEL}(t+2) \rangle_\beta$. Thus, by Equations IV.63 and IV.64, it is possible that $\langle \overline{CON}(t+1) \rangle_\beta \subset \langle \overline{FBK}(t+2) \rangle_\beta$. Therefore, it is possible that $\langle \overline{SEN}(t+1) \rangle_\beta \cup \langle \overline{CON}(t+1) \rangle_\beta \subset \langle \overline{FBK}(t+2) \rangle_\beta$.

Now, at any external time index $\tau > 0$, the elements of $\langle \overline{SEN}^c(t+1) \rangle_\beta$ are defined in Equations IV.17 and IV.23 while the Contructor state $\overline{CON}(t+1)$ is justified by Theorem E.5 to be composed of the basic objects defined in Equations IV.43 and IV.44. Thus, by Equation IV.11, the elements of $\langle \overline{SEN}^c(t+1) \rangle_\beta \cup \langle \overline{CON}(t+1) \rangle_\beta \subset \langle \overline{FBK}(t+2) \rangle_\beta$ have data identical at each τ and repeats every eight external time indices.

At $\tau = 0$, $FBK(-2) = \emptyset$ as defined in Item II-B.1, i.e., it contains no τ -old basic objects. Thus, by Equations II.9 and IV.29 and Theorem D.7, $\overline{MEM}(1) = \overline{SEN}(1) = \overline{MEM}^w(1)$, i.e., $\overline{MEM}(1)$ only contains τ -new basic objects and, by Theorem E.1, is bare unique. Thus, Transformer has no output based on Equations IV.32 to IV.37. Consequently, by Equations IV.38 to IV.42, Contructor has no output. Further, by Equations IV.45 to IV.48, Interactor has no output as well. The Figure 5 algorithm and Equations IV.45, IV.58 and IV.59 imply that $\langle \overline{SEL}(2) \rangle_\beta = \langle \overline{SEN}(1) \rangle_\beta$. The Selector state $\overline{SEL}(2)$ and Executioner state $\overline{XEC}(2)$ — which has elements defined in Equations IV.60 and IV.61 — are fed to Feedback. Given that $|\overline{SEN}(1)| < MXS$ then $\overline{SEN}(1) = \overline{SEL}(2) = \overline{SEL}^c(2)$ in Equation IV.63. Knowing

that the sets $\widehat{SEN}(1)$ and $\widehat{XEC}(2)$ are, respectively, composed of sensory and action type objects (i.e., they are different) then, by Theorem D.8 and Equations IV.63 and IV.64, $\langle \widehat{FBK}(2) \rangle_\beta = \langle \widehat{SEN}(1) \rangle_\beta \cup \langle \widehat{XEC}(2) \rangle_\beta$. ■

At any fixed external time index $\tau > 0$, let the set of similar type ψ bare basic objects be

$$\langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau, \psi) \rangle_\beta = \bigcup_{i=1}^{|\widehat{SMT}(\tau, \psi)|} \widehat{O}_i(\tau, \psi)$$

where

$$\widehat{O}_i(\tau, \psi) = [\psi, z_i(\tau)]; \quad (\text{E.8})$$

and the function $z_i(\tau)$ yields an element of \mathbb{Z}^+ . Further, let the Sensors-issued bare basic object of type ψ at $t + 1$ be

$$\widehat{S}(\tau, \psi) = [\psi, 2^{\kappa(\tau)} \text{TRUE}] \quad (\text{E.9})$$

where $\psi \in \Psi = \{m^+, m^-, \text{"footSen"}, \text{"eyeSen"}\}$; $2^{\kappa(\tau)} = \text{CAL}(\tau)$ if $\psi = \text{"footSen"}$ or "eyeSen" , and $0 \leq \kappa(\tau) \leq 31 < \text{NBT}$, if $\psi = m^+$ or m^- ; and $\kappa(\tau)$ is a function of τ . In the expression

$$\langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau, \psi) \rangle_\beta = \langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta \cup \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi) \cup \langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta \oplus \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi), \quad (\text{E.10})$$

let $\langle \widehat{SMT}(\sigma, \psi) \rangle_\beta = \widehat{\theta}$ when $\sigma < 0$, i.e., $\langle \widehat{SMT}(0, \psi) \rangle_\beta = \widehat{S}(0, \psi)$. Lastly, let the set of positive integers $\text{XPS} = \{i \mid 0 \leq i < \text{NBT}\}$.

Theorem E.17: For any external time index $\tau > 0$ and $\kappa \in \text{XPS}$, $\langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau, \psi) \rangle_\beta \oplus \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi) = \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi)$ or $\widehat{\theta}$.

Proof Consider any $\widehat{O}_i(\tau, \psi) \in \langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau, \psi) \rangle_\beta$, and take $\widehat{O}_i^c(\tau, \psi) \triangleq \widehat{O}_i(\tau, \psi) \otimes \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi) = [\psi, z_i(\tau) \otimes (2^\kappa \text{TRUE})]$ by Equations III.21 and E.9, where $z_i(\tau) = \sum_{n=0}^{\text{NBT}-1} 2^n a_{n,i}(\tau)$; and the function $a_{n,i}(\tau)$ yields either TRUE or FALSE. In accord with Equation III.19, the expression $z_i(\tau) \otimes (2^\kappa \text{TRUE}) = (2^\kappa a_{\kappa,i}(\tau)) \otimes (2^\kappa \text{TRUE})$. If $a_{\kappa,i}(\tau) = \text{TRUE}$ then $\widehat{O}_i^c(\tau, \psi) = \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi)$, else $\widehat{O}_i^c(\tau, \psi) = \widehat{\theta}$ based on Definition 2. Thus, employing the set theoretic properties of the \cup operator over bare basic objects, one obtains $\langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau, \psi) \rangle_\beta \oplus \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi) = \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi)$ or $\widehat{\theta}$. ■

Lemma E.1: At any fixed external time index $\tau > 0$, suppose all elements of the set $\langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta$ are unauthentic (not authentic) generalization, and the only possible ψ type bare basic objects in the Feedback output $\langle \widehat{FBK}(t - 2) \rangle_\beta$. Then, all elements of $\langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau, \psi) \rangle_\beta$ are unauthentic generalization, and the only possible ψ type bare basic objects in the Feedback output $\langle \widehat{FBK}(t + 2) \rangle_\beta$. This result is due to the data of the Transformer inputs at τ .

Proof Consider a fixed $\psi \in \Psi$. In accord with Equations IV.16 to IV.20, IV.22 and IV.23, Sensors issues at external time index $\tau > 0$ the only ψ type $\widehat{\theta}$ basic object $\vec{\widehat{S}}(\tau, \psi) = \{\widehat{S}(\tau, \psi) \mid \mathbf{c} : \text{THR}, \mathbf{t} : t + 1\} \in \widehat{SEN}(t + 1)$ where $\widehat{S}(\tau, \psi)$ is defined in Equation E.9. The bare basic object $\widehat{S}(\tau, \psi)$ could be similar to at most one (based on Theorem E.10) bare basic object $\widehat{S}^s(\tau, \psi) \in \langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta$, such that, all the elements of the set $\langle \widehat{SMT}^d(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta \triangleq \langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta - \widehat{S}^s(\tau, \psi)$ are different to $\widehat{S}(\tau, \psi)$. Now, Theorems E.1 and E.10 imply that $\widehat{SEN}(t + 1)$ and $\widehat{FBK}(t - 2)$ are bare unique sets of τ -new and τ -old basic objects, respectively. Thus, applying

Theorem E.2 obtains $\langle \widehat{SMT}^d(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta \subset \langle \widehat{MEM}^o(t + 1) \rangle_\beta$ and $\widehat{S}(\tau, \psi) \in \langle \widehat{MEM}^w(t + 1) \rangle_\beta$ that are inputs to Transformer.

Equations IV.32 to IV.37 imply that all the ψ type bare basic objects that Transformer outputs comprise

$$\langle \widehat{SMT}^c(\tau, \psi) \rangle_\beta \triangleq \langle \widehat{SMT}^d(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta \cup \langle \widehat{SMT}^d(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta \oplus \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi) \cup \langle \widehat{SMT}^d(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta \otimes \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi). \quad (\text{E.11})$$

Applying Theorem E.17 yields

$$\langle \widehat{SMT}^d(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta \otimes \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi) = \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi) \text{ or } \widehat{\theta}, \quad (\text{E.12})$$

i.e., due to the data of the Transformer inputs $\langle \widehat{SMT}^d(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta$ and $\widehat{S}(\tau, \psi)$ as can be inferred from the proof of Theorem E.17. By employing the given, every element of $\langle \widehat{SMT}^d(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta$ is an unauthentic generalization, such that, every element of $\langle \widehat{SMT}^d(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta \oplus \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi)$ is also an unauthentic generalization as the \oplus operation does not perform generalization. Therefore, every element of $\langle \widehat{SMT}^c(\tau, \psi) \rangle_\beta$ is likewise an unauthentic generalization due to the data of the Transformer inputs at τ .

Using Equations IV.32 to IV.37 and Theorem D.6 proves all elements of $\langle \widehat{SMT}^c(\tau, \psi) \rangle_\beta$ to be the only ψ type bare basic objects in $\langle \widehat{XFM}^c(t + 1) \rangle_\beta$ where $\widehat{XFM}^c(t + 1)$ is defined through Equation E.4. Based on Theorem E.6, these bare basic objects are also the only possible ψ type elements of $\langle \widehat{INT}(t + 2) \rangle_\beta$. They are then used in the Figure 5 algorithm to become the only possible ψ type bare basic objects in $\langle \widehat{CN}(t + 2) \rangle_\beta \cup \langle \widehat{SB}(t + 2) \rangle_\beta = \langle \widehat{INT}^{(1)}(t + 2) \rangle_\beta \subset \langle \widehat{SEL}'(t + 2) \rangle_\beta$ related through Equation IV.58. The latter also relates the set $\langle \widehat{NSL}(t + 1) \rangle_\beta \subset \langle \widehat{SEL}'(t + 2) \rangle_\beta$ that, by Equation IV.45 and Theorem E.2, contains $\widehat{S}(\tau, \psi) \in \langle \widehat{SEN}(t + 1) \rangle_\beta = \langle \widehat{MEM}^w(t + 1) \rangle_\beta$ as the only ψ type bare basic object in $\langle \widehat{NSL}(t + 1) \rangle_\beta$. Thus, employing $\widehat{SEL}'(t + 2)$ to Equation IV.59 and using Theorem D.6, one can prove that all the possible ψ type bare basic object Selector outputs comprise $\langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau, \psi) \rangle_\beta = \langle \widehat{SMT}^c(\tau, \psi) \rangle_\beta \cup \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi) = \langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta \cup \langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta \oplus \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi) \cup \widehat{S}(\tau, \psi)$ whose initial condition is defined through Equation E.10; the last equation is derived by using Equations E.11 and E.12, Theorem B.4, and the idempotence of bare basic objects under the \cup operation. Knowing that $\widehat{S}(\tau, \psi)$ is Sensors-issued (i.e., an unauthentic generalization) then every element of $\langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau, \psi) \rangle_\beta$ is also an unauthentic generalization due to the data of the Transformer inputs at τ , as can be inferred from the above results.

The Selector output $\langle \widehat{SEL}(t + 2) \rangle_\beta$ is united with the non- ψ type Executioner outputted bare basic objects, defined in Equations IV.60 and IV.61, resulting to the ψ type bare basic object Feedback input found only in $\langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau, \psi) \rangle_\beta$. As implied in Section IV-M, Feedback does not add new bare basic object to its input to obtain its output, such that, the elements of $\langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau, \psi) \rangle_\beta$ are the only possible ψ type bare basic objects in the Feedback output $\langle \widehat{FBK}(t + 2) \rangle_\beta$. From the above, this result is due to the data of the Transformer inputs at τ . ■

Theorem E.18: At any external time index $\tau > 0$, any ψ -type bare basic object in the Feedback output is an unauthentic

generalization due to the data of the Transformer inputs at σ , $\forall 0 < \sigma \leq \tau$.

Proof In conformity with Equations IV.16 to IV.20, IV.22 and IV.23, Sensors issues at external time index $\tau = 0$ the only ψ type $\hat{\sigma}$ basic object $\vec{S}(0, \psi) = \{\widehat{S}(0, \psi) \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{t} : t + 1\}$ where $\widehat{S}(0, \psi) = [\psi, 2^{\kappa(0)}\text{TRUE}]$ and $\langle \widehat{SMT}(0, \psi) \rangle_\beta$ based on Equation E.9 and the initial condition for Equation E.10, respectively. Using the details in Item E1.2.f one concludes that $\widehat{S}(0, \psi)$ is the only possible ψ type bare basic object found in $\langle \widehat{FBK}(2) \rangle_\beta$. Without loss of generality, let this prospect be realized.

At external time index $\tau = 1$, Sensors issues the only ψ type $\hat{\sigma}$ basic object $\vec{S}(1, \psi) = \{\widehat{S}(1, \psi) \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{t} : t + 1\}$ where $\widehat{S}(1, \psi) = [\psi, 2^{\kappa(1)}\text{TRUE}]$. Thus, by Lemma E.1 and $\langle \widehat{SMT}(0, \psi) \rangle_\beta$ derived above, all elements of $\langle \widehat{SMT}(1, \psi) \rangle_\beta$ are unauthentic generalization, and the only possible ψ type bare basic objects in the Feedback output $\langle \widehat{FBK}(\Delta + 2) \rangle_\beta$. Without loss of generality, let this prospect be realized.

Now, suppose that at external time index $\tau - 1 \geq 0$ all elements of $\langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau - 1, \psi) \rangle_\beta$ are ψ type bare basic objects, unauthentic generalization, and the only possible ψ type bare basic objects in the Feedback output $\langle \widehat{FBK}((\tau - 1)\Delta + 2) \rangle_\beta$. At external time index τ , Sensors issues the only ψ type $\hat{\sigma}$ basic object $\vec{S}(\tau, \psi) = \{\widehat{S}(\tau, \psi) \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{t} : t + 1\}$ where $\widehat{S}(\tau, \psi)$ is defined through Equation E.9. Thus, by Lemma E.1, all elements of $\langle \widehat{SMT}(\tau, \psi) \rangle_\beta$ are unauthentic generalization, and the only possible ψ type bare basic objects in the Feedback output $\langle \widehat{FBK}(\tau\Delta + 2) \rangle_\beta$. Without loss of generality, let this prospect be realized. Therefore, by mathematical induction, any ψ -type bare basic object in the Feedback output is an unauthentic generalization at any external time index $\tau > 0$.

This conclusion is made through the use of Lemma E.1, such that, it is due to the data of the Transformer inputs. The recursive form of Equation E.10 implies that the conclusion is due to the data of the Transformer inputs at external time index σ , $\forall 0 < \sigma \leq \tau$. ■

Theorem E.19: At any external time index $\tau > 0$, any operation type bare basic object in the Feedback output $\langle \widehat{FBK}(t + 2) \rangle_\beta$ is an unauthentic generalization due to the data of the Transformer inputs at $t + 1$.

Proof As implied in Section IV-H, the Transformer inputs at any $\tau > 0$ are $\langle \widehat{MEM}^w(t + 1) \rangle_\beta = \langle \widehat{SEN}^{(1)}(t + 1) \rangle_\beta$ (by Theorem E.3) and $\langle \widehat{MEM}^o(t + 1) \rangle_\beta$ which may or may not contain operation type bare basic objects. Without loss of generality, suppose $\langle \widehat{MEM}^o(t + 1) \rangle_\beta$ does contain operation type bare basic objects, all in the set $\langle \widehat{OPR}(t + 1) \rangle_\beta = \bigcup_{i=1}^{|\widehat{OPR}(t+1)|} \vec{O}_i^o$. Now, any elements $\vec{O}_i^o \in \widehat{OPR}(t + 1)$ and $\vec{M}_j^w \in \widehat{SEN}^{(1)}(t + 1)$ are feed to, and processed in, the Transformer using Equation IV.37 which yield $\hat{0}$, as they are of different type. Thus, applying Equations IV.32 to IV.36, E.4 and Theorem D.6 obtains $\widehat{XFM}^c(t + 1)$ devoid of any operation type basic object (i.e., due to the Transformer inputs at $t + 1$), and so does $\widehat{INT}(t + 2)$ based on Theorem E.6. The elements of $\widehat{INT}(t + 2)$ are then used in the Figure 5 algorithm to obtain the set

$\widehat{CN}(t + 2) \cup \widehat{SB}(t + 2) = \widehat{INT}^{(1)}(t + 2) \subset \widehat{SEL}'(t + 2)$ that has, therefore, no operation type basic object.

Now, by Theorem E.5, Contrector may or may not produce either or both of the operation type bare basic objects defined in Equations IV.43 and IV.44 that are unauthentic generalization based on these equations. To abide by Equation IV.45, the bare basic objects become elements of $\langle \widehat{NSL}(t + 1) \rangle_\beta \subset \langle \widehat{SEL}'(t + 2) \rangle_\beta$, such that by Equation IV.59 and Theorem D.6, $\langle \widehat{SEL}(t + 2) \rangle_\beta$ contains operation type, but unauthentic generalized, bare basic objects.

The latter are united with the non-operation type Executioner outputs (defined in Equations IV.60 and IV.61), then the union is inputted to Feedback, as supported in Sections IV-L and IV-M. The latter shows Feedback as not adding new bare basic object to its input to produce its output, such that, $\langle \widehat{FBK}(t + 2) \rangle_\beta$ contains operation type, but unauthentic generalized, bare basic objects. From the above discussion, this result is due to the data of the Transformer inputs at $t + 1$. ■

Theorem E.20: The random variable x with average $\mathbf{E}[x]$ and standard deviation $\sigma[x] \ll \mathbf{E}[x]$ yields $\prod_{i=1}^N x_i \approx \mathbf{E}[x]^N$ where $x_i = \mathbf{E}[x] + dx_i$ is the i^{th} sample value of x , dx_i is the difference between x_i and $\mathbf{E}[x]$, and N is a large positive integer.

Proof Consider the expression $P_2 = x_1 x_2$ where $x_1 = \mathbf{E}[x] + dx_1$ and $x_2 = \mathbf{E}[x] + dx_2$ such that $P_2 = (\mathbf{E}[x] + dx_1)(\mathbf{E}[x] + dx_2) = \mathbf{E}[x]^2 (1 + [dx_1 + dx_2]/\mathbf{E}[x] + \epsilon)$ where $\epsilon = dx_1 dx_2 / (\mathbf{E}[x]^2)$. Considering that $\sigma[x] \ll \mathbf{E}[x]$ then $\epsilon \approx 0$ and $P_2 \approx \mathbf{E}[x]^2 (1 + [dx_1 + dx_2]/\mathbf{E}[x])$.

Now take, $P_3 = x_1 x_2 x_3$ where $x_3 = \mathbf{E}[x] + dx_3$ such that $P_3 \approx \mathbf{E}[x]^2 (1 + [dx_1 + dx_2]/\mathbf{E}[x]) (\mathbf{E}[x] + dx_3) \approx \mathbf{E}[x]^3 (1 + [dx_1 + dx_2 + dx_3]/\mathbf{E}[x])$, again by using the given $\sigma[x] \ll \mathbf{E}[x]$.

Suppose $P_n \approx \mathbf{E}[x]^n (1 + [\sum_{i=1}^n dx_i]/\mathbf{E}[x])$ for a fixed n . Let us take, $P_{n+1} = P_n (\mathbf{E}[x] + dx_{n+1}) \approx \mathbf{E}[x]^{n+1} (1 + [\sum_{i=1}^{n+1} dx_i]/\mathbf{E}[x])$. Therefore, by induction, $P_n \approx \mathbf{E}[x]^n (1 + [\sum_{i=1}^n dx_i]/\mathbf{E}[x])$ for any value of n .

For large value of N the sum $\sum_{i=1}^N dx_i \approx 0$; otherwise $\mathbf{E}[x]$ is not the average of x . Therefore, $P_N \approx \mathbf{E}[x]^N$. ■

2) *Conscious level dynamics:* Each proof presented thus far only uses concepts contained in the theorem it proves. In the foregoing, however, this containment is defied in order to simplify concept declaration. Thus, the terms *dynamics* and *illustration* are employed instead of theorem and proof, respectively. Let us now explore the consciousness level dynamics of the objects as they move along the $3.I^M$ system.

Dynamics E.1: At every external time index τ , $1 \leq \tau \leq N \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, suppose Sensors issues a basic object similar in type but different to the basic object $\vec{K} = \{\vec{K} \mid \mathbf{c} : C_0\} \in \widehat{FBK}(2)$, where $C_0 < THR$. Then $\langle \vec{K} \rangle_\gamma$ can rise from being subconsciously to consciously perceived by $3.I^M$ over τ .

Illustration In the following itemized episode, let the integral item label be added to $t = \Delta$ to obtain the internal time at which the event described by the item occurs. The episode comprising events are as follows:

[0] Theorem E.10 implies $3.I^M$ as being at Environment location $x = 1$, such that, Environment issues to Sensors the information $ENV(1, 1)$ defined in Equation IV.1.

[1] This information is processed as follows:

(s) Theorem E.1 justifies the Sensors state $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$ as bare and type unique. One basic object $\vec{S}_{t+1} = \left\{ \vec{S}_{t+1} \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t+1, \mathbf{o} : \text{" " } \right\} \in \widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$ has similar type but different bare component to that of \vec{K} , as provided. Thus, \vec{K} is different to all elements of $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$.

(o) In compliance with Equation II.9, $\widetilde{SUM}(t+1) = \widetilde{SEN}(t+1) \cup \widetilde{FBK}(t-2)$ where, by Theorem E.10, $\widetilde{FBK}(t-2) = \vec{F}_{t-2} \cup \vec{I}_{t-2} \cup \widetilde{FBK}^d(t-2) \cup \widetilde{FBK}^s(t-2)$ is bare unique — the terms in the last equation are defined in Equations E.2 and E.3. It follows from the results in Dynamics item E.1.1.s (subitem (s) of item [1] in Dynamics E.1) that $\vec{K} \in \widetilde{FBK}^d(t-2)$.

(m) Employing the details in Dynamics items E.1.1.s and 1.o and Theorem E.2 obtains the different bare unique sets $\widetilde{MEM}^o(t+1) = \vec{F}_{t-2} \cup \vec{I}_{t-2} \cup \widetilde{FBK}^d(t-2) \ni \vec{K}$ and $\widetilde{MEM}^w(t+1) = \widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1) \ni \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(1)}$ comprised of 1-old and 1-new basic objects, respectively.

(t) Applying the results in Dynamics item E.1.1.m with Theorem D.6 to Equations IV.32 to IV.37 yields $\vec{K}^{(1)} = \left\{ \vec{K} \mid \mathbf{c} : \chi_1 C_0 \right\} \in \widetilde{XFM}^c(t+1)$, $\exists \chi_1 \in \mathbb{R}^+$, where $\widetilde{XFM}^c(t+1)$ is bare unique based on Theorem E.3 and defined through Equation E.4.

(c) As can be inferred from Theorem E.5, if the Contrector state $\widetilde{CON}(t+1)$ is not empty then it is operation type unique. In contrast, the outcome in Dynamics item E.1.1.s shows $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$ as sensory type unique. Thus, applying the results in Dynamics item E.1.1.m to Equation IV.45 yields $\widetilde{NSL}(t+1) = \widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1) \cup \widetilde{CON}(t+1) \ni \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(1)}$ that is therefore type unique.

[2] The last Memory, Transformer and Contrector outputs are processed as follows:

(n) As mentioned in Dynamics item E.1.1.c, $\widetilde{NSL}(t+1)$ is type unique, such that, applying Equations IV.47 to IV.49 yields $\left\langle \widetilde{NSL}(t+1) \mid \oplus \mid \vec{K}^{(1)} \right\rangle = \left\langle \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(1)} \mid \oplus \mid \vec{K}^{(1)} \right\rangle = \eta_1 \vec{K}^{(1)} = \left\{ \vec{K} \mid \mathbf{c} : \eta_1 \chi_1 C_0 \right\} \triangleq \vec{K}^{(2)}$ which is considered as a singleton set/partition, and has

$$\eta_1 \propto \langle \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(1)} \rangle_\gamma \quad (\text{E.13})$$

based on Equation IV.49. Thus, by Equations III.51 and IV.46, $\Gamma_{[CNL]} \left(\left\langle \widetilde{NSL}(t+1) \mid \oplus \mid \vec{K}^{(1)} \right\rangle \right) + \epsilon_1 = \left\{ \vec{K} \mid \mathbf{c} : (\eta_1 \chi_1 + \epsilon_1) C_0 \right\} \triangleq \vec{K}^{(3)}$ where $\epsilon_1 \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is a random value that satisfies $-MXR \leq \epsilon_1 \leq MXR \in \mathbb{R}^+$. The bare basic object \vec{K} is different to all the other elements of the bare unique $\langle \widetilde{XFM}(t+1) \rangle_\beta$, as mentioned in Dynamics item E.1.1.t. Thus, by Theorem E.6, $\vec{K}^{(3)}$ is in, but different to all the other elements of, $\widetilde{INT}(t+2)$ which is bare unique based on Theorem E.6.

(l) The Figure 5 algorithm could change the consciousness level of $\vec{K}^{(3)}$, say, to produce $\vec{K}^{(4)} = \left\{ \vec{K} \mid$

$\mathbf{c} : \sigma_1 (\eta_1 \chi_1 + \epsilon_1) C_0 \right\} \in \widetilde{SEL}'(t+2)$ where σ_1 is the change factor. Further, based on the Dynamics item E.1.1.c information, $\vec{K}^{(4)}$ is different to all elements of $\widetilde{NSL}(t+1)$. Thus, by Equations IV.58 and IV.59, it is in, but different to all the other elements of, $\widetilde{SEL}(t+2)$ which is bare unique based on Theorem E.8.

(x) As explained in Section IV-L, Executioner produces the action type basic objects \vec{F}_{t+2} and \vec{I}_{t+2} consciously perceived by $3.I^M$ and defined through Equations IV.60 and IV.61, respectively.

(f) In view of the Feedback process described in Section IV-M, the bare basic object $\langle \vec{K}^{(4)} \rangle_\beta \in \langle \widetilde{SEL}(t+2) \rangle_\beta$ may not be Feedback outputted; and if indeed outputted could have its consciousness level changed. Let us suppose it is outputted but changed, say, to produce $\vec{K}^{(5)} = \left\{ \vec{K} \mid \mathbf{c} : \beta_1 \sigma_1 (\eta_1 \chi_1 + \epsilon_1) C_0 \right\} \in \widetilde{SEL}^c(t+2)$ (defined through Equation IV.63) where β_1 is the change factor. Learning from Dynamics item E.1.2.l and the given, the sensory type $\vec{K}^{(5)}$ is different to all the other elements of $\widetilde{SEL}^c(t+2)$. Thus, by Equations IV.63, IV.64 and Theorem D.3, it is in, but different to all the other elements of, $\widetilde{FBK}(t+2)$ which is bare unique based on Theorem E.10.

[3] Equation IV.12 expresses Actuators as acquiring \vec{F}_{t+2} and \vec{I}_{t+2} at $t+3$.

[4] Applying the last $3.I^M$ location mentioned in Dynamics item E.1.0 and the result of Dynamics item E.1.3 to Equations IV.14 and IV.15 proves Foot as moving $3.I^M$ to Environment location $x = \tau + 1 = 2$. Thus, Environment issues to Sensors the information $ENV(\tau + 1, \tau + 1)$.

As illustrated in this episode, the attributed consciousness level to the bare basic object \vec{K} varies from C_0 to $\alpha_1 C_0$, where $\alpha_1 = \beta_1 \sigma_1 (\eta_1 \chi_1 + \epsilon_1)$, when \vec{K} belongs from $\langle \widetilde{FBK}(t-2) \rangle_\beta$ to $\langle \widetilde{FBK}(t+2) \rangle_\beta$, i.e., the variation occurs at $\tau = 1$ and in one cycle (a 3^M process that lasts one external time unit Δ). This consciousness level dynamics is expressed as $\langle \vec{K}^{(5)} \rangle_\gamma = \alpha_1 \langle \vec{K} \rangle_\gamma = \alpha_1 C_0$ where α_1 is referred to as the *consciousness level gain* in one external time unit Δ and corresponds to $\tau = 1$. Let the assumption in Dynamics item E.1.2.f (that \vec{K} is Feedback outputted) also be true in every succeeding cycles till $\tau = N \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Thus, at $1 \leq \tau \leq N$, the Feedback output $\widetilde{FBK}(\tau\Delta + 2)$ can be shown by mathematical induction to contain $\vec{K}^{(5\tau)}$ with $\langle \vec{K}^{(5\tau)} \rangle_\gamma = C_0 \prod_{i=1}^{\tau} \alpha_i$ where α_i is the consciousness level gain at $\tau = i$.

Suppose $\langle \vec{K}^{(5\tau)} \rangle_\gamma < THR$, $\forall 1 \ll M \leq \tau < N$, $M \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, and $\langle \vec{K}^{(5N)} \rangle_\gamma \geq THR$, i.e., \vec{K} is subconsciously perceived until just before $\tau = N$ when it is consciously perceived by $3.I^M$. Further, suppose that the average consciousness level gain over the external time index i , $1 \leq i \leq \tau$, is $\alpha = \mathbf{E}[\alpha_i] \gg \sigma[\alpha_i]$ with $\tau \gg 1$, such that using Theorem E.20 obtains

$$\langle \vec{K}^{(5\tau)} \rangle_\gamma \approx C_0 \alpha^\tau \triangleq E_0 \alpha^{\tau'} = E_0 \exp^{\tau' \ln|\alpha|} \quad (\text{E.14})$$

where $E_0 = C_0 \alpha^M$, and $\tau' = \tau - M$. The latter equation and the last episode imply that, driven by the Environment information $ENV(i, i)$, $\forall 1 \leq i \leq \tau$: (a) The consciousness level attribute of \vec{K} may vary approximately exponentially on

the time scale $\tau \geq M$ with a factor of $\ln|\alpha|$, which is akin to the so called *Lyapunov exponent* [11]. (b) If $\alpha > 1$ then the consciousness level may approximately exponentially rise from the subconscious (when $E_0 < THR$ and $\tau' = 0$) towards the consciousness level threshold THR ; and if $0 < \alpha < 1$ and $E_0 > THR$ the converse may occur. (c) The exponential rate of ascent or descent of the consciousness level is proportional to $|\ln|\alpha||$. (d) The factor η_τ (defined in Equation E.13 with $\tau = 1$) is related to the environmentally-triggered and Sensors-issued basic object $\vec{S}_{\tau\Delta+1}$ (defined in Dynamics item E.1.1.s with $\tau = 1$) which therefore influences the consciousness dynamics of the bare basic object \vec{K} . ■

F. Categorization

Let us now explore how $3.I^M$ performs authentic generalization of SIETBOs.

Dynamics F.1: $3.I^M$ can create an authentic generalization out of a category of SIETBOs.

Illustration A prototype (e.g., the one defined in Equation III.25) is demonstrated below to be formed by $3.I^M$ over the episode that transpires at external time index range $1 \leq \tau \leq T \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. The episode is itemized below and illustrated in Table XVI which has similar format to that of Figure XV. Let the integral item label below be added to $t = \Delta$ to obtain the internal time at which the event described by the item occurs. The episode comprising events are as follows:

[0] Theorem E.10 implies $3.I^M$ as being at Environment location $x = 1$, such that, Environment issues to Sensors the information $ENV(1, 1)$ defined in Equation IV.1.

[1] This information is processed as follows:

(s) Theorem E.1 justifies the 1-new Sensors state $\widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$ as bare and type unique. Let the SIETBO $\vec{S}_{t+1} = \{\widehat{S}_{t+1} \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t+1, \mathbf{o} : \text{" "}\} \in \widetilde{SEN}(t+1)$ where $\widehat{S}_{t+1} = [\text{"eyeVissn"}, IMG(1)]$.

(σ) Referring to Equation II.9, $\widetilde{SUM}(t+1) = \widetilde{SEN}(t+1) \cup \widetilde{FBK}(t-2)$ where, by Theorem E.10, $\widetilde{FBK}(t-2)$ is 1-old and bare unique.

(m) Employing the details in Dynamics items F.1.1.s and 1.σ to Theorem E.2 proves $\widetilde{MEM}^o(t+1)$ and $\widetilde{MEM}^w(t+1) = \widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+1) \ni \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(1)}$ as different bare unique sets and comprised of 1-old and 1-new basic objects, respectively.

(t) Using the results in Dynamics item F.1.1.m to Theorem E.3 justifies $\widetilde{XFM}(t+1)$ as bare unique.

(c) As in Dynamics item E.1.1.c, $\widetilde{NSL}(t+1) \ni \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(1)}$ is type unique.

[2] The last Memory, Transformer and Contrector outputs are processed as follows:

(n) Applying the information in Dynamics items F.1.1.t and 1.c to Theorem E.6 confirms the Interactor state $\widetilde{INT}(t+2)$ as bare unique.

(l) Applying the Dynamics item F.1.1.c information to the Figure 5 algorithm and then using Equations IV.58 and IV.59 yield $\vec{S}_{t+1}^{(2)} \in \widetilde{SEL}(t+2)$ which is bare unique based on Theorem E.8.

(x) As explained in Section IV-L, Executioner produces the action type different basic objects \vec{F}_{t+2} and \vec{I}_{t+2} consciously perceived by $3.I^M$ and defined through Equations IV.60 and IV.61, respectively.

(f) Considering the Feedback process described in Section IV-M, $\langle \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(2)} \rangle_\beta$ may not be Feedback outputted; and if indeed outputted could have its consciousness level changed. Let us suppose it is outputted but changed, say, to produce $\vec{S}_{t+1}^{(3)} \in \widetilde{FBK}(t+2)$ which is bare unique based on Theorem E.10.

[3] Equation IV.12 expresses Actuators as acquiring \vec{F}_{t+2} and \vec{I}_{t+2} at $t+3$.

[4] Applying the last $3.I^M$ location mentioned in Dynamics item F.1.0 and the results in Dynamics item F.1.3 to Equations IV.14 and IV.15 proves Foot as moving $3.I^M$ to the Environment location $x = 2$. Thus, Environment issues to Sensors the information $ENV(2, 2)$.

[5] This information is processed as follows:

(s) Theorem E.1 verifies the 2-new Sensors state $\widetilde{SEN}(t+5)$ as bare and type unique. Let the SIETBO $\vec{S}_{t+5} = \{\widehat{S}_{t+5} \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t+5, \mathbf{o} : \text{" "}\} \in \widetilde{SEN}(t+5)$ with $\widehat{S}_{t+5} = [\text{"eyeVissn"}, IMG(2)]$.

(σ) Considering Equation II.9, $\widetilde{SUM}(t+5) = \widetilde{SEN}(t+5) \cup \widetilde{FBK}(t+2)$ where, based on the details in Dynamics items F.1.2.f and 5.s, $\vec{S}_{t+1}^{(3)} \in \widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t+2)$ (defined through Equation E.2) which is 2-old and bare unique.

(m) Employing the details in Dynamics items F.1.5.s and 5.σ to Theorem E.2 proves $\widetilde{MEM}^o(t+5) = \widetilde{FBK}^\delta(t+2) \ni \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(3)}$ and $\widetilde{MEM}^w(t+5) = \widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+5) \ni \vec{S}_{t+5}^{(1)}$ as different bare unique sets and comprised of 2-old and 2-new basic objects, respectively.

Let us decompose $\widetilde{MEM}^o(t+5) = \vec{A} \cup \vec{B} \cup \vec{C} \cup \vec{D} \cup \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(3)}$ where the components do not have common element; $\langle \vec{A} \rangle_\beta = \langle \vec{S}_{t+5}^{(1)} \otimes (\vec{S}_{t+1}^{(3)} \cup \vec{B}) \rangle_\beta = \langle \vec{O}_{t+5} \rangle_\beta$; every element of $\langle \vec{S}_{t+5}^{(1)} \otimes (\vec{A} \cup \vec{C} \cup \vec{D}) \rangle_\beta$ is not equal to $\langle \vec{O}_{t+5} \rangle_\beta$; $\langle \vec{S}_{t+5}^{(1)} \oplus \cup \vec{C} \rangle_\beta = \langle \vec{O}_{t+5} \rangle_\beta$; and every element of $\langle \vec{S}_{t+5}^{(1)} \oplus (\vec{A} \cup \vec{B} \cup \vec{D} \cup \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(3)}) \rangle_\beta$ is not equal to $\langle \vec{O}_{t+5} \rangle_\beta$.

(t) Thus, applying the details in Dynamics item F.1.5.m to Equations IV.32 to IV.37 yields $\vec{S}_{t+5}^{(1)} \otimes (\vec{B} \cup \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(3)}) \cup (\vec{S}_{t+5}^{(1)} \oplus \vec{C}) \triangleq \vec{P}''$ which is therefore a partition of $\widetilde{XFM}''(t+5)$.

Knowing $\widetilde{MEM}^o(t+5)$ as bare unique, then $\vec{A} \cup \Gamma_{[CNM]}(\vec{P}'') \triangleq \vec{P}'$ is a partition of $\widetilde{XFM}'(t+5)$. Therefore, $\Gamma_{[CNL]}(\vec{P}') \triangleq \vec{O}_{t+5} \in \widetilde{XFM}^c(t+5)$ which is bare unique based on Theorem E.3. To obtain an authentic generalization, $\vec{S}_{t+5}^{(1)}$ and $\vec{S}_{t+1}^{(3)}$ are such that $\vec{O}_{t+5} \neq \hat{0}$.

(c) Following the approach in Dynamics item E.1.1.c yields $\vec{S}_{t+5}^{(1)} \in \widetilde{NSL}(t+5)$ which is type unique.

[6] The last Memory, Transformer and Contrector outputs are processed as follows:

(n) Dynamics item F.1.5.c shows $\widetilde{NSL}(t+5)$ as type unique, such that, applying the Dynamics item F.1.5.t details to

TABLE XVI: Category Formation

$t+$	$\langle \widetilde{SMS}(t) \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \widetilde{SUM}(t) \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \widetilde{MEM}^o(t) \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \widetilde{MEM}^w(t) \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \widetilde{XFM}(t) \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \widetilde{NSL}(t) \rangle_\beta$
1	$\langle \vec{S}_{t+1} \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \vec{S}_{t+1} \rangle_\beta$		$\langle \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(1)} \rangle_\beta$		$\langle \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(1)} \rangle_\beta$
5	$\langle \vec{S}_{t+5} \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \vec{S}_{t+5} \rangle_\beta, \langle \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(3)} \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(3)} \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \vec{S}_{t+5}^{(1)} \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \vec{S}_{t+5}^{(1)} \otimes \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(3)} \rangle_\beta = \langle \vec{O}_{t+5} \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \vec{S}_{t+5}^{(1)} \rangle_\beta$
9	$\langle \vec{S}_{t+9} \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \vec{S}_{t+9} \rangle_\beta, \langle \vec{O}_{t+5}^{(4)} \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \vec{O}_{t+5}^{(4)} \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \vec{S}_{t+9}^{(1)} \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \vec{S}_{t+9}^{(1)} \otimes \vec{O}_{t+5}^{(4)} \rangle_\beta = \langle \vec{O}_{t+9} \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \vec{S}_{t+9}^{(1)} \rangle_\beta$
$t+$		$\langle \widetilde{INT}(t) \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \widetilde{SEL}(t) \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \widetilde{XEC}(t) \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \widetilde{FBK}(t) \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \widetilde{ACT}(t) \rangle_\beta$
2			$\langle \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(2)} \rangle_\beta$	$\widehat{F}_{t+2}, \widehat{I}_{t+2}$	$\langle \vec{S}_{t+1}^{(3)} \rangle_\beta$	
3						$\widehat{F}_{t+2}, \widehat{I}_{t+2}$
6		$\langle \vec{O}_{t+5}^{(2)} \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \vec{O}_{t+5}^{(3)} \rangle_\beta$	$\widehat{F}_{t+6}, \widehat{I}_{t+6}$	$\langle \vec{O}_{t+5}^{(4)} \rangle_\beta$	
7						$\widehat{F}_{t+6}, \widehat{I}_{t+6}$
10		$\langle \vec{O}_{t+9}^{(2)} \rangle_\beta$	$\langle \vec{O}_{t+9}^{(3)} \rangle_\beta$	$\widehat{F}_{t+10}, \widehat{I}_{t+10}$	$\langle \vec{O}_{t+9}^{(4)} \rangle_\beta$	

Equations IV.47 to IV.49 yields $\langle \widetilde{NSL}(t+5) \mid \textcircled{P} \mid \vec{O}_{t+5} \rangle = \langle \vec{S}_{t+5}^{(1)} \mid \textcircled{P} \mid \vec{O}_{t+5} \rangle \triangleq \vec{O}_{t+5}^{(1)}$ which, by Theorem E.6, is a singleton set/partition. Thus, by Equations III.51 and IV.46, $\Gamma_{[CNL]} \left(\left(\widetilde{NSL}(t+5) \mid \textcircled{P} \mid \vec{O}_{t+5} \right) \right) + \epsilon_6 \triangleq \vec{O}_{t+5}^{(2)} \in \widetilde{INT}(t+6)$ where ϵ_6 is a random value that satisfies $-MXR \leq \epsilon_6 \leq MXR$. The state $\widetilde{INT}(t+6)$ is bare unique based on Theorem E.6.

- (l) The Figure 5 algorithm could change the consciousness level of $\langle \vec{O}_{t+5}^{(2)} \rangle_\beta$, say, to produce $\vec{O}_{t+5}^{(3)}$ which, based on the results in Dynamics items F.1.5.t and 5.c, is different to all elements of $\widetilde{NSL}(t+5)$. Thus, by Equations IV.58 and IV.59, $\vec{O}_{t+5}^{(3)} \in \widetilde{SEL}(t+6)$ which is bare unique based on Theorem E.8.
- (x) Executioner produces the action type different basic objects \vec{F}_{t+6} and \vec{I}_{t+6} consciously perceived by $3.I^M$ and defined through Equations IV.60 and IV.61, respectively.
- (f) Considering the Feedback process, $\langle \vec{O}_{t+5}^{(3)} \rangle_\beta$ may not be Feedback outputted; and if indeed outputted could have its consciousness level changed. Let us suppose it is outputted but changed, say, to produce $\vec{O}_{t+5}^{(4)} \in \widetilde{FBK}(t+6)$ which is bare unique based on Theorem E.10.

[7] By Equation IV.12, Actuators acquires \vec{F}_{t+6} and \vec{I}_{t+6} .

[8] Using the last $3.I^M$ location mentioned in Dynamics item F.1.4 and the results in Dynamics item F.1.7 to Equations IV.14 and IV.15 proves Foot as moving $3.I^M$ to the Environment location $x = 3$. Thus, Environment issues to Sensors the information $ENV(3, 3)$.

[9] This information is processed as follows:

(s) Theorem E.1 justifies the Sensors state $\widetilde{SEN}(t+9)$ as bare and type unique. Let the SIETBO $\vec{S}_{t+9} = \{ \vec{S}_{t+9} \mid \mathbf{c} : THR, \mathbf{p} : 1, \mathbf{t} : t+9, \mathbf{o} : \text{" " } \} \in \widetilde{SEN}(t+9)$ with $\vec{S}_{t+9} = [\text{"eyeVissn"}, IMG(3)]$.

(σ) Considering the details in Dynamics items F.1.6.f and 9.s, $\vec{O}_{t+5}^{(4)} \in \widetilde{FBK}^o(t+6)$.

(m) Employing the details in Dynamics items F.1.9.s and 9.σ to Theorem E.2 justifies $\widetilde{MEM}^o(t+9) = \widetilde{FBK}^o(t+6) \ni \vec{O}_{t+5}^{(4)}$ and $\widetilde{MEM}^w(t+9) = \widetilde{SEN}^{(1)}(t+9) \ni \vec{S}_{t+9}^{(1)}$ as different bare unique sets and comprised of 3-old and 3-new basic objects, respectively.

(t) Implementing the approach in Dynamics items F.1.5.m and 5.t yields $\langle \vec{S}_{t+9}^{(1)} \otimes \vec{O}_{t+5}^{(4)} \rangle_\beta \triangleq \langle \vec{O}_{t+9} \rangle_\beta \in \widetilde{XFM}^c(t+9)_\beta$ which is bare unique based on Theorem E.3. To obtain an authentic generalization, $\vec{S}_{t+9}^{(1)}$ and $\vec{O}_{t+5}^{(4)}$ are such that $\vec{O}_{t+9} \neq \hat{\theta}$.

(c) Pursuing the approach in Dynamics item E.1.1.c obtains $\vec{S}_{t+9}^{(1)} \in \widetilde{NSL}(t+9)$ which is type unique.

[10] The last Memory, Transformer and Contrector outputs are processed as follows:

(n) Dynamics item F.1.9.c shows $\widetilde{NSL}(t+9)$ as type unique, such that, applying the Dynamics item F.1.9.t details and Equations IV.47 to IV.49 yields $\langle \widetilde{NSL}(t+9) \mid \textcircled{P} \mid \vec{O}_{t+9} \rangle = \langle \vec{S}_{t+9}^{(1)} \mid \textcircled{P} \mid \vec{O}_{t+9} \rangle \triangleq \vec{O}_{t+9}^{(1)}$ which, by Theorem E.6, is a singleton set/partition. Thus, by Equations III.51 and IV.46, $\Gamma_{[CNL]} \left(\left(\widetilde{NSL}(t+9) \mid \textcircled{P} \mid \vec{O}_{t+9} \right) \right) + \epsilon_9 \triangleq \vec{O}_{t+9}^{(2)}$ where ϵ_9 is a random value that satisfies $-MXR \leq \epsilon_9 \leq MXR$. The state $\widetilde{INT}(t+10)$ is bare unique based on Theorem E.6.

(l) The Figure 5 algorithm could change the consciousness level of $\langle \vec{O}_{t+9}^{(2)} \rangle_\beta$, say, to produce $\vec{O}_{t+9}^{(3)}$ which, based on the results in Dynamics items F.1.9.t and 9.c, is different to all elements of $\widetilde{NSL}(t+9)$. Thus, by Equations IV.58 and IV.59, $\vec{O}_{t+9}^{(3)} \in \widetilde{SEL}(t+9)$ which is bare unique based on Theorem E.8.

(x) Executioner produces the action type different basic objects \vec{F}_{t+10} and \vec{I}_{t+10} consciously perceived by $3.I^M$ and defined through Equations IV.60 and IV.61, respectively.

(f) Considering the Feedback process, $\langle \vec{O}_{t+9}^{(3)} \rangle_\beta$ may not be Feedback outputted; and if indeed outputted could have its consciousness level changed. Let us suppose it is outputted but changed, say, to produce $\vec{O}_{t+9}^{(4)} \in \widetilde{FBK}(t+10)$ which is bare unique based on Theorem E.10.

As cited in Dynamics items F.1.5.t and 9.t, $\widehat{S}_{t+1} \otimes \widehat{S}_{t+5} = \widehat{O}_{t+5}$ and $\widehat{S}_{t+9} \otimes \widehat{O}_{t+5} = \widehat{O}_{t+9}$, such that, $\widehat{O}_{t+9} = \prod_{i=1}^{[3:\infty]} \widehat{S}_{t+4i-3}$. Suppose $\vec{O}_{t+9}^{(4)}$ is consciously perceived by $3.I^M$ and $\widehat{O}_{t+9} \neq \widehat{S}_{t+4i-3}, \forall 1 \leq i \leq 3$. Thus, $3.I^M$ is capable of creating the prototype \widehat{O}_{t+9} out of the category $\widehat{S}_{t+1} \cup \widehat{S}_{t+5} \cup \widehat{S}_{t+9}$.

The methodology applied in Dynamics items F.1.3 to 6.f can be utilized for every $\tau, 1 < \tau \leq T$, to prove $3.I^M$ as capable

of creating the prototype $\widehat{C}_{t+4T-3} = \prod_{i=1}^{[T:\infty]} \widehat{R}_{t+4i-3}$ out of the category $\cup_{i=1}^T \widehat{R}_{t+4i-3}$ where \widehat{R}_{t+4i-3} is the SIETBO at $t+4i-3$, and $\widehat{C}_{t+4T-3} \neq \widehat{R}_{t+4i-3}$, $\forall 1 \leq i \leq T$. ■

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